

**BUNDESMINISTERIUM
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Report 2012

**Trends and Sources of
Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents
in Humans, Foodstuffs, Animals and
Feedingstuffs**

Austria

**Including information on foodborne outbreaks,
antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic agents and some
pathogenic microbiological agents**

AUSTRIA

The Report referred to in Article 9 of Directive 2003/99/EC

**TRENDS AND SOURCES OF ZONOSSES AND ZONOTIC AGENTS
IN HUMANS, FOODSTUFFS, ANIMALS AND FEEDINGSTUFFS**

**Including information on foodborne outbreaks, antimicrobial
resistance in zoonotic agents and some pathogenic microbiological
agents**

IN 2012

1. Information on the Reporting and Monitoring System

Country: Austria

Reporting Year: 2012

This report was prepared by the Department for Statistics and the Department for Data Management of the area Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES. Following Institutions and Laboratories were involved:

Institutions and laboratories involved in monitoring

Authorities		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Central Veterinary Services	Federal Ministry of Health	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals; Revision of the draft of the Trend Report; Approval of the Trend Report for Submission
Food Office	Federal Ministry of Health	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
DG Public Health	Federal Ministry of Health	Validation of data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks; revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Feed Office	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, the Environment and Watermanagement	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Provincial Veterinary Services	9 provinces, one Veterinary Service per province	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals
Local/District health authorities	Part of each local administration authority ("Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde"); one physician per district	Collection and entry of the data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks

Institutes		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Department for Statistics and the Department for Data Management of the area Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment (DSR)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Compilation, validation, preparation, data entry and submission of the Zoonoses Trend Report (Reporting officer, national reporter); Analysis of laboratory results for antimicrobial resistance of Salmonella spp., Campylobacter spp., Enterococcus faecalis/faecium and E. coli; Mapping of food and feed data; Creation of xml-files
Statistics Austria	The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions.	Demographic and livestock census data

Human Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Centre for Salmonella Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for Campylobacter, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of Campylobacter from food and animals, antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Centre for Tuberculosis, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in humans
National Reference Center for E. coli including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals

Human Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Centre for Listeria Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning listeriosis in humans
National Reference Centre for Yersinia, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning yersiniosis in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Toxoplasmosis, Echinococcosis, Toxocarosis and other Parasitic Diseases; Department of Medical Parasitology; Institute of Specific Prophylaxis and Tropical Medicine; Center for Physiology, Pathophysiology and Immunology	Medical University of Vienna	Laboratory data concerning parasitic diseases in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning brucellosis in humans and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies in humans and animals

Food Control Institutes		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Official Food Control Laboratories (ILMU)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz, Salzburg and Vienna	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Food Safety Department of the City of Vienna	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Institute for Environment and Food Safety of the State of Vorarlberg	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Carinthian Institute for Food Analysis and Quality Control	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs

Food Control Institutes		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Centre for Salmonella Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for Campylobacter, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of Campylobacter from food and animals, antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Centre for E. coli including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Listeria Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning listeriosis in food
National Reference Centre for Yersinia, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning yersiniosis in food

Veterinary Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in animals
National Reference Centre for Salmonella Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for Campylobacter, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of Campylobacter from food and animals, antimicrobial resistance testing

Veterinary Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial resistance, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Testing for antimicrobial resistance of E. coli and enterococci from animals
National Reference Centre for E. coli including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning brucellosis in humans and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Trichinellosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Innsbruck	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning trichinellosis in animals
Institutes for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz and Moedling	Data concerning investigations in animals; bacteriological investigation in slaughtered animals
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies in humans and animals
Austrian Poultry Health Data (PHD)	Association installed by law, running different programs e.g. salmonella control and hygiene programs, Control of veterinarians and poultry farmers	Data concerning the Austrian poultry industry

Feed Control Institute		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Institute for Animal Nutrition and Feed, Linz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning feeding stuff
National Reference Centre for Salmonella Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans and antimicrobial resistance testing

PREFACE

This report is submitted to the European Commission in accordance with Article 9 of Council Directive 2003/99/EC1. The information has also been forwarded to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

The report contains information on trends and sources of zoonoses and zoonotic agents in Austria during the year 2012. The information covers the occurrence of these diseases and agents in humans, animals, foodstuffs and in some cases also in feedingstuffs. In addition the report includes data on antimicrobial resistance in some zoonotic agents and commensal bacteria as well as information on epidemiological investigations of foodborne outbreaks. Complementary data on susceptible animal populations in the country is also given.

The information given covers zoonoses that are important for public health in the whole European Community as well as zoonoses which are relevant on the basis of the national epidemiological situation.

The report describes the monitoring systems in place and the prevention and control strategies applied in the country. For some zoonoses this monitoring is based on legal requirements laid down by the Community Legislation, while for the other zoonoses national approaches are applied.

The report presents the results of the examinations carried out in the reporting year. A national evaluation of the epidemiological situation, with special reference to trends and sources of zoonotic infections, is given. Whenever possible, the relevance of findings in foodstuffs and animals to zoonoses cases in humans is evaluated.

The information covered by this report is used in the annual Community Summary Report on zoonoses that is published each year by EFSA.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AGES	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety
BMSK	Federal Ministry for Social Security, Generations and Consumer Protection
CC-INFE	Competence Centre for Infectious Disease Epidemiology
EHEC	Enterohemorrhagic E. coli
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EMS	Epidemiological Notification System for human notifiable diseases ("epidemiologisches Meldesystem")
FMH	Federal Ministry of Health
ILMU	Official Food Control Laboratories, AGES
IMED	Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, AGES
IVET	Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, AGES
MOH	Federal Ministry of Health
NRC	National Reference Centre
NRL	National Reference Laboratory
OIE	World organisation for animal health
PHD	Poultry Health Data
TESSy	the European Surveillance System
VIS	Veterinary Information System
VTEC	Verotoxin producing E. coli

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3. Animal Populations

3.1. Information on susceptible animal population 2012

Sources of information

The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions. The data for this report are available from an online database established by Statistics Austria.

Herds, flocks, holdings, stocks

Cattle: The number of holdings and animals is based on the official database for cattle.

Equids, Pigs, Sheep, Goats and Farmed Deer: The number of holdings and animals is based on the yearly full survey for pig, sheep and goats of the Veterinary Information System (VIS).

Poultry: The number of holdings and animals is based on a random sample survey performed by Statistics Austria (farm structure survey). The last random sample survey was performed 2007.

Slaughters

Cattle, Equids: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), performed by Statistics Austria.

Pigs: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), combined with not-examined slaughters (out of pig-random-sample-surveys) performed by Statistics Austria.

Sheep & Goats: The number of slaughters is based on an expert-model carried out by Statistics Austria.

Poultry: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly full survey in main poultry-slaughterhouses performed by Statistics Austria.

Dates the figures relate to and the content of the figures

Data are received from Statistics Austria, only poultry data from QGV.

Definitions used for different types of animals, herds, flocks and holdings as well as the types covered by the information

Cattle: BGBl. II Nr. 147/2009 (Statistiken über den Viehbestand)

Swine, Sheep and Goats: BGBl. II Nr. 291/2009 (Tierkennzeichnungs- und Registrierungsverordnung 2009)

Poultry: BGBl. II Nr. 310/2007 (Erstellung der Statistik über die Agrarstruktur und den Viehbestand im Jahr 2007); BGBl. II Nr. 356/2003 (Erhebung der Geflügelschlachtungen in Betrieben mit min. 5000 Vorjahres-Geflügelschlachtungen)

Geographical distribution and size distribution of the herds, flocks and holdings

Pigs: 97.15 % of all pigs are kept in 84.46 % of the holdings that are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria;

Sheep: 73.04 % of the sheep holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 74.99 % of the sheep are kept there.

Goats: 70.99 % of the goat holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 78.25 % of the goats are kept there.

Additional information

Nil

Table 1 Susceptible animal populations: number of herds and holdings rearing animals, 2012

	Animals species	date	Unit	Number	comments
in total	Cattle (bovine animals)	01.04.2012	holding	69.430	64.258 with birth before 1.04.2010
in total	Cattle (bovine animals)	01.04.2012	animal	1.976.698	920.483 with birth before 1.04.2010
in total	Cattle (bovine animals)		slaughter animal (heads)	609.673	"cattle" without "calves"
	Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	01.12.2012	animal	628.715	"calves" & "young cattle" (under 1 year)
	Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)		slaughter animal (heads)	70.099	"calves" only
	Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals	01.12.2012	animal	274.755	"male cattle" & "heifers for slaughtering" > 1 year ("bulls for breeding" not seperable)
	Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals		slaughter animal (heads)	410.623	"male cattle" & "heifers" without "cows"
in total	Pigs	01.04.2012	holding	29.079	
in total	Pigs	01.04.2012	animal	3.016.658	
in total	Pigs		slaughter animal (heads)	5.432.959	5.396.345 (only examined)
	Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	01.04.2012	holding	6.874	
	Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	01.04.2012	animal	265.733	
	Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows		slaughter animal (heads)	93.708	
	Pigs - fattening pigs	01.04.2012	holding	22.032	
	Pigs - fattening pigs	01.04.2012	animal	1.117.888	
	Pigs - fattening pigs		slaughter animal (heads)	5.339.251	
in total	Sheep	01.04.2012	holding	16.113	
in total	Sheep	01.04.2012	animal	424.707	
in total	Sheep		slaughter animal (heads)	289.533	130.756 (only examined)
	Sheep - animals over 1 year	01.04.2012	holding	15.714	
	Sheep - animals over 1 year	01.04.2012	animal	247.634	
	Sheep - animals over 1 year		slaughter animal (heads)	65.819	
	Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	01.04.2012	holding	13.030	
	Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	01.04.2012	animal	177.073	
	Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)		slaughter animal (heads)	223.714	
in total	Goats	01.04.2012	holding	10.671	
in total	Goats	01.04.2012	animal	91.206	

Animal Populations

	Animals species	date	Unit	Number	comments
in total	Goats		slaughter animal (heads)	58.133	5.147 (only examined)
	Goats - animals over 1 year	01.04.2012	holding	10.413	
	Goats - animals over 1 year	01.04.2012	animal	63.643	
	Goats - animals over 1 year		slaughter animal (heads)	12.368	
	Goats - animals under 1 year	01.04.2012	holding	4.485	
	Goats - animals under 1 year	01.04.2012	animal	27.563	
	Goats - animals under 1 year		slaughter animal (heads)	45.765	
in total	Solipeds, domestic	01.04.2012	holding	15.324	
in total	Solipeds, domestic	01.04.2012	animal	74.122	
in total	Solipeds, domestic		slaughter animal (heads)	933	
in total	Deer - farmed	01.04.2012	holding	1.570	
in total	Deer - farmed	01.04.2012	animal	35.639	
in total	Gallus gallus (fowl)		slaughter animal (heads)	73.394.000	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line		holding	56	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line		animal	867.039	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line		herd/flock	103	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line		holding	11	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line		animal	240.976	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line		herd/flock	25	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers		holding	453	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers		animal	58.103.907	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers		herd/flock	3.510	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens		holding	1.092	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens		animal	8.760.554	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens		herd/flock	2.740	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for		holding	56	

Animal Populations

	Animals species	date	Unit	Number	comments
	broiler production line				
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line		animal	867.039	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line		herd/flock	103	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line		holding	11	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line		animal	240.976	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line		herd/flock	25	
in total	Turkeys		holding	135	
in total	Turkeys		animal	2.464.348	
in total	Turkeys		herd/flock	375	
	Turkeys - meat production flocks		holding	135	
	Turkeys - meat production flocks		animal	2.464.348	
	Turkeys - meat production flocks		herd/flock	375	

* Some holdings keep sheep and goats together. Thus the sum of holdings in total with sheep and goats amounts to 23.787.

4. Information on Specific Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents

The World Health Organization defines zoonoses as “those diseases and infections which are naturally transmitted between vertebrate animals and man.” Foodstuffs often serve as vehicles of zoonotic infections. Zoonotic agents include viruses, bacteria, fungi, parasites or other biological entities that are likely to cause zoonoses.

Collection of human cases

Starting with January 1st 2009 a new reporting system, the **epidemiological reporting system** (Epidemiologisches Meldesystem, EMS) has been put in operation at the MOH. The physicians report all notifiable diseases (case based) to the local health authorities which are part of the local administration authorities (“Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde”). The physicians working at the local health authorities (public health officers) have to enter the data of the human cases of all notifiable diseases in the data base EMS including all relevant variables and laboratory results (case based). In the near future all laboratories will enter the results of their laboratory work in EMS via a gateway to streamline the process. Beginning with 2011 the national reference laboratories dealing with zoonotic diseases already entered their laboratory data in EMS.

EMS is the one and only database for notifiable diseases in the human sector in Austria. This system is also the standard gateway for reporting to ECDC (TESSy). A short report is also extracted and compiled using EMS which is published nationwide monthly and once a year by the Federal Ministry of Health online on the BMG-homepage:

http://bmg.gv.at/home/Schwerpunkte/Krankheiten/Uebertragbare_Krankheiten/Statistiken/Monatliche_Statistik_meldepflichtiger_Infektionskrankheiten_ab_2010).

Additionally data of primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centres are available. The responsible reference centres for zoonotic diseases published the numbers of microbiologically typed primary isolates from humans; due to the fact that more than one bacterial strain could be isolated from single patients these figures may differ from the case numbers notified to the Federal Ministry. As mentioned above, with 2011 these laboratory data were also available in the EMS.

In this report it is indicated which data source has been used for the reporting of human cases for each respective zoonosis.

General Information about the Food Sampling Strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2012 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2012“ (BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2011) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can

comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2012, approximately 26,000 samples were planned (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that has to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail or at the producer.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for specific food items (about 60-65 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2012, 9 food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2011 BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2011). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002. (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). Therefore food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures. Therefore Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs indicates the quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

4.1. Salmonellosis

4.1.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human salmonellosis remains a major health problem in Austria. In 2012, the number of notified salmonellosis cases was the second highest reported food borne pathogen after campylobacteriosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The incidence of human salmonellosis has significantly declined since the peak in 1998/1999. The salmonella-contamination of raw poultry meat has declined from 30 % in 1999 to less than 5.5 % in 2009, and increased in 2012 to 9.3 %. The consumption of eggs and egg products that are contaminated with Salmonella is presumably the main cause of human infection.

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report (table 2) reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to EMS, n = 1,729 cases. This number shows again a reduction compared to the previous year and reflects the success of interventions aimed at combating salmonella.

As compared to the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis (see chapter campylobacteriosis), salmonella is the second most important cause for enteric diseases in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2012, data from feedingstuffs (n = 308; only feedingstuffs for food producing animals, exclusive pet feed) indicate that the prevalence of salmonella remains very low (2 %). None of the tested table eggs or egg products were positive for salmonella, although infected eggs pose the main vehicle for human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

There were EU programs implemented to control the contamination of Salmonella in poultry, most programs involved meat and egg production. The effort of the intervention is directed toward improving the sanitation of breeding flocks and laying flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks according to EU legislation.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continue the efforts already started, especially to improve harmonization of monitoring and control programs along the food chain.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents, which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obligated to send these strains to the respective national reference laboratory for typing and comparative analysis.

4.1.2. Salmonellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following four symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Fever
- Abdominal pain
- Vomiting

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of Salmonella (other than *S. Typhi* and *S. Paratyphi*) from stool or blood

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Sample material is processed as described in „Richtlinien für die Diagnostik von Salmonellen (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 11-12)“.

At the National Reference Centre for Salmonella (NRC Salmonella), all isolates are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor Scheme. And further all *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. Additionally the antimicrobial resistance testing by disk diffusion method is performed with each isolate.

Notification system in place

Notification of salmonellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 1989 and 1990, human infections with salmonella increased markedly in Austria. After a peak in 1992, the incidence of salmonella illness decreased, but the number of infections has remained at a high level until 2002. Since that year the number of laboratory confirmed cases of human Salmonella cases has decreased by 79 % (2012: 1,729 notified cases).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2012, the number of human laboratory confirmed cases of salmonellosis notified to EMS decreased compared to the years before.

The proportion of *S. Enteritidis* isolates (based on data of the NRC Salmonella, table 26, because for about one fourth of the notified salmonellosis cases in EMS the serotype information was not available, table 2), out of all Salmonella isolates, decreased in 2012 to 49 % (compared to 57 % in 2011). The most frequently identified Enteritidis phage types in 2012 were (table 27): PT8 (52 %), PT21 (7.3 %) and PT13a (6.1 %). The reduction of salmonellosis cases is only due to *S. Enteritidis*, all other serotypes remained more or less constant between 1,200 and 947 cases (2002 to 2012).

The proportion of *S. Typhimurium* isolates reported increased slightly to 13.9 % (2011: 13.1 %) but decreased in absolute numbers: 241 isolates in 2012, 291 isolates in 2011 (NRC Salmonella, table 26).

Additionally 95 isolates of *S. Typhimurium* monophasic strain (antigenic formula = 1,4,5,12 : i : -) were found in humans.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2012, the number of notified human laboratory confirmed cases of campylobacteriosis again exceeded the number of salmonellosis cases. The reduction in the number of human salmonellosis cases is due to EU wide control programs and establishment of goals for the reduction of prevalences of salmonella in laying hen flocks, broilers and turkeys.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria on monthly and yearly basis. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH

Table 2 Salmonellosis cases from humans - serotype distribution (EMS), 2012

Serotype	N	Cases		
		Incidence/100,000 population	Imported cases	Unknown status
Salmonellosis	1729	20,48	337	133
Enteritidis	673	7,97	138	54
Typhimurium	162	1,92	19	11
Stanley	103	1,22	5	7
Monophasic 1.4.[5].12:l:-	65	0,77	6	8
Infantis	42	0,50	7	2
Paratyphi B var. L(+) tartrate+ (variant Java)	22	0,26	4	1
Thompson	15	0,18	1	2
Kentucky	14	0,17	5	1
Saintpaul	12	0,14	1	2
Agona	11	0,13	2	0
Newport	11	0,13	4	1
Coeln	10	0,12	2	1
Muenchen	9	0,11	0	0
Napoli	8	0,09	2	2
Bovismorbificans	7	0,08	4	1
Braenderup	7	0,08	3	0
Kottbus	7	0,08	1	1
Stanleyville	7	0,08	0	0
Group (B) O:4	6	0,07	5	0
Corvallis	5	0,06	3	0
Hadar	5	0,06	1	0
Panama	5	0,06	1	1
Tunis	5	0,06	1	1
Group (C1) O:7	4	0,05	0	0
GroupD	4	0,05	1	0
Mbandaka	4	0,05	3	0
Montevideo	4	0,05	3	0
Oranienburg	4	0,05	1	0
Subspecies IIIb (diarizonae)	4	0,05	0	0
Tennessee	4	0,05	0	0
Virchow	4	0,05	2	1
Bareilly	3	0,04	2	0

Serotype	N	Cases		
		Incidence/100,000 population	Imported cases	Unknown status
Rissen	3	0,04	2	0
Weltevreden	3	0,04	0	0
Choleraesuis	2	0,02	0	0
Gaminara	2	0,02	0	0
Group (D1) O:9	2	0,02	0	0
Haifa	2	0,02	0	1
Indiana	2	0,02	0	0
Javiana	2	0,02	1	0
Kenya	2	0,02	0	0
Litchfield	2	0,02	0	0
Mikawasima	2	0,02	0	0
Monschau	2	0,02	0	0
Schwarzengrund	2	0,02	2	0
Senftenberg	2	0,02	0	0
Subspecies II (salamae)	2	0,02	1	1
Tudu	2	0,02	0	1
Uppsala	2	0,02	0	1
Adelaide	1	0,01	0	0
Anatum	1	0,01	1	0
Baildon	1	0,01	1	0
Bardo	1	0,01	0	1
Bere	1	0,01	0	0
Bispebjerg	1	0,01	1	0
Blockley	1	0,01	0	0
Brancaster	1	0,01	1	0
Brandenburg	1	0,01	0	1
Bredeney	1	0,01	0	0
Cerro	1	0,01	0	0
Chester	1	0,01	1	0
Colindale	1	0,01	1	0
Derby	1	0,01	0	1
Dieppeul	1	0,01	0	0
Edinburg	1	0,01	1	0
Goelzau	1	0,01	1	0
Goettingen	1	0,01	0	0
Goldcoast	1	0,01	0	0
Group O:3,10 (E1)	1	0,01	1	0
Heidelberg	1	0,01	1	0
Hvittingfoss	1	0,01	0	0
Kambole	1	0,01	0	0
Kedougou	1	0,01	0	0
Kisarawe	1	0,01	0	0
Leeuwarden	1	0,01	0	0
Liverpool	1	0,01	1	0
Livingstone	1	0,01	0	0
Mpouto	1	0,01	0	0
Muenster	1	0,01	0	0
Nagoya	1	0,01	1	0
Nottingham	1	0,01	1	0
Obogu	1	0,01	1	0

Serotype	N	Cases		
		Incidence/100,000 population	Imported cases	Unknown status
Ona	1	0,01	0	0
Poona	1	0,01	0	0
Reading	1	0,01	0	0
Stourbridge	1	0,01	0	0
Strathcona	1	0,01	0	0
Subspecies IV (houtenae)	1	0,01	0	0
Szentes	1	0,01	1	0
Telelkebir	1	0,01	0	0
Uganda	1	0,01	0	1
Umbilo	1	0,01	1	0
Unknown	404	4,78	88	37

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

Table 3 Salmonellosis isolates in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2012

Age group	Salmonellosis			S. Enteritidis			S. Typhimurium			monophasic S. Group B (1,4,5,12 : i : -)			other serotypes*		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	51	28	23	8	7	1	4	1	3	0	0	0	39	20	19
1 to 4 years	242	124	118	105	53	52	25	14	11	10	8	2	102	49	53
5 to 14 years	328	193	135	127	67	60	34	23	11	18	13	5	149	90	59
15 to 24 years	226	122	104	100	48	52	15	9	6	8	7	1	103	58	45
25 to 44 years	341	187	154	127	69	58	29	18	11	13	9	4	172	91	81
45 to 64 years	280	133	147	102	44	58	24	14	10	9	2	7	145	73	72
65 years and older	261	104	157	104	37	67	26	16	10	7	1	6	124	50	74
All age groups	1729	891	838	673	325	348	157	95	62	65	40	25	834	431	403

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

Table 4 Salmonellosis isolates in humans – seasonal distribution (EMS), 2012

Month	<i>Salmonella sp.</i>	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	monophasic S. Group B (1,4,5,12 : i : -)	other serotypes*
	Cases	Cases	Cases	Cases	Cases
January	107	44	8	5	50
February	73	28	6	5	34
March	89	34	11	1	43
April	82	36	9	4	33
May	109	55	5	2	47
June	156	89	11	1	55
July	194	63	26	6	99
August	255	90	21	5	139
September	282	96	23	6	157
October	191	67	20	21	83
November	136	53	14	8	61
December	55	18	3	1	33
Total	1729	673	157	65	834

* without SE, ST, monophasic S. Group B

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

4.1.3. Salmonella spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2012 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2012“ (BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2011) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2012, approximately 26,000 samples were planned (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that has to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail or at the producer.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for specific food items (about 60-65 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2012, 9 food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2011 BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2011). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002. (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). Therefore food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures. Therefore Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs indicates the quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelf-life and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat, meat preparations, minced meat, etc.

Defintion of positive finding

A positive sample is a sample from which Salmonella has been isolated.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method ISO 6579:2002 + Cor.1:2004 + Amd.1:2007.

The amount of tested food in general is 25 g. Some exeptions exist, according to the Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 as indicated in Table 5 - Table 18.

All Salmonella isolates are sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella in Graz and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor-Scheme. All S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. Additionally all isolates are tested for their antibiotic susceptibility according to EUCAST. In case of an outbreak situation the stored isolates may be further investigated with pulsed-field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) or multiple-locus variable-number of tandem-repeats analysis (MLVA).

Control program/mechanisms

All isolates have to be sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella in Graz, where the isolates are further analysed and stored.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Whenever Salmonella is detected the isolates are sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella in Graz. Investigation into the source of the contamination is initiated if indicated.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections.

Salmonella spp. was detected in fresh broiler meat samples in 10.3 % (17 out of 165) and in 11.1 % of fresh turkey meat samples (7 out of 63). Segregating these data at sampling stage 31.3 % (5 out of 16) of the broiler meat were positive at processing plant, whereas the majority of positive samples of fresh turkey meat were found at retail (11.3 %).

In samples of meat products from broilers, intended to be eaten cooked, 4.3 % contained Salmonella and of unspecified poultry meat preparations 9% were contaminated. Comparing these values to 2011, an increase of Salmonella in fresh meat samples and a decrease in meat preparations were observed.

In total 1,098 samples of red meat and meat preparations thereof were tested, with only two positive samples for Salmonella in the category meat preparations from pig intended to be eaten cooked, two out of 172, (1 %). In 2010, these meat preparations have been positive in 5 samples out of 496 (1 %) and in 1 sample out of 188 (0.5 %) in 2011.

No Salmonella were found in 669 samples of milk, dairy products and cheeses, as in the years 2007-2011. 1,936 samples of different matrices were tested for Salmonella (Table 10-Table 18), resulting in one positive finding respectively in the categories "cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea" and "spices and herbs".

153 samples of egg products have been tested for Salmonella without any positive findings. Out of the 124 sample units, each containing 25 g of table eggs that were sampled and examined at packing centres or at retail level, no sample was tested positive for salmonella.

The campaigns in 2012 focusing on vegetables and fruits could not identify any positive sample as well (147 samples tested).

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in foodborne outbreaks **Foodborne outbreaks**.

Since January 2012 the Outbreak Detection System (ODS) for the early detection of Salmonellosis has been installed in Austria. Within this tool realtime data on Salmonella isolates are utilized to determine a threshold value. If the number of Salmonella cases of the current week exceeds this threshold, a signal indicates a possible outbreak. This signal enables an early start of outbreak investigations.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-006-12: Salmonella spp. in food – fruits and vegetables - at border control - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

40 samples were taken at the border control (Vienna Airport)

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January - April

Type of specimen taken

Padan leaves, Sadau leaves, Yellow Turmanic, Yodkhea, Cha Om, young green pepper, Morminy fly, Chinese Chive Leaves, lemon grass, tomatoes, strawberries, Pak Waan, Okra, Kra Chai, Tamlueng, others

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

40 samples tested, no sample positive for Salmonella spp.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for VTEC

Campaign A-041-12: Salmonella spp. in food – Egg products - non-ready-to-eat - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - December

Type of specimen taken

Egg products liquid and dried, pasteurized whole eggs

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

107 samples were tested, no sample positive for Salmonella spp.

Campaign A-801-12: Salmonella spp. in food – fruits and vegetables - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May - July

Type of specimen taken

packaged sprouts, strawberries and cutted salad

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of Salmonella spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

99 samples tested, no sample positive for Salmonella spp.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for VTEC

Table 5 Salmonella spp. in poultry meat and meat products, 2012

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bovismorbificans	Salmonella - S. Derby	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis	Salmonella - S. Infantis	Salmonella - S. Kentucky	Salmonella - S. Mbandaka	Salmonella - S. Newport	Salmonella - S. Saintpaul	Salmonella - S. Stanley	Salmonella - S. Tennessee	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium	Salmonella - S. Wellkade
Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - carcass	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	16	5	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	56	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		FR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		HR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		NL	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		SI	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	67	10	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	
	at slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail	DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	38	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from duck - fresh	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		FR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from duck - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail	DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from geese - fresh	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		GB	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	74	8	0	0	3	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	
		DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		HU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from turkey - fresh	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	48	5	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	
		DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		FR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		HU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	
		IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
PL	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0			
Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from turkey - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from turkey - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Table 6 Salmonella spp. in red meat and products thereof, 2012 part 1

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium, monophasic
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
				25	Gram	1	0	0	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	8	0	0	0
				25	Gram	3	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
	Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
at retail		AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	9	0	0	0
	25			Gram	1	0	0	0	
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	33	0	0	0
		SI	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
	at slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat products	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	18	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals and pig - minced meat	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	5	0	0	0
Meat from farmed game - ratites - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	5	0	0	0
				25	Gram	8	0	0	0
		DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products	at retail	LT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
Meat from pig - fresh	at cutting plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	12	0	0	0
				25	Gram	11	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	22	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	11	0	0	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	143	2	1	1
				25	Gram	11	0	0	0
		DE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0	0
				25	Gram	1	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
				25	Gram	1	0	0	0
	unspecified	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
XX		single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten raw	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0	0
				25	Gram	11	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	83	0	0	0
				25	Gram	1	0	0	0

Table 7 Salmonella spp. in red meat and products thereof, 2012 part 2

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium, monophasic
Meat from pig - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	12	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	223	0	0	0
	unspecified	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
Meat from sheep - fresh	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0
Meat from sheep - meat preparation	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	9	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
Meat from wild boar - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
		IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
Meat from wild game - birds - fresh	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
		GB	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
Meat from wild game - birds - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
Meat from wild game - land mammals - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail	IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
		unspecified	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	111	0	0	0
		DE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
unspecified	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	0	0	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	31	0	0	0
		CH	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
		DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0
		ES	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
		IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0
		SI	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	
unspecified	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0
		IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
TR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	at game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	39	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	88	0	0	0
	at retail	DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0
		ES	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0
		HU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
		IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0
		SI	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0
XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	41	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0

Table 8 Salmonella spp. in milk and dairy products, 2012 part 1

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.
Cheeses made from cows' milk - curd	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0
		FR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
		IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
		DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0
		IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses)	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - made from pasteurised milk	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	33	0

Table 9 Salmonella spp. in milk and dairy products, 2012 part 2

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0
		DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	at catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	43	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	379	0
				50	Gram	3	0
		BE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
		DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0
				50	Gram	3	0
IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0		
XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0		
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - milk powder and whey powder	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	50	Gram	1	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk	at farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	18	0
	unspecified	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Milk, sheep's - raw milk	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0

Table 10 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2012 part 1

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bispelberg	Salmonella - S. Braenderup	Salmonella - S. Thompson
Bakery products		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0
			BA	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			DK	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - bread		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - cakes		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	65	0	0	0	0
			SE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - cakes - containing heat-treated cream		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	24	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - pastry		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	130	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			GB	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Beverages, alcoholic		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Beverages, non-alcoholic		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
			TW	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Cereals and meals		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	18	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			IN	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Chocolate		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0

Table 11 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2012 part 2

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bispbjerg	Salmonella - S. Braenderup	Salmonella - S. Thompson
Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	1	1	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	58	0	0	0	0
			CH	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			CN	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0
			GB	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
			HU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			IN	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			JP	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			KE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			LK	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			PL	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	0	0	0	0
			Crustaceans		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
at retail	AR	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	AT	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
	CL	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	DE	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	DK	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
	FR	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
	IN	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	IT	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	NL	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
	TH	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
	VN	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	XX	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0

Table 12 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2012 part 3

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bispebjerg	Salmonella - S. Braenderup	Salmonella - S. Thompson
Crustaceans - unspecified - cooked		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans - unspecified - raw		at retail	DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			NL	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Egg products		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0
					120	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Egg products - dried		at retail	HU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	
Egg products - liquid		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			DK	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			NL	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Egg products - non-ready-to-eat	campaign A-041-12	at retail	AR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	39	0	0	0	0
			BE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	27	0	0	0	0
			DK	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	16	0	0	0	0
			IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0	0	0	0
			NL	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0

Table 13 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2012 part 4

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bispebjerg	Salmonella - S. Braenderup	Salmonella - S. Thompson			
Eggs - table eggs		at packing centre	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0			
					300	Gram	23	0	0	0	0			
					360	Gram	2	0	0	0	0			
		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
					at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	34	0	0	0	0
								300	Gram	51	0	0	0	0
		360	Gram	2	0	0	0	0						
		at retail	AT	batch (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0		
					NL	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
		Fats and oils (excluding butter)		at retail	CN	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Fish - raw		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0			
			NL	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0			
		unspecified	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
Fish - smoked		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
Fishery products, unspecified		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0			
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0			
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0			
			LT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
			NO	single (food/feed)	20	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
					25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
			PL	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0				
		unspecified	CN	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
Fishery products, unspecified - non-ready-to-eat - frozen		at retail	DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0			
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
Fruits		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
Fruits - non-pre-cut - frozen		at retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			
Fruits - products		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			

Table 14 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2012 part 5

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bispebjerg	Salmonella - S. Braenderup	Salmonella - S. Thompson
Fruits and vegetables	campaign A-006-12	at border control	EG	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			IL	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			IN	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			TH	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	32	0	0	0	0
			VN	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
	campaign A-801-12	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	35	0	0	0	0
			BE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			CN	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
			ES	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0
			HU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
			IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	35	0	0	0	0
			NL	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			SI	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	Infant formula	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0
		at retail	CH	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0
HR			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
XX			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	
unspecified		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
Infant formula - dried - intended for infants below 6 months		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	
Juice - fruit juice	at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	
		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	GB	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	

Table 15 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2012 part 6

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bispebjerg	Salmonella - S. Braenderup	Salmonella - S. Thompson
Juice - fruit juice - unpasteurised		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
			CR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Juice - mixed juice		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh		at game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from deer (venison) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten raw		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw		at game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Molluscan shellfish - raw		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Mushrooms		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			CN	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			HU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			PL	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			TH	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0

Table 16 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2012 part 7

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bispebjerg	Salmonella - S. Braenderup	Salmonella - S. Thompson
Nuts and nut products		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			ID	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			PH	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Nuts and nut products - dried		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
			US	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Nuts and nut products - roasted		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Other food		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	31	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Other food of non-animal origin		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
			ES	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			FR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0

Table 17 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2012 part 8

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bispebjerg	Salmonella - S. Braenderup	Salmonella - S. Thompson
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		at catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	32	0	0	0	0
					50	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	26	0	0	0	0
			at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	423	0	0	0
		50				Gram	19	0	0	0	0
		CN		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
		DE		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	20	0	0	0	0
		FR		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		GL		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		HU		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		IT		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
		LI		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		MY		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		US		single (food/feed)	50	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		XX		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	49	0	0	0	0
					50	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0

Table 18 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2012 part 9

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bispebjerg	Salmonella - S. Braenderup	Salmonella - S. Thompson
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	35	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	36	0	0	0	0
			BA	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			CH	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0
			HU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0
			SE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	24	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - containing raw egg		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	79	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads - containing mayonnaise		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			TH	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0

Table 19 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2012 part 10

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bispebjerg	Salmonella - S. Braenderup	Salmonella - S. Thompson
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			TR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Seeds, sprouted - ready-to-eat		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Soups - dehydrated		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0
Spices and herbs		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	0	0	0	0
			BR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			GD	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	43	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	35	1	0	1	1
			DK	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			EG	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			ES	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			GR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			HR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			ID	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			IN	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			JP	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			LK	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			MA	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			MX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			TH	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			TN	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			TR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0			
ZA	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			

Table 20 Salmonella spp. in other food, 2012 part 11

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bispebjerg	Salmonella - S. Braenderup	Salmonella - S. Thompson
Spices and herbs - dried		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			IN	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Sweets		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Vegetables		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			FR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			HU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Vegetables - non-pre-cut		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	
Vegetables - products		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			GR	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0

4.1.4. Salmonella spp. in animals

A. Salmonella spp. in Gallus gallus - breeding flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are only parent flocks in Austria. The permanent monitoring plan performed by a national program takes place at hatcheries and on farm level; each flock is tested regularly as well by the farmer as by the Veterinary Authorities.

If *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Hadar* and *S. Virchow* or *S. Pullorum Gallinarum* is isolated from breeding flocks at the hatchery the flock is banned and sampled for confirmation on the farm: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens are pooled.

If a parent flock tests positive for other salmonella serotypes, official veterinarians are required to investigate the source of infection to optimise biosecurity.

Frequency of the sampling

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Every flock is tested at day one

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

1. Routine testing: Every flock is tested at the age of 4 and 12 weeks and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit.
2. Confirmation: If routine testing reveals positive Salmonella test results then follow-up test must be performed from the identical flock.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Monitoring is performed according the national program and takes place at hatchery and on the farm: at hatchery: each flock is tested every two weeks by the industry, and every 16 weeks by the Veterinary Authorities; on the farm: each flock is tested every two weeks by the farmer and 3 times by the Veterinary Authorities (at beginning of production, in the middle of the production period and within the last 8 weeks before slaughter).

Type of specimen taken

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Routine testing: drag swabs, pooled faeces.

For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: Boot swabs, pooled faeces; in the hatchery: dust, meconium, broken eggshells and hatched eggs.

For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs or 200 to 300 pooled droppings a 1 gram per flock, collection of dust.

For confirmation: For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Breeding flocks: Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs, pooled faeces, collection of dust.

For confirmation: For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Case definition

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the White-KauffmannLe Minor-Scheme. All S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: See day old chicks

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: See day old chicks

Vaccination policy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The national program for parent flocks made vaccination against Salmonella Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). It is in line with CR (EU) No 200/2010. The Austrian program for monitoring and eradication of Salmonella in breeding flocks of poultry was again (already since 2000) approved for the year 2013 by Commission Decision 2012/761/EU of November 30th 2012.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Measures according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation:

- Banning of the incriminated sector of the holding
- Culling of the infected flock
- Disposal of the hatched eggs
- Abolishing of the restriction after cleaning and disinfection
- If necessary prescriptions of GMP to prevent re-infection

Notification system in place

All positive results from parent flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Poultry Health Data (PHD) to the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG).

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2012, *Salmonella* spp. was detected in five parent flocks in Austria. From two flocks (both meat production lines) *S. Enteritidis* were isolated. That reveals an overall prevalence for target relevant serotypes of 1.6 %. Therefore the EU-target was not achieved in 2012. Three other flocks were positive for *S. Agona*, *S. Montevideo* and *S. Rissen* (1-time egg production line, 2-times meat production line). In one rearing parent flock (meat production line) *S. Senftenberg* was detected before it was moved to the holding(s) of production. During production salmonella carriage was never found, neither in (the) parent flock(s) nor in the subsequent hatchery.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Salmonella* spp. in *Gallus gallus* - flocks of laying hens

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Laying hens flocks

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks sampling two pairs of boot swabs, at least one testing per year is done by an official veterinarian (boot swabs, dust samples and faeces for residue testing are taken) according to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

At the earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter, two pairs of boot swabs must be taken from each flock. Since May 2007, every flock has been tested in accordance to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Frequency of the sampling

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Chickens are tested at day one.

Laying hens: Rearing period

3 times (at day one, week 8 to 12) and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit

Laying hens: Production period

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks with two pairs of boot swabs; an official veterinarian samples every flock at least once a year according to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Within 3 weeks before slaughter with two pairs of boot swabs at farm

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: Not applicable. No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: according to the program of the cooperatives voluntary surface swabs (e.g. every eight weeks)

Type of specimen taken

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Laying hens: Rearing period

Boot swabs, pooled faeces

Laying hens: Production period

Boot swabs, pooled faeces in holdings with enriched cages; official controls: additional dust samples and pooled faeces for antimicrobial testing

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: no sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: Voluntary e.g. surface swabs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Laying hens: Rearing period

2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: Production period

Industry sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Official sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock, 25 g of dust and 60 pooled faeces samples

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

No legal requirements, e.g. surface swabs

Case definition

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken

Laying hens: Rearing period

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken

Laying hens: Production period

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs or dust or detection of antimicrobials or bacterial growth inhibitory effect in feces samples

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Salmonella spp. isolated from surface swabs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the White-KauffmannLe Minor-Scheme. All S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Laying hens: Rearing period

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: Production period

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: no testing

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Vaccination policy

Laying hens flocks

The national program made vaccination against Salmonella Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Laying hens flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Laying hens flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

All actions according to EU- and national legislation

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Laying hens flocks

No class A eggs or culling in case of association with a food borne outbreak; EU regulation No 1237/2007 is in force

Notification system in place

All positive results from laying flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Poultry Health Data to the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG).

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2012, 2,740 laying hen flocks were in production. *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* was detected in 20 flocks (0.7 %). The EU-target was achieved in 2012.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. *Salmonella* spp. in *Gallus gallus* - broiler flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Broiler flocks

Within 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Within 3 weeks before slaughter at farm 2 pairs of boot swabs have to be taken. 10 % of the flocks have to be tested by the competent authority. Commission Regulation (EC) No 646/2007, followed by Commission Regulation (EC) No 200/2012 is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Type of specimen taken

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Nil

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Industry sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Official sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock, 60 pooled faeces samples (150g)

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements, e.g. pooled faeces

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 646/2007, followed by Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2012, is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xId or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the White-KauffmannLe Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

no testing

Vaccination policy

Broiler flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Broiler flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Broiler flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2012.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Competitive exclusion strategies take place.

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Competitive exclusion strategies take place.

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Competitive exclusion strategies take place. Logistic Slaughtering is permitted for Salmonella spp. positive flocks

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Notification system in place

All positive findings in broiler flocks had to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry health data (PHD) to the Federal Ministry of Health.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2012, 3,510 broiler flocks were in production. *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* was detected in 23 flocks (0.7 %). The EU-target was achieved in 2012.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

D. *Salmonella* spp. in turkey - meat production flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Meat production flocks

Within 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 584/2008, followed by Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012, is in force since 01.01.2010

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Type of specimen taken

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Industry sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Official sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock, 60 pooled faeces samples (150g)

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

no sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No sampling

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 584/2008, followed by Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012, is in force since 01.01.2010

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the White-KauffmannLe Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

see day-old chicks

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

see day-old chicks

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

see day-old chicks

Vaccination policy

Meat production flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Meat production flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Meat production flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

According to Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005

Notification system in place

All positive findings in turkey broiler flocks have to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry health data (PHD) to the Federal Ministry of Health.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2012, 375 turkey meat production flocks existed in Austria. *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* was detected in 2 (0.5 %) turkey flocks. The EU-targeted was achieved in 2012.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

An outbreak of *S. Stanley* in humans could be traced back to contaminated turkey flocks.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 21 Salmonella spp. in poultry breeding flocks (*Gallus gallus*), 2012

Animal species	No of flocks under control programme	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Sample origin	Target verification	Sampling unit	Comment	Units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella	Salmonella - S. Agona	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis	Salmonella - S. Montevideo	Salmonella - S. Rissen	Salmonella - S. Senftenberg
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for egg production line, during rearing period, control and eradication programmes	13	phd	Census	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock		13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for egg production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	25	phd	Census	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock		25	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), grandparent breeding flocks for egg production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	0	phd					Yes										
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), elite breeding flocks for egg production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	0	phd					Yes										
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for broiler production line, during rearing period, control and eradication programmes	53	phd	Census	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock		53	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for broiler production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	103	phd	Census	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock		103	4	0	1	2	1	0	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), grandparent breeding flocks for broiler production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	0	phd					Yes										
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), elite breeding flocks for broiler production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	0	phd					Yes										

phd: Poultry Health Data.

Table 22 Salmonella spp. in other commercial poultry, 2012

Animal species	No of flocks under control programme	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Sample origin	Target verification	Sampling unit	Comment	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Agona	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Bovismorbificans	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Braenderup	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Coeln	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Dublin	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Enteritidis	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Gallinarum	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Give	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. group B, monophasic strain	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Hadar	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Infantis	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Jerusalem	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Kottbus	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Livingstone	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Llandoff	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. London	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Mbandaka	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Montevideo	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Ohio	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Oranienburg	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Saintpaul	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Senftenberg	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Stanley	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Tennessee	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Thompson	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Typhimurium	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Worthington
Gallus gallus (fowl)																																						
Laying hens																																						
During rearing period, control and eradication programmes	429	phd	Census	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock		429	7	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	
Adult, at farm, control and eradication programmes	2740	phd	Census	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock	1)	2740	59	8	1	1	1	1	14	1	2	1	0	4	0	1	1	0	1	5	0	0	1	0	9	0	0	1	7	0
Adult, at farm, control and eradication programmes	2740	phd	Census	Industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock		2547	30	4	1	1	0	0	6	1	2	0	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	2	0
Adult, at farm, control and eradication programmes	2740	phd	Objective sampling	Official sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock	1)	1582	29	4	0	0	1	1	8	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	0	0	1	0	6	0	0	0	4	0
Adult, at farm, control and eradication programmes	2740	phd	Suspect sampling	Official sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock		27	9	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	
Gallus gallus (fowl)																																						
Broilers																																						
Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers - before slaughter	3510	phd	Census	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock		3510	113	13	4	0	1	0	21	0	0	1	2	21	0	1	0	1	0	7	2	1	1	1	28	0	1	3	2	2
Turkeys																																						
Breeding flocks, unspecified																																						
Turkeys - breeding flocks - adult	0	phd	Census	Official and industry sampling			Yes																															
Turkeys																																						
Fattening flocks, unspecified																																						
Turkeys - fattening flocks - before slaughter	375	phd	Census	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock	2)	375	36	2	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	12	0	16	0	0	1	1

1) one flock with 2 serovars (*S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium*)

2) one flock with 3 serovars (*S. Montevideo*, *S. Infantis* and *S. Saintpaul*)

phd: Poultry Health Data.

4.1.5. Salmonella spp. in feedstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Official monitoring based on risk assessment, own check programme by the industry based on HACCP.

Frequency of the sampling

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Other: See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

Other: See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

Other: See above

Process control in feed mills

Other: See above

Compound feeding stuffs

Other: See above

Type of specimen taken

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Feed material of cereal grain and oil seed or fruit origin

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Imported feed material of plant origin

Oil seed meals and cakes

Imported feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Process control in feed mills

Not applicable (n. a.)

Compound feeding stuffs

Feed for farm animals (mainly poultry) and pets

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Sampling is performed according EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Definition of positive finding

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Process control in feed mills

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Compound feeding stuffs

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Bacteriological method: ISO 6579:2002; sample weight: 25 g (samples related to suspected lots or cases are analysed by testing several subsamples in parallel); all isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Other: as above

Imported feed material of plant animal

Other: as above

Imported feed material of animal origin

Other: as above

Process control in feed mills

Other: as above

Compound feeding stuffs

Other: as above

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

National legislation: BGBl. Nr. 139/1999, as last amendet by BGBl. Nr. 87/2005 (Futtermittelgesetz 1999, § 3) and BGBl. Nr. 316/2010 (Futtermittelverordnung 2010) containing general requirements for feedingstuffs and BGBl. II Nr. 100/2007 (Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007).

EC: VO (EG) 183/2005 (Futtermittelhygieneverordnung) and VO (EG) 882/2004 (Kontrollverordnung) with regard to salmonella monitoring, general requirements for feed material and compound feed, coordinated annual control program

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings

Domestic feed material of plant origin

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Notification system in place

The Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) notifies the local authorities and the system has been in place since 1979. The legal basis of the RASFF is Regulation EC/178/2002.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the last 20 years, the quality of feed has improved due to the increase of numbers of farms, processing plants and retailer using HACCP concepts, traceability of contaminated feed/components of feed and palletizing feed/contaminated feed. In 2012, data from feedingstuffs (only feedingstuffs for food producing animals, exclusive pet feed) indicate that the prevalence of salmonella (< 2%) remains very low. Although in pet food Salmonella was detected in 7% (6 out of 88) of analysed samples.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 23 Salmonella spp. in feed material of animal origin, 2012

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Unit	Sample Origin	Sample Weight	Total units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.
Feed material of marine animal origin - fish meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0
			DE	25g	1	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	5	0
Feed material of marine animal origin - fish oil	at retail	batch (food/feed)	DE	25g	1	0

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 24 Salmonella spp. in compound feeding stuff, 2012

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Unit	Sample Origin	Sample Weight	Total units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Derby	Salmonella - S. Infantis	Salmonella - S. Mbandaka	Salmonella - S. Saintpaul	Salmonella - S. Tennessee	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium, monophasic
Compound feedingstuffs for cattle - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for fish - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	8	0						
	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	4	0						
	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	8	0						
			NL	25g	2	0						
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	29	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - pelleted	at retail	batch (food/feed)	DE	25g	3	0						
			NL	25g	1	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - breeders - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
			DE	25g	1	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers - final product	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	9	1					1	
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers - final product - pelleted	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	3	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	5	0						
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens - final product - pelleted	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0						
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	5	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	33	0						
	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0						
	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	5	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - pelleted	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	24	0						
	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	5	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	13	0						
	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	5	0						
	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	13	1						1
	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - pelleted	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	4	0						
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	9	0						
	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0						
	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	3	0						
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - pelleted	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	3	0						
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0						
	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	3	0						
Compound feedingstuffs, not specified - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
Compound feedingstuffs, not specified - final product - pelleted	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						
	at processing plant	single (food/feed)	AT	25g	8	0						
Pet food - dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones)	at retail	single (food/feed)	AT	25g	60	4	1	1		1		1
			BE	25g	1	0						
			CH	25g	2	0						
			DE	25g	16	2	1		1			
Pet food - rodents	at retail	single (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0						

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 25 Salmonella spp. in other feed matter, 2012

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Unit	Sample Origin	Sample Weight	Total units tested	Total units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Agona
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - groundnut derived	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - linseed derived	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - other oil seeds derived	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - rape seed derived	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	11	0	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - soya (bean) derived	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	3	0	
	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0	
	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	12	1	1
			IT	25g	3	2	2
at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	23	1	1	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - sunflower seed derived	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	5	0	
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	3	0	
			DE	25g	1	0	
Other feed material - legume seeds and similar products	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

4.1.6. Salmonella serovars and phage type distribution

The methods of collecting, isolating and testing of the Salmonella isolates are described in the chapters above respectively for each animal species, foodstuffs and in humans. The serotype and phage type distributions can be used to investigate the sources of the Salmonella infections in humans. Findings of same serovars and phagetypes in human cases and in foodstuffs or animals may indicate that the food category or animal species in question serves as a source of human infections. However, as information of the potential source of infection is not available, conclusions have to be made with caution.

Table 26 Salmonella serovars in humans, food and animals (NRC), 2012

Serovars	Humans	Bovine meat	Pig meat	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	turkey meat	Cattle	Pigs	Gallus gallus, fowl laying hens	Gallus gallus fowl, broilers	Turkey
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	N= 1.888	6	19	61	59	38	40	151	116	259
S. Enteritidis	933	2	1	6	1	-	1	74	26	6
S. Typhimurium	241	-	4	-	-	30	17	5	4	10
S. Stanley	146	-	1	3	10	-	-	-	-	98
S. Infantis	78	-	-	40	3	-	1	4	19	2
S. Typhimurium monophasisch	96	-	6	-	1	-	-	-	-	-
S. Saintpaul	18	-	-	-	18	-	-	7	3	40
S. Bovismorbificans	11	-	-	-	1	-	-	4	4	63
S. Senftenberg	2	-	-	-	-	2	-	16	26	14
S. Agona	18	-	-	-	-	-	-	15	10	11
S. Mbandaka	5	-	-	2	-	-	-	14	6	2
S. Thompson	25	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	3	-
S. Newport	16	-	1	-	11	-	-	-	-	-
S. Paratyphi B var. Java	28	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Derby	2	-	2	-	2	-	19	1	-	-
S. Kentucky	21	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-
S. Coeln	15	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	2	-
S. Montevideo	8	1	1	1	-	-	2	-	2	2
S. Virchow	12	-	-	1	3	-	-	-	-	1
S. Kottbus	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	5	-
S. Indiana	7	-	-	4	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Muenchen	11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Napoli	11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Stanleyville	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Braenderup	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-
S. Dublin	0	2	-	-	-	6	-	1	-	-
S. Hadar	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
S. IIIb (<i>Salmonella enterica</i> subsp. diarizonae)	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Panama	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Tennessee	4	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	1	1
Monophasischer Stamm d. B-Gruppe	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Weltevreden	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Corvallis	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Litchfield	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Livingstone	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-
S. Bareilly	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Bredeney	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3
S. Give	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-
S. Haifa	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Mikawasima	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Oranienburg	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
other serotypes	84	1	3	3	4	-	-	3	4	6

Data source: NRC Salmonella primary isolates as of April 30, 2013

Table 27 S. Enteritidis phage types in humans, food and animals (NRC), 2012

Phagetypes <i>S. Enteritidis</i>	N=	Humans	Bovine meat	Pig meat	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	turkey meat	Cattle	Pigs	Gallus gallus (fowl) laying hens	Gallus gallus (fowl) broiler	Turkey
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped		933	2	1	6	1	0	1	74	26	6
PT 8		483	2	1	5	-	-	1	27	14	6
PT 21		68	-	-	-	-	-	-	7	1	-
PT 4		53	-	-	-	1	-	-	8	-	-
PT 13a		57	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	-	-
PT 14b		43	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-
PT 6		35	-	-	-	-	-	-	6	-	-
PT 1		37	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
RDNC		25	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-
PT 29		10	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	-	-
PT 5		17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 12		2	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	11	-
PT 1b		13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 6a		13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 4b		8	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-
PT 6c		10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 21c		9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U		8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 2		6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 7		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6	-	-
PT 15a		6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 23		5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 3		3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 3a		3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 5a		3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 1d		2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 11		2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 20a		2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 35		2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 6b		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 6d		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 21b		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 30		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 34		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 47		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 51		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PT 55		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Data source: NRC Salmonella as of April 30, 2013 (primary isolates in the NRC)

Table 28 S. Typhimurium definitive types in humans, food and animals (EMS), 2012

Lysotypes <i>S. Typhimurium</i>	N=	Humans	Bovine meat	Pig meat	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	turkey meat	Cattle	Pigs	Gallus gallus (fowl) laying hens	Gallus gallus (fowl) broiler	Turkey
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	N=	241	0	4	0	0	30	17	5	4	10
RDNC		61	-	1	-	-	-	12	-	-	-
DT 104L		42	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 120		36	-	1	-	-	-	3	2	-	-
DT 1		6	-	-	-	-	30	-	1	1	-
DT 193		24	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
DT 85		7	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	4
U 302		9	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-
DT 2		6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
U 311		7	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
DT 8		6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U		6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 12			-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4
DT 41		3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
DT 104H		4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U 323		4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 10		3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 17		3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 208		3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 7a		2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U 277		2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 2A		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 44		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 46A		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 99		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 135		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 136		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 186		1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U 298		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-

Data source: NRC Salmonella as of April 30, 2013 (primary isolates in the NRC)

Table 29 S. Typhimurium, monophasic, definitive types in humans, food and animals (EMS), 2012

Lysotypes S.Typhimurium, monophasic phage types	N=	Humans	Bovine meat	Pig meat	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus)	turkey meat	Cattle	Pigs	Gallus gallus (fowl) laying hens	Gallus gallus (fowl) broiler	Turkey
		Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped		96	6	1					
DT 193		82	5	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U		5	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U 311		4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
U 302		3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 120		2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Data source: NRC Salmonella as of April 30, 2013 (primary isolates in the NRC)

4.1.7. Antimicrobial resistance in *Salmonella* spp. isolates

Antimicrobial resistance is the ability of certain microorganisms to survive or grow in the presence of a given concentration of antimicrobial agent that usually would kill or inhibit the microorganism species in question. Antimicrobial resistant *Salmonella* strains may be transferred from animals or foodstuffs to humans.

A. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The resistance rates against antibiotics remained stable over the past years but an increase in resistance could be observed in 2012.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The resistance rates increased in 2012. This can be explained by changes of the isolated serotypes or lysotypes, e.g. by an increase/stable number of multiresistant *S. Typhimurium* (e.g. DT193, DT104L, DT120) or *S. Infantis* strains and by a contemporaneous decrease of fully susceptible *S. Enteritidis* isolates. High level resistances against ciprofloxacin and third generation cephalosporins (cefotaxime) were still extremely rare in comparison to rates reported within the EU.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the NRL-S Report (Jahresbericht) and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES)

B. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in animals and food

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

All *Salmonella* spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories, as well as all primary isolates from humans were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method.

Salmonella isolates from the control programmes in laying hens, broilers and turkeys although were subjected to MIC-testing; all unique strains isolated from one epidemiological unit in the course of the control programmes.

Type of specimen taken

For animals and food see chapters *Salmonella* spp. in animal species and *Salmonella* spp. in food.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

For animals and food see chapters *Salmonella* spp. in animal species and *Salmonella* spp. in food.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All *Salmonella* spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories, as well as all primary isolates from humans were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method.

According to Commission Decision 2007/407/EC all unique strains isolated in the course of the control programme (identical strains from one epidemiological unit only once) were subjected to microdilution susceptibility testing.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

See chapter salmonellosis in humans; for the MIC testing CLSI standards are used, applying EU-RL (European Reference Laboratory) cut-off values.

Laboratory used for detection of resistance

National Reference Centre for *Salmonella*, AGES Graz

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

All *Salmonella* isolates were susceptibility tested (disc diffusion) according to EUCAST. Isolates obtained in course of the control programs were tested according CD Nr. 2007/407/EC. See corresponding tables! Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *Salmonella* this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole.

Control program/mechanisms

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the NRL-S Report (Jahresbericht) and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES)

Table 30 Breakpoints for antibiotic resistance of *Salmonella* spp., 2012

Test method used					
	Disc diffusion	x			
	E-test				
	Agar dilution				
	Broth dilution	x			
Standards used for testing			The methods are used for investigation of isolates from		
	EUCAST	x	Feedingstuff	x (Dilution method)	
	CLSI	x	Animals	x (Dilution method)	
	EN ISO 20776-1		Food	x (Dilution method)	
			Humans	x (Diffusion method)	
<i>Salmonella</i>	Dilution method Resistant >		Diffusion method Resistant ≤		
	Standard for cut-off	concentration (µg/ml)	Standard for breakpoint	zone diameter (mm)	
Tetracyclines					
	Tetracycline	CLSI	8	CLSI	11
Amphenicols					
	Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	16	EUCAST	16
	Florphenicol	EU-RL	16	-	-
Penicillins					
	Ampicillin	EUCAST	8	EUCAST	13
Cephalosporins					
	Cefotaxim	EUCAST	0.5	EUCAST	16
	Ceftazidime	EUCAST	2	EUCAST	18
Fluoroquinolones					
	Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	0.06	EUCAST	18
Sulfonamides					
	Sulfamethoxazol	EU-RL	256	CLSI	12
Aminoglycosides					
	Streptomycin	EUCAST	16	EUCAST	11
	Gentamicin	EUCAST	2	EUCAST	13
	Kanamycin	EU-RL	4	CLSI	13
Quinolones					
	Nalidixic acid	EUCAST	16	CLSI	13
Polymyxine					
	Colistin	EU-RL	2/8 ¹	-	-
Trimethoprim					
		EU-RL	2	EUCAST	14

¹ The EUCAST ECOFF (>2) for colistin was applied for *S. Typhimurium*, but for *S. Enteritidis* the ECOFF >8 was applied as recommended by Agersøe et al, 2011

EU-RL = European Reference Laboratory

Table 31 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. in humans, animals and food (diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2012

Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no) Number of isolates available in the laboratory	Salmonella spp.																																
	Humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			bovine meat			pig meat			laying hens			broiler			turkeys			cattle			pigs					
	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes					
1888			61			59			6			19			151			116			259			38			40						
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n
Tetracyclines																																	
Tetracycline	1888	19,5	368	61	68,9	42	59	37,3	22	6	0	0	19	68,4	13	151	13,9	21	116	19,8	23	259	6,2	16	38	0	0	40	22,5	9			
Amphenicols																																	
Chloramphenicol	1888	3,5	67	61	3,3	2	59	5,1	3	6	0	0	19	15,8	3	151	0	0	116	0	0	259	1,5	4	38	0	0	40	0	0			
Penicillins																																	
Ampicillin	1888	17,3	326	61	1,6	1	59	25,4	15	6	0	0	19	57,9	11	151	5,3	8	116	4,3	5	259	13,5	35	38	0	0	40	12,5	5			
Cephalosporins																																	
Cefotaxim	1888	0,6	11	61	0	0	59	0	0	6	0	0	19	0	0	151	0	0	116	0	0	259	0	0	38	0	0	40	0	0			
Fluoroquinolones																																	
Ciprofloxacin	1888	1,1	20	61	1,6	1	59	5,1	3	6	0	0	19	0	0	151	0	0	116	0	0	259	0	0	38	0	0	40	0	0			
Sulfonamides																																	
Sulfamethoxazol	1888	17,7	335	61	67,2	41	59	30,5	18	6	0	0	19	57,9	11	151	9,3	14	116	16,4	19	259	11,6	30	38	0	0	40	20	8			
Aminoglycosides																																	
Streptomycin	1888	18,3	346	61	9,8	6	59	18,6	11	6	16,7	1	19	26,3	5	151	10,6	16	116	19	22	259	13,1	34	38	5,3	2	40	22,5	9			
Gentamicin	1888	2,0	38	61	0	0	59	5,1	3	6	0	0	19	0	0	151	0	0	116	0	0	259	0	0	38	5,3	2	40	0	0			
Kanamycin	1888	1,0	18	61	1,6	1	59	0	0	6	0	0	19	0	0	151	0	0	116	0	0	259	1,9	5	38	0	0	40	2,5	1			
Quinolones																																	
Nalidixic acid	1888	16,4	310	61	73,8	45	59	76,3	45	6	0	0	19	10,5	2	151	8,6	13	116	23,3	27	259	53,7	139	38	0	0	40	2,5	1			
Trimethoprim																																	
Trimethoprim	1888	3,3	63	61	1,6	1	59	18,6	11	6	0	0	19	15,8	3	151	6	9	116	0	0	259	6,9	18	38	0	0	40	0	0			
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	1888	76,2	1438	61	30	18	59	59	35	6	100	6	19	26	5	151	79,5	120	116	75,9	88	259	82	212	38	95	36	40	73	29			
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	1888	4,2	79	61	3,3	2	59	1,7	1	6	0	0	19	10,5	2	151	11,3	17	116	5,2	6	259	4,6	12	38	5,3	2	40	5,0	2			
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	1888	1,9	35	61	3,3	2	59	8,5	5	6	0	0	19	5,3	1	151	0	0	116	2,6	3	259	1,5	4	38	0	0	40	0,0	0			
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	1888	3,5	66	61	60,7	37	59	7	4	6	0	0	19	5,3	1	151	4	6	116	16,4	19	259	1,5	4	38	0	0	40	17,5	7			
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	1888	8,8	166	61	0	0	59	13,6	8	6	0	0	19	36,8	7	151	4,6	7	116	0	0	259	9,3	24	38	0	0	40	5,0	2			
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	1888	5,5	104	61	3,3	2	59	10,2	6	6	0	0	19	15,8	3	151	0,7	1	116	0	0	259	1,2	3	38	0	0	40	0,0	0			

Table 32 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* in humans, animals and food (diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2012

Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no) Number of isolates available in the laboratory	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>																													
	Humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			bovine meat			pig meat			laying hens			broiler			turkeys			cattle			pigs		
	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
933			6			1			2			1			74			26			6			0			1			
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n
Tetracyclines																														
Tetracycline	933	1,7	16	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0
Ampenicols																														
Chloramphenicol	933	0,2	2	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0
Penicillins																														
Ampicillin	933	2,4	22	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	7,7	2	6	0	0				1	0	0
Cephalosporins																														
Cefotaxim	933	0,1	1	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0
Fluoroquinolones																														
Ciprofloxacin	933	0	0	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0
Sulfonamides																														
Sulfamethoxazol	933	0,6	6	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0
Aminoglycosides																														
Streptomycin	933	0,8	7	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0
Gentamicin	933	0,1	1	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0
Kanamycin	933	0	0	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0
Quinolones																														
Nalidixic acid	933	5,9	55	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0
Trimethoprim																														
Trimethoprim	933	0,2	2	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	933	96,7	902	6	100	6	1	100	1	2	100	2	1	100	1	74	100	74	26	92,3	24	6	100	6				1	100	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	933	1,6	15	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	7,7	2	6	0	0				1	0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	933	1,2	11	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	933	0,1	1	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	933	0,3	3	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	933	0,1	1	6	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	74	0	0	26	0	0	6	0	0				1	0	0

Table 33 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2012

Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no) Number of isolates available in the laboratory	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>																													
	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat			Laying hens			Broiler			Turkeys			Cattle			Pigs		
	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
241			0			0			0			4			5			4			10			30			17			
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n
Tetracyclines																														
Tetracycline	241	58,9	142										4	0	0	5	20	1	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	17,6	3
Amphenicols																														
Chloramphenicol	241	21,6	52										4	50	2	5	0	0	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	0	0
Penicillins																														
Ampicillin	241	56,4	136										4	75	3	5	20	1	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	29,4	5
Cephalosporins																														
Cefotaxim	241	0,4	1										4	0	0	5	0	0	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	0	0
Fluoroquinolones																														
Ciprofloxacin	241	0	0										4	0	0	5	0	0	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	0	0
Sulfonamides																														
Sulfamethoxazol	241	54,4	131										4	100	4	5	20	1	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	11,8	2
Aminoglycosides																														
Streptomycin	241	56,0	135										4	100	4	5	20	1	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	17,6	3
Gentamicin	241	1,2	3										4	0	0	5	0	0	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	0	0
Kanamycin	241	1,7	4										4	0	0	5	0	0	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	5,9	1
Quinolones																														
Nalidixic acid	241	2,9	7										4	0	0	5	0	0	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	0	0
Trimethoprim																														
Trimethoprim	241	5,0	12										4	50	2	5	0	0	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	241	35,3	85										4	0	0	5	80	4	4	100	4	10	100	10	30	100	30	17	70,6	12
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	241	8,7	21										4	0	0	5	0	0	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	11,8	2
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	241	0,8	2										4	0	0	5	0	0	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	241	2,9	7										4	0	0	5	0	0	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	5,9	1
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	241	27,8	67										4	50	2	5	20	1	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0	0	17	11,8	2
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	241	24,5	59										4	50	2	5	0	0	4	0	0	10	0	0	30	0,0	0	17	5,9	1

Table 34 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* monophasic strain in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2012

	monophasic <i>S. Group B</i> (1,4,5,12 : i : -)																																
	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat			Laying hens			Broiler			Turkeys			Cattle			Pigs					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	96			0			1			0			6			0			0			0			0			0					
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n
Tetracyclines																																	
Tetracycline	96	91,7	88				1	100	1				6	100	6																		
Amphenicols																																	
Chloramphenicol	96	5,2	5				1	0	0				6	16,7	1																		
Penicillins																																	
Ampicillin	96	93,8	90				1	100	1				6	83,3	5																		
Cephalosporins																																	
Cefotaxim	96	2,1	2				1	0	0				6	0	0																		
Fluoroquinolones																																	
Ciprofloxacin	96	0	0				1	0	0				6	0	0																		
Sulfonamides																																	
Sulfamethoxazol	96	93,8	90				1	100	1				6	83,3	5																		
Aminoglycosides																																	
Streptomycin	96	92,7	89				1	100	1				6	83,3	5																		
Gentamicin	96	3,1	3				1	0	0				6	0	0																		
Kanamycin	96	2,1	2				1	0	0				6	0	0																		
Quinolones																																	
Nalidixic acid	96	0,0	0				1	0	0				6	0	0																		
Trimethoprim	96	6,3	6				1	0	0				6	16,7	1																		
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	96	4,2	4				1	0	0				6	16,7	1																		
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	96	2,1	2				1	0	0				6	0	0																		
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	96	0	0				1	0	0				6	0	0																		
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	96	4,2	4				1	0	0				6	0	0																		
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	96	83,3	80				1	100	1				6	66,6	4																		
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	96	6,3	6				1	0	0				6	17	1																		

Table 35 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Stanley* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2012

Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no) Number of isolates available in the laboratory	S. Stanley																																
	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat			Laying hens			Broiler			Turkeys			Cattle			Pigs					
	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes					
146			3			10			0			1			0			0			98			0			0						
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n
Tetracyclines																																	
Tetracycline	146	4,8	7	3	0	0	10	10	1				1	0	0							98	1	1									
Amphenicols																																	
Chloramphenicol	146	0,0	0	3	0	0	10	0	0				1	0	0							98	0	0									
Penicillins																																	
Ampicillin	146	5,5	8	3	0	0	10	20	2				1	0	0							98	6,1	6									
Cephalosporins																																	
Cefotaxim	146	0,7	1	3	0	0	10	0	0				1	0	0							98	0	0									
Fluoroquinolones																																	
Ciprofloxacin	146	0,0	0	3	0	0	10	0	0				1	0	0							98	0	0									
Sulfonamides																																	
Sulfamethoxazol	146	2,1	3	3	0	0	10	10	1				1	0	0							98	0	0									
Aminoglycosides																																	
Streptomycin	146	1,4	2	3	0	0	10	0	0				1	0	0							98	3,1	3									
Gentamicin	146	0	0	3	0	0	10	0	0				1	0	0							98	1	1									
Kanamycin	146	0	0	3	0	0	10	0	0				1	0	0							98	0	0									
Quinolones																																	
Nalidixic acid	146	90,4	132	3	0	0	10	100	10				1	0	0							98	100	98									
Trimethoprim																																	
Trimethoprim	146	1,4	2	3	0	0	10	10	1				1	0	0							98	0	0									
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	146	93,8	137	3	100	3	10	80,0	8				1	100	1							98	91,8	90									
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	146	1,4	2	3	0	0	10	10	1				1	0	0							98	7,1	7									
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	146	2,7	4	3	0	0	10	0	0				1	0	0							98	0	0									
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	146	0	0	3	0	0	10	0	0				1	0	0							98	0	0									
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	146	1,4	2	3	0	0	10	10	1				1	0	0							98	1,0	1									
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	146	0,7	1	3	0	0	10	0	0				1	0	0							98	0	0									

Table 36 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2012

Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no) Number of isolates available in the laboratory	<i>S. infantis</i>																																
	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat			Laying hens			Broiler			Turkeys			Cattle			Pigs					
	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes					
78			40			3			0			0			4			19			2			0			1						
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n	N	%r	n
Tetracyclines																																	
Tetracycline	78	56,4	44	40	100	40	3	100	3							4	100	4	19	100	19	2	100	2							1	100	1
Amphenicols																																	
Chloramphenicol	78	1,3	1	40	0	0	3	0	0							4	0	0	19	0	0	2	0	0							1	0	0
Penicillins																																	
Ampicillin	78	3,8	3	40	2,5	1	3	0	0							4	0	0	19	0	0	2	0	0							1	0	0
Cephalosporins																																	
Cefotaxim	78	2,6	2	40	0	0	3	0	0							4	0	0	19	0	0	2	0	0							1	0	0
Fluoroquinolones																																	
Ciprofloxacin	78	0	0	40	2,5	1	3	0	0							4	0	0	19	0	0	2	0	0							1	0	0
Sulfonamides																																	
Sulfamethoxazol	78	53,8	42	40	97,5	39	3	100	3							4	100	4	19	100	19	2	100	2							1	100	1
Aminoglycosides																																	
Streptomycin	78	52,6	41	40	92,5	37	3	100	3							4	100	4	19	100	19	2	100	2							1	100	1
Gentamicin	78	1,3	1	40	0	0	3	0	0							4	0	0	19	0	0	2	0	0							1	0	0
Kanamycin	78	3,8	3	40	0	0	3	0	0							4	0	0	19	0	0	2	0	0							1	0	0
Quinolones																																	
Nalidixic acid	78	65,4	51	40	100	40	3	0	0							4	100	4	19	100	19	2	100	2							1	100	1
Trimethoprim																																	
Trimethoprim	78	5,1	4	40	0	0	3	0	0							4	0	0	19	0	0	2	0	0							1	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	78	42,3	33	40	0	0	3	0	0							4	0	0	19	0	0	2	0	0							1	0	0
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	78	3,8	3	40	2,5	1	3	0	0							4	0	0	19	0	0	2	0	0							1	0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	78	1,3	1	40	5,0	2	3	0	0							4	0	0	19	0	0	2	0	0							1	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	78	46,2	36	40	90	36	3	100	3							4	100	4	19	100	19	2	100	2							1	100	1
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	78	3,8	3	40	0	0	3	0	0							4	0	0	19	0	0	2	0	0							1	0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	78	2,6	2	40	2,5	1	3	0	0							4	0	0	19	0	0	2	0	0							1	0	0

Table 37 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis, Typhimurium, monophasic S. group B, S. Stanley and S. Infantis in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2012

Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no) Number of isolates available in the laboratory	other serotypes than S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium, monophasic S. Group B (1,4,5,12 : i : -), S. Stanley and S. Infantis																													
	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat			Laying hens			Broiler			Turkeys			Cattle			Pigs		
	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
394			12			44			4			7			68			67			143			8			21			
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n
Tetracyclines																														
Tetracycline	394	18,0	71	12	16,7	2	44	39	17	4	0	0	7	42,9	3	68	23,5	16	67	6,0	4	143	9,1	13	8	0	0	21	24	5
Amphenicols																														
Chloramphenicol	394	1,8	7	12	16,7	2	44	6,8	3	4	0	0	7	0	0	68	0	0	67	0	0	143	2,8	4	8	0	0	21	0	0
Penicillins																														
Ampicillin	394	17,0	67	12	0	0	44	27,3	12	4	0	0	7	42,9	3	68	10,3	7	67	4,5	3	143	20,3	29	8	0	0	21	0	0
Cephalosporins																														
Cefotaxim	394	1,0	4	12	100	12	44	100	44	4	100	4	7	100	7	68	0	0	67	0	0	143	0	0	8	0	0	21	0	0
Fluoroquinolones																														
Ciprofloxacin	394	5,1	20	12	0,0	0	44	6,8	3	4	0	0	7	0	0	68	0	0	67	0	0	143	0	0	8	0	0	21	0	0
Sulfonamides																														
Sulfamethoxazol	394	16,0	63	12	16,7	2	44	20,5	9	4	0	0	7	28,6	2	68	13,2	9	67	0,0	0	143	19,6	28	8	0	0	21	24	5
Aminoglycosides																														
Streptomycin	394	18,3	72	12	16,7	2	44	29,5	13	4	0	0	7	28,6	2	68	16,2	11	67	4,5	3	143	20,3	29	8	25	2	21	24	5
Gentamicin	394	7,6	30	12	0,0	0	44	6,8	3	4	0	0	7	0	0	68	0	0	67	0	0	143	4,2	6	8	0	0	21	0	0
Kanamycin	394	2,3	9	12	8,3	1	44	0,0	0	4	0	0	7	0	0	68	0	0	67	0	0	143	3,5	5	8	0	0	21	0	0
Quinolones																														
Nalidixic acid	394	16,5	65	12	16,7	2	44	70,5	31	4	0	0	7	14,3	1	68	13,2	9	67	11,9	8	143	27,3	39	8	0	0	21	0	0
Trimethoprim																														
Trimethoprim	394	9,4	37	12	8,3	1	44	23	10	4	0	0	7	0	0	68	13,2	9	67	0	0	143	12,6	18	8	0	0	21	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	394	70,3	277	12	75,0	9	44	59,1	26	4	100	4	7	43	3	68	61,8	42	67	89,6	60	143	74,1	106	8	75	6	21	76	16
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	394	9,1	36	12	8,3	1	44	0	0	4	0	0	7	14	1	68	25,0	17	67	6,0	4	143	3,5	5	8	25	2	21	0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	394	4,3	17	12	0	0	44	11,4	5	4	0	0	7	14	1	68	0	0	67	4,5	3	143	2,8	4	8	0	0	21	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	394	4,6	18	12	8,3	1	44	2,3	1	4	0	0	7	14	1	68	2,9	2	67	0	0	143	1,4	2	8	0	0	21	24	5
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	394	2,8	11	12	0	0	44	13,6	6	4	0	0	7	14	1	68	8,8	6	67	0	0	143	16,1	23	8	0	0	21	0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	394	8,9	35	12	8,3	1	44	13,6	6	4	0	0	7	0	0	68	1,5	1	67	0	0	143	2,1	3	8	0	0	21	0	0

Table 38 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella serotypes derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method, cut-off values), 2012

Gallus gallus laying hens, control program

	Salmonella spp.	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Agona	S. Infantis	S. Mbandaka	S. Senftenberg	all other serovares
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	63	15	8	9	4	5	9	13
Antimicrobials	n res	n res	n res	n res	n res	n res	n res	n res
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	8	0	3	0	3	0	0	2
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	7	0	0	0	3	0	3	1
Penicillins - Ampicillin	3	0	2	0	0	0	0	1
Polymyxins - Colistin	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	4	0	0	0	3	0	0	1
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	9	0	3	0	3	0	3	0
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	13	0	3	0	3	4	3	0
Trimethoprim	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0
Number of multiresistant isolates								
fully sensitive	46	15	5	9	1	1	6	9
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	7	0	0	0	0	4	0	3
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	7	0	1	0	3	0	3	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0

N = number of isolates tested

n = number of resistant isolates

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For Salmonella this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole

Table 39 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella serotypes derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method, cut-off values), 2012

Gallus gallus broiler, control program

	Salmonella spp.	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Agona	S. Infantis	S. Mbandaka	S. Senftenberg	all other serovares
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	113	21	2	13	21	7	28	21
Antimicrobials	n res	n res	n res	n res	n res	n res	n res	n res
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	23	0	0	0	19	1	0	3
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	25	0	0	0	21	0	0	4
Penicillins - Ampicillin	4	1	0	1	0	0	0	2
Polymyxins - Colistin	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	25	0	0	0	21	0	0	4
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	21	0	0	0	21	0	0	0
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	27	0	0	0	21	2	1	3
Trimethoprim	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates								
fully sensitive	81	20	2	12	0	5	27	15
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	8	1	0	1	0	1	1	4
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	21	0	0	0	19	0	0	2
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

n = number of resistant isolates

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For Salmonella this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole

Table 40 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella serotypes derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method, cut-off values), 2012

Turkey, control program

	Salmonella spp.	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Stanley	S. Saintpaul	all other serovares
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	38	1	1	16	12	8
Antimicrobials	n res	n res	n res	n res	n res	n res
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	3	0	0	0	3	0
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	3	0	0	0	3	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	9	0	0	0	8	1
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	30	1	0	16	11	2
Penicillins - Ampicillin	9	0	0	0	8	1
Polymyxins - Colistin	0	0	0	0	0	0
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	30	1	0	16	11	2
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	10	0	0	0	8	2
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	2	0	0	0	0	2
Trimethoprim	5	0	0	0	5	0
Number of multiresistant isolates						
fully sensitive	7	0	1	0	1	5
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	21	1	0	16	3	1
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	0	0	0	0	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	1	0	0	0	0	1
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	1	0	0	0	0	1
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	8	0	0	0	8	0

n = number of resistant isolates

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For Salmonella this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole

Table 41 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella spp. derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2012

		<i>Salmonella</i> spp. layer control program																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		63		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
				=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Antimicrobials	N	%r	n	n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	63	1.6%	1						12	44	5	1					1						
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	63	3.2%	2										61	2									
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	63	12.7%	8									8	6	37	4	4	2	2					
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	63	3.2%	2									2	38	21			2						
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	63	1.6%	1									4	57		1	1							
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	63	1.6%	1				46	16						1									
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	63	1.6%	1						48	14					1								
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	63	11.1%	7		25	31			4	3													
Penicillins - Ampicillin	63	4.8%	3							3	49	8					3						
Polymyxins - Colistin	63	1.6%	1									56	7										
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	63	6.3%	4										56		3		4						
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	63	14.3%	9											1	5	39	9					9	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	63	20.6%	13								32	18				1	12						
Trimethoprim	63	4.8%	3							60						3							

Table 42 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Enteritidis derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2012

				S. Enteritidis laying hens, control program																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				15																					
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
				=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048		
Antimicrobials				N	%r	n	n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin				15	0.0%	0				7	8														
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin				15	0.0%	0							15												
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin				15	0.0%	0						8	6	1											
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol				15	0.0%	0							15												
Amphenicols - Florfenicol				15	0.0%	0						1	14												
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime				15	0.0%	0			14	1															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim				15	0.0%	0				15															
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin				15	0.0%	0		4	11																
Penicillins - Ampicillin				15	0.0%	0						11	4												
Polymyxins - Colistin				15	0.0%	0							9	6											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid				15	0.0%	0							15												
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol				15	0.0%	0										1	14								
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline				15	0.0%	0						11	4												
Trimethoprim				15	0.0%	0							15												

Table 43 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Typhimurium derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2012

				S. Typhimurium laying hens, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				8																				
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	8	12.5%	1							5	2					1								
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	8	0.0%	0										8											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	8	37.5%	3											3	2		1	2						
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	8	25.0%	2										3	3			2							
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	8	12.5%	1										6		1	1								
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	8	0.0%	0				7	1																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	8	0.0%	0						8															
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	8	0.0%	0		3	5																		
Penicillins - Ampicillin	8	25.0%	2								6					2								
Polymyxins - Colistin	8	0.0%	0									8												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	8	0.0%	0										8											
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	8	37.5%	3											1	4							3		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	8	37.5%	3								1	4				1	2							
Trimethoprim	8	0.0%	0						8															

Table 44 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2012

<i>S. Infantis</i> layer, control program				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				4																			
Antimicrobials	N	%r	n	=<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	4	0.0%	0						2	2													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	4	0.0%	0										4										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	4	75.0%	3											1		3							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	4	0.0%	0										2	2									
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	4	0.0%	0										4										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	4	0.0%	0					4															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	4	0.0%	0						2	2													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	4	75.0%	3			1				3													
Penicillins - Ampicillin	4	0.0%	0								2	2											
Polymyxins - Colistin	4	0.0%	0										4										
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	4	75.0%	3										1				3						
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	4	75.0%	3													1						3	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	4	75.0%	3									1					3						
Trimethoprim	4	0.0%	0							4													

Table 45 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Senftenberg* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2012

				<i>S. Senftenberg</i> layers, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				9																			
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	9	0.0%	0	9																			
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	9	0.0%	0	9																			
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	9	0.0%	0	8 1																			
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	9	0.0%	0	2 7																			
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	9	0.0%	0	9																			
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	9	0.0%	0	4 5																			
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	9	0.0%	0	3 6																			
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	9	33.3%	3	2 4 3																			
Penicillins - Ampicillin	9	0.0%	0	9																			
Polymyxins - Colistin	9	0.0%	0	9																			
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	9	0.0%	0	6 3																			
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	9	33.3%	3	2 4 3																			
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	9	33.3%	3	6 3																			
Trimethoprim	9	33.3%	3	6 3																			

Table 46 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Agona* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2012

		<i>S. Agona</i> layers, control program																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		9																						
		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	9	0.0%	0						2	7														
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	9	0.0%	0										9											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	9	0.0%	0											9										
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	9	0.0%	0										4	5										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	9	0.0%	0										9											
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	9	0.0%	0				7	2																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	9	0.0%	0						6	3														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	9	0.0%	0		6	3																		
Penicillins - Ampicillin	9	0.0%	0								8	1												
Polymyxins - Colistin	9	0.0%	0									9												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	9	0.0%	0										9											
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	9	0.0%	0													7	2							
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	9	0.0%	0								4	5												
Trimethoprim	9	0.0%	0							9														

Table 47 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Mbandaka* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2012

				<i>S. Mbandaka</i> layer control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				5																				
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	5	0.0%	0							3	2													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	5	20.0%	1										4	1										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	5	0.0%	0											5										
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	5	0.0%	0										1	4										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	5	0.0%	0										5											
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	5	0.0%	0				3	2																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	5	0.0%	0						2	3														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	5	0.0%	0		4	1																		
Penicillins - Ampicillin	5	0.0%	0								4	1												
Polymyxins - Colistin	5	0.0%	0									5												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	5	0.0%	0										5											
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	5	0.0%	0													1	4							
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	5	80.0%	4								1						4							
Trimethoprim	5	0.0%	0							5														

Table 48 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis, Typhimurium, Infantis, Senftenberg, Agona and Mbandaka derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2012

				<i>Salmonella</i> other than Enteritidis, Typhimurium, Infantis, Senftenberg, Agona and Mbandaka laying hens, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	13			Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	13	0.0%	0						1	10	1	1											
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	13	7.7%	1										12	1									
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	13	15.4%	2											10	1	1	1						
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	13	0.0%	0									2	11										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	13	0.0%	0									3	10										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	13	7.7%	1				11	1					1										
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	13	7.7%	1						12						1								
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	13	7.7%	1		6	6			1														
Penicillins - Ampicillin	13	7.7%	1							3	9						1						
Polymyxins - Colistin	13	7.7%	1									12	1										
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	13	7.7%	1										12					1					
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	13	0.0%	0												2	8	3						
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	13	0.0%	0								9	4											
Trimethoprim	13	0.0%	0							13													

Table 49 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella spp. derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2012

				<i>Salmonella spp.</i> broiler, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				113																				
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	113	0.0%	0						15	79	19													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	113	0.0%	0											113										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	113	20.4%	23									3	19	54	14	15	6	2						
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	113	0.0%	0										47	65	1									
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	113	0.0%	0									1	104	7	1									
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	113	0.0%	0				50	62	1															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	113	0.0%	0						55	55	3													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	113	22.1%	25		27	61			5	20														
Penicillins - Ampicillin	113	3.5%	4								82	26	1			4								
Polymyxins - Colistin	113	1.8%	2									108	5											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	113	22.1%	25										88				25							
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	113	18.6%	21											2	7	79	4					21		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	113	23.9%	27								61	25				1	26							
Trimethoprim	113	0.0%	0						111	2														

Table 50 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Enteritidis derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2012

				S. Enteritidis broiler, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				21																			
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	21	0.0%	0					4	14	3													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	21	0.0%	0										21										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	21	0.0%	0								3	17	1										
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	21	0.0%	0									21											
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	21	0.0%	0									21											
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	21	0.0%	0				15	6															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	21	0.0%	0					21															
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	21	0.0%	0	5	16																		
Penicillins - Ampicillin	21	4.8%	1							12	8				1								
Polymyxins - Colistin	21	0.0%	0								18	3											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	21	0.0%	0									21											
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	21	0.0%	0											5	16								
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	21	0.0%	0							21													
Trimethoprim	21	0.0%	0							21													

Table 51 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2012

				<i>S. Typhimurium</i> broiler, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				2																			
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
N	%r	n	n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	2	0.0%	0						1	1													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	2	0.0%	0									2											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	2	0.0%	0											2									
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	2	0.0%	0										2										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	2	0.0%	0									2											
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	2	0.0%	0				2																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	2	0.0%	0						2														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	2	0.0%	0			2																	
Penicillins - Ampicillin	2	0.0%	0								2												
Polymyxins - Colistin	2	0.0%	0									2											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	2	0.0%	0										2										
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	2	0.0%	0													2							
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	2	0.0%	0									2											
Trimethoprim	2	0.0%	0							2													

Table 52 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2012

				<i>S. Infantis</i> broile, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				21																				
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	21	0.0%	0						8	13														
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	21	0.0%	0										21											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	21	90.5%	19												2	14	4	1						
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	21	0.0%	0										6	14	1									
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	21	0.0%	0										16	4	1									
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	21	0.0%	0					20	1															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	21	0.0%	0						3	15	3													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	21	100.0%	21						1	20														
Penicillins - Ampicillin	21	0.0%	0								9	11	1											
Polymyxins - Colistin	21	0.0%	0									21												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	21	100.0%	21														21							
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	21	100.0%	21																			21		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	21	100.0%	21														21							
Trimethoprim	21	0.0%	0							20	1													

Table 53 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Senftenberg* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2012

		<i>S. Senftenberg</i> broiler, control program																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		28																						
		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	28	0.0%	0						1	20	7													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	28	0.0%	0										28											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	28	0.0%	0										1	23	4									
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	28	0.0%	0										5	23										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	28	0.0%	0										27	1										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	28	0.0%	0				8	20																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	28	0.0%	0						8	20														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	28	0.0%	0		1	27																		
Penicillins - Ampicillin	28	0.0%	0								25	3												
Polymyxins - Colistin	28	0.0%	0									28												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	28	0.0%	0										28											
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	28	0.0%	0												28									
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	28	3.6%	1								24	3					1							
Trimethoprim	28	0.0%	0							27	1													

Table 54 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Agona* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2012

				<i>S. Agona</i> broiler control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				13																			
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	13	0.0%	0							11	2												
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	13	0.0%	0										13										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	13	0.0%	0										1	10	2								
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	13	0.0%	0										13										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	13	0.0%	0										12	1									
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	13	0.0%	0				4	9															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	13	0.0%	0						4	9													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	13	0.0%	0		6	7																	
Penicillins - Ampicillin	13	7.7%	1								11	1				1							
Polymyxins - Colistin	13	0.0%	0									13											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	13	0.0%	0										13										
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	13	0.0%	0													13							
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	13	0.0%	0									13											
Trimethoprim	13	0.0%	0							13													

Table 55 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Mbandaka* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2012

<i>S. Mbandaka</i> broiler control program				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	7			n																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	7	0.0%	0							2	5												
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	7	0.0%	0										7										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	7	14.3%	1											5	1			1					
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	7	0.0%	0										1	6									
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	7	0.0%	0										7										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	7	0.0%	0				4	3															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	7	0.0%	0							7													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	7	0.0%	0		5	2																	
Penicillins - Ampicillin	7	0.0%	0								6	1											
Polymyxins - Colistin	7	0.0%	0									7											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	7	0.0%	0										7										
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	7	0.0%	0													6	1						
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	7	28.6%	2								3	2					2						
Trimethoprim	7	0.0%	0							7													

Table 56 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis, Typhimurium, Infantis, Senftenberg, Agona and Mbandaka derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2012

				<i>Salmonella</i> other than Enteritidis, Typhimurium, Infantis, Senftenberg, Agona and Mbandaka broiler, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				21																				
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
		N	%r	n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin				21	0.0%	0			2	18	1													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin				21	0.0%	0							21											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin				21	14.3%	3								15	3	1	2							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol				21	0.0%	0							14	7										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol				21	0.0%	0						1	19	1										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime				21	0.0%	0		17	4															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim				21	0.0%	0				17	4													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin				21	19.0%	4	10	7		4														
Penicillins - Ampicillin				21	9.5%	2					17	2					2							
Polymyxins - Colistin				21	9.5%	2						19	2											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid				21	19.0%	4							17					4						
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol				21	0.0%	0								2	2	14	3							
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline				21	14.3%	3					13	5					1	2						
Trimethoprim				21	0.0%	0				21														

Table 57 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Salmonella spp. derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2012

				<i>Salmonella spp.</i> turkey, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				38																				
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	38	7.9%	3						1	28	5	1			2	1								
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	38	7.9%	3										35			1	2							
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	38	23.7%	9											17	12		8	1						
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	38	0.0%	0										30	8										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	38	0.0%	0									2	32	4										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	38	0.0%	0				30	5	3															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	38	0.0%	0						32	4	2													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	38	78.9%	30			7	1		25	3	2													
Penicillins - Ampicillin	38	23.7%	9							1	21	7				9								
Polymyxins - Colistin	38	0.0%	0									38												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	38	78.9%	30										8				30							
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	38	26.3%	10											1	2	23	2					10		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	38	5.3%	2								27	7	2				2							
Trimethoprim	38	13.2%	5							30	3					5								

Table 58 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2012

				S. Enteritidis turkey, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				1																			
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	1	0.0%	0							1													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	1	0.0%	0										1										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	1	0.0%	0											1									
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	1	0.0%	0										1										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	1	0.0%	0										1										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	1	0.0%	0				1																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	1	0.0%	0						1														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	1	100.0%	1						1														
Penicillins - Ampicillin	1	0.0%	0								1												
Polymyxins - Colistin	1	0.0%	0									1											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	1	100.0%	1															1					
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	1	0.0%	0														1						
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	1	0.0%	0								1												
Trimethoprim	1	0.0%	0							1													

Table 59 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2012

				<i>S. Typhimurium</i> turkey, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				1																			
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
N	%r	n	n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	1	0.0%	0	1																			
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	1	0.0%	0	1																			
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	1	0.0%	0	1																			
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	1	0.0%	0	1																			
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	1	0.0%	0	1																			
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	1	0.0%	0	1																			
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	1	0.0%	0	1																			
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	1	0.0%	0	1																			
Penicillins - Ampicillin	1	0.0%	0	1																			
Polymyxins - Colistin	1	0.0%	0	1																			
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	1	0.0%	0	1																			
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	1	0.0%	0	1																			
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	1	0.0%	0	1																			
Trimethoprim	1	0.0%	0	1																			

Table 60 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Stanley* derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2012

<i>S. Stanley</i> turkey control program				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			=<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	16			n																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n																					
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	16	0.0%	0						13	3														
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	16	0.0%	0										16											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	16	0.0%	0											9	7									
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	16	0.0%	0									16												
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	16	0.0%	0									16												
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	16	0.0%	0				14	2																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	16	0.0%	0						16															
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	16	100.0%	16						16															
Penicillins - Ampicillin	16	0.0%	0							14	2													
Polymyxins - Colistin	16	0.0%	0									16												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	16	100.0%	16															16						
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	16	0.0%	0												1	14	1							
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	16	0.0%	0							15	1													
Trimethoprim	16	0.0%	0						16															

Table 61 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Saintpaul* derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2012

<i>S. Saintpaul</i> turkey control program				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	12																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	12	25.0%	3							7	1	1			2	1							
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	12	25.0%	3										9			1	2						
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	12	66.7%	8											4			7	1					
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	12	0.0%	0										8	4									
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	12	0.0%	0									2	7	3									
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	12	0.0%	0				8	1	3														
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	12	0.0%	0						8	2	2												
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	12	91.7%	11			1			8	1	2												
Penicillins - Ampicillin	12	66.7%	8								2	2				8							
Polymyxins - Colistin	12	0.0%	0									12											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	12	91.7%	11										1				11						
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	12	66.7%	8												1	3						8	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	12	0.0%	0								6	4	2										
Trimethoprim	12	41.7%	5							4	3					5							

Table 62 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than S. Enteritidis, S. Typhimurium S. Stanley and S. Saintpaul derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2012

				Salmonella other than S. Enteritidis, S. Typhimurium, S. Stanley and S. Saintpaul turkey, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				8																			
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	8	0.0%	0						1	6	1												
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	8	0.0%	0										8										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	8	12.5%	1											3	4		1						
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	8	0.0%	0										4	4									
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	8	0.0%	0										7	1									
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	8	0.0%	0				6	2															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	8	0.0%	0						6	2													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	8	25.0%	2			6				2													
Penicillins - Ampicillin	8	12.5%	1							1	4	2					1						
Polymyxins - Colistin	8	0.0%	0									8											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	8	25.0%	2										6					2					
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	8	25.0%	2											1	4	1						2	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	8	25.0%	2								4	2						2					
Trimethoprim	8	0.0%	0							8													

4.2. Campylobacteriosis

4.2.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases exceeded for the first time the number of notified salmonellosis cases in Austria. Since then, the gap between the number of human campylobacter cases and salmonella cases has been widening.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In recent years, the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis – with the exception of 2003 – steadily increased, reaching a new peak of 6,132 cases in 2007. The number of Campylobacter cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to EMS, n = 4,710 cases.

The sources of infection are still unclear. The few published outbreaks in Austria were due to contaminated cow's raw milk or chicken meat. Pets may be considered another possible source.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Feedings stuff has no obvious relevance. Animals are diversly infected: broiler flocks around 50%, cattle approx. 25%. The actual source of infection is unknown in human cases, chicken meat may account for approx. 40% of human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

On January 1st, 2006, the Federal Zoonoses Act (128. Bundesgesetz: Zoonosengesetz, published on 18th November 2005) was implemented. The subject of this Act is to ensure that zoonoses, zoonotic agents and related antimicrobial resistance are properly monitored, that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation to enable the collection of the information necessary in the EU. According to this Zoonoses Act, to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria, a Federal Commission for Zoonoses (Zoonoses Commission) has been founded to advise the Federal Minister. The first meeting took place on May 3rd, 2006. The tasks of this Zoonoses Commission are

- Securing of effective and continuous teamwork of special fields concerned
- Cooperation based on free exchange of general information and where necessary, of specific data
- Determination of measures in case of Austrian-wide food borne outbreaks (concerning several provinces by one outbreak)
- Issues the annually report on trends and sources of zoonoses in Austria
- Preparation of risk based, integrated monitoring and surveillance programmes

The Austria-wide monitoring program on the trends of campylobacter prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of campylobacter in broiler was continued according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council and the Federal Zoonoses Act. The sampling was carried out from January to December 2012, and follow up programs will be implemented in the forthcoming years. In 2012, the monitoring program was suspended in pigs and cattle due to low relevance for human infections.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continue to work for harmonization of monitoring programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.2.2. Campylobacteriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Campylobacter cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain
- Fever

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of Campylobacter spp. from stool or blood
- Differentiation of Campylobacter spp. should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Stool samples are plated on selective media and incubated in microaerobic atmosphere at 37 - 42 °C for a minimum of 36 hours (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 13). Campylobacter is confirmed by observing the typical colony morphology and characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope. For typing and differentiation of isolates to species level biochemical and/or molecular methods as well as matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF) were applied. The differentiation to species level is not performed in each laboratory.

Notification system in place

Notification of Campylobacteriosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases in Austria for the first time exceeded the number of notified salmonellosis cases. Since that year campylobacteriosis has remained the most frequently reported bacterial enteritis in humans in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2012 campylobacteriosis (n = 4,710) was the most frequently notified food borne enteric disease. It seems that the main sources of infection are chicken meat and raw milk (Feierl G. 2007. Jahresbericht 2006 der Nationalen Referenzzentrale für Campylobacter. Mitteilungen der Sanitätsverwaltung 4/2007).

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2012, campylobacteriosis remained the most frequently notified food borne disease in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via reports published by the Federal Ministry of Health (FMH) on a monthly and yearly basis and the annual report of the National Reference Centre. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 63 Campylobacteriosis in humans - species distribution (EMS), 2012

	Cases				
	N	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Campylobacteriosis	4710	55,8	3880	478	352
C. jejuni	3193	37,8	2644	325	224
Campylobacter not specified	1239	14,7	1016	122	101
C. coli	251	3,0	195	30	26
C. sputorum	9	0,1	8	1	-
C. concisus	4	0,0	3	-	1
C. lanienae	4	0,0	4	-	-
C. upsaliensis	4	0,0	4	-	-
C. curvus	2	0,0	2	-	-
C. fetus	2	0,0	2	-	-
C. gracilis	1	0,0	1	-	-
C. mucosalis	1	0,0	1	-	-

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

Table 64 Campylobacteriosis in humans - age and gender distribution (EMS), 2012

age groups	Campylobacter spp.			C. jejuni			C. coli			other species/ not typed		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	63	34	29	47	26	21	1	-	1	15	8	7
1 to 4 years	382	223	159	270	156	114	13	8	5	99	59	40
15 to 24 years	509	307	202	372	221	151	13	7	6	124	79	45
25 to 44 years	959	499	460	653	340	313	61	31	30	245	128	117
45 to 64 years	1331	672	659	904	460	444	71	37	34	356	175	181
5 to 14 years	880	505	375	578	337	241	65	36	29	237	132	105
65 years and older	586	288	298	369	192	177	27	14	13	190	82	108
All age groups	4710	2528	2182	3193	1732	1461	251	133	118	1266	663	603

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

Table 65 Campylobacteriosis in humans - seasonal distribution (EMS), 2012

Month	Campylobacter spp.	C. jejuni	C. coli	other species/ not typed
	cases	cases	cases	cases
January	377	263	31	83
February	195	127	19	49
March	195	125	20	50
April	240	128	14	98
May	358	223	20	115
June	512	354	24	134
July	566	390	23	153
August	587	417	35	135
September	535	370	22	143
October	425	296	14	115
November	444	323	18	103
December	276	177	11	88
Total	4710	3193	251	1266

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

4.2.3. Campylobacter spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2012 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2012“ (BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2011) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2012, approximately 26,000 samples were planned (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that has to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail or at the producer.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for specific food items (about 60-65 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2012, 9 food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2011 BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2011). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002. (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). Therefore food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures.

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat, meat preparations from poultry;

Definition of positive finding

Isolation of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* from the sample independent of the microbiological method (quantitative or qualitative) used.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method: ISO 10272-1:2006 and 10272-2:2006

All isolates were sent to the National Reference Centre. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were differentiated into *Campylobacter jejuni* or *Campylobacter coli* with matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). All other species were identified by additional biochemical and molecular methods including 16S rDNA sequencing. Pulsed field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) is available for outbreak detection and all isolates are stored for epidemiological investigations.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A *Campylobacter* platform called “*Campylobacter* – a concern to everyone” was launched in June 2012. Experts in the fields of human and veterinary medicine, food as well as representatives from industry, several authorities, poultry health service, trade organizations, etc. are assembled to ventilate on possible and plausible strategies against *Campylobacter* in the Austrian broiler production chain, including the impact of *Campylobacter* on human health in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

49 single samples of fresh broiler meat were tested and in 32.7 % (= 16 samples) thermotolerant *Campylobacter* was found (2011: 6.2 %, 2010: 10 %, 2009: 26 %). The reason for this fluctuation is not known yet. As in the previous years, the percentage of *Campylobacter* positive samples at the sampling stage slaughterhouse or processing plant is very high (2012: 100 %, 2011: 100 %, 2010: 90 %).

No *Campylobacter* was detected in 66 samples of non-poultry meat preparations and meat products and in 32 samples of milk, cheeses and dairy products.

A special campaign on atmosphere packaged fresh broiler meat was conducted in 2012. In addition to the microbiological tests the oxygen pressure and carbon dioxide pressure were measured in each packed sample. The prevalence of positive samples (74 %) was in accordance to a previous campaign in 2007, where 78.6 % of the tested samples (no selection for or against modified atmosphere packaging) had positive results for *Campylobacter*. Apart from that the quantitative results (not shown) indicate a lower number of *Campylobacter* isolates (cfu/g).

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-805-12: *Campylobacter* spp. in food - Meat from broilers (*Gallus gallus*) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked – chilled - at retail - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - November

Type of specimen taken

Meat from poultry, modified atmosphere packaged

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in 25 g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up monitoring programs

Results of the investigation

70 samples tested, *Campylobacter* spp. detected in 52 samples (74 %; 30 x *C. jejuni*, 11 x *C. coli*, 11 x *Campylobacter* spp., unspecified).

Table 66 Thermotolerant Campylobacter spp. in poultry meat, 2012

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Campylobacter spp.	Campylobacter - C. coli	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	Campylobacter - Thermophilic Campylobacter spp., unspecified
Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - carcase		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	1	0	0	1
Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - fresh		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	4	0	2	2
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	0	1
			IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	1	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	29	1	0	0	1
		at slaughter house	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	9	7	2	0
Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - chilled	campaign A-805-12	at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	58	44	10	24	10
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	5	0	4	1
			IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			SI	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	3	1	2	0
Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus) - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		at retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	1	0	0	1
Meat from geese - meat products		at retail	HU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	1	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	1	0	1	0
Meat from turkey - fresh		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	1	0	1	0
Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		at retail	DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0

Table 67 Thermotolerant Campylobacter spp. in food, 2012

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Campylobacter spp.	Campylobacter
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at retail	IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Crustaceans		at retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified		at retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - fresh		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
Meat from pig - fresh		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	23	0	0
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
Meat from wild game - birds - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	20	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
			IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk		at farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	18	0	0
		unspecified	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products		at farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Milk, sheep's - raw milk		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
			IT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Sauce and dressings		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
Spices and herbs		at retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0

4.2.4. Campylobacter in animals

A. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal – broiler - at slaughterhouse –official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2012 the monitoring on the prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* spp. was continued in broiler slaughter batches. The period of sampling was randomized over the whole year. Sampling was performed in the 5 broiler slaughter facilities with slaughter batches consisting of >2000 animals in Austria in 2011.

Frequency of the sampling

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: according to the randomized sampling plan

Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration the whole intestines of 10 animals were taken and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. Using a hobcock or polystyrene box cooled samples (4 °C) were sent to the AGES Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory a caecum of each intestinal convolute was identified, some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*.

Case definition

At slaughter: A slaughter batch is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *Campylobacter jejuni* or *C. coli* from the pooled caecal content.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

At slaughter: The pooled samples were examined by direct inoculation on modified Charcoal Cefoperazone Deoxycholate agar plates (mCCDA) being incubated in a microaerobic atmosphere at 42 ± 1 °C for 48 hours. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were subcultured on blood agar plates and incubated for another 48 hours in a microaerobic atmosphere at 37 ± 1 °C. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase and gram staining. For typing and differentiating of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates a PCR as described by Menard et al. (2005) was performed. All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were frozen in proteose peptone solution containing 10 % glycerol or thioglycolat-broth at -70 °C. For quality control *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* were used. Data analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel 2010.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Different strategies are in discussion, e.g. a quick test for identification of *campylobacter* infected flocks at farm.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A Campylobacter platform called “Campylobacter – a concern to everyone” was launched in June 2012. Experts in the fields of human and veterinary medicine, food as well as representatives from industry, several authorities, poultry health service, trade organizations, etc. are assembled to ventilate on possible and plausible strategies against Campylobacter in the Austrian broiler production chain, including the impact of Campylobacter on human health in Austria.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None.

Notification system in place

Findings of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in animals do not need to be reported to authorities in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the course of this monitoring thermotolerant Campylobacter were detected in 146 out of 312 (46.8 %) of the tested slaughter batches. *C. jejuni* was found in 35.9 % of samples, *C. coli* in 10.9 %. Due to the fact that *Gallus gallus* is the animal species with the highest prevalence of Campylobacter *jejuni* and *coli*, poultry meat seem to be the most risky food combined with mistakes in kitchen hygiene for humans acquiring an infection with *C. jejuni/coli*.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 68 Thermophilic Campylobacter spp. in animals, 2012

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive	Campylobacter jejuni	Campylobacter coli
Broiler flocks	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	10 intestines per slaughter batch	IVET Graz	slaughter batch	312	146	112	34

IVET Graz: AGES Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Graz

4.2.5. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter* spp.

A. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

A sentinel surveillance program for *Campylobacter* isolates from human infections was installed in October 2006. On a monthly basis, the first 10 isolates collected at each of four designated diagnostic laboratories serving different provinces in Austria are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Campylobacter* for speciation analysis and antimicrobial resistance testing.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Stool specimens were plated on *Campylobacter* blood-free selective agar at 37°C or 42°C for 48 hours under microaerobic conditions, and organisms were identified as *Campylobacter* spp. by oxidase testing and cell morphology. Isolates were speciated by biochemical methods and/or molecular methods as well as matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF).

Broth microdilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility microtitre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, UK). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin!

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2012 387 isolates of *Campylobacter* (345 *C. jejuni*, 42 *C. coli*) were tested for their antimicrobial resistance. In contrast to previous years, no increase in resistance to ciprofloxacin was observed, the resistance rate remained at a high level (> 60 %). Resistance to tetracyclin also seems to be stable at about 30 %, and resistance to erythromycin is still very low.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

The sentinel surveillance system will be continued. Results are published annually in the Report of the National Reference Centre and in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

B. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in broiler meat

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

Isolates from broiler meat isolated in the course of the national food surveillance programs that were sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Campylobacter* were tested for antimicrobial susceptibility.

Type of specimen taken

Food surveillance programs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant *campylobacter* in food

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed at the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene in Graz. *Campylobacter* isolates from poultry meat were tested.

Methods used for collecting data

All informations concerning the tested food and results of the antimicrobial testing were analysed using Microsoft® Excel2010.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Described in chapter thermotolerant *campylobacter* in broilers.

Broth microdilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex UK). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin.

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Samples from food animals were monitored for antimicrobial residues according to a randomized sampling scheme (BMGF-74320/0003-IV/B/7/2010, Rückstandsuntersuchung-Durchführungserlass 2007).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A project has been started to assess the appropriate method for collecting data on antimicrobial usage in animals. Results of this study are expected for 2013.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Nil

Notification system in place

No notification system for resistant isolates in place.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2012, *C. jejuni* isolated from broiler meat and broiler flocks showed high resistance rates for ciprofloxacin, ampicillin, nalidixic acid and tetracycline.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Additional information

Results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

C. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in broiler slaughter batches

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers

Type of specimen taken

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of all isolates was performed at the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene in Graz. A randomized sampling plan was calculated to obtain approximately 170 thermotolerant *Campylobacter* isolates per animal species. If less than 170 isolates were obtained, all isolates were tested. If more than 170 thermotolerant *Campylobacter* were isolated 170 were randomly chosen.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals, sampled slaughterhouses and results of the antimicrobial testing were analysed using Microsoft® Excel 2010.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Described in chapter thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers.

Broth microdilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex UK). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for Campylobacter includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin.

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Samples from food animals were monitored for antimicrobial residues according to a randomized sampling scheme (BMGF-74320/0003-IV/B/7/2010, Rückstandsuntersuchung-Durchführungserlass 2007).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Nil

Notification system in place

No notification system for resistant isolates in place.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2012, *C. jejuni* isolated from broiler meat and broiler flocks showed high resistance rates for ciprofloxacin, ampicillin, nalidixic acid and tetracycline.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

Table 69 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni*, 2012

Test method used: Broth dilution		Number of reporting laboratory: 1			
Standards used for testing EUCAST		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from			
		Animals	x		
		Food	x		
		Humans	x		
		Dilution method			
		Standard for cut-off	Cut-off concentration (µg/ml)	Range tested	
<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>			Resistant >	lowest	highest
Aminoglycosides					
	Gentamicin	EUCAST	> 2	0.125	16
	Neomycin	EUCAST	> 1	0.125	8
	Streptomycin	EUCAST	> 4	0.5	32
Betalactam antibiotics/betalactamase inhibitor - combination					
	Amoxicillin/clavulanic-acid (2:1)	EUCAST	> 16	1	64
Quinolones und quinoxalines					
	Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	> 0.5	0.06	32
	Nalidixic acid	EUCAST	> 16	2	256
Macrolides					
	Erythromycin	EUCAST	> 4	0.25	128
Penicillines					
	Ampicillin	EUCAST	> 8	0.5	64
Phenicoles					
	Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	> 16	2	64
Polymyxins					
	Colistin	EUCAST	-	4	64
Tetracyclines					
	Tetracycline	EUCAST	> 1	0.125	64

Table 70 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni*, qualitative data, 2012

C. jejuni									
	human			broiler meat			Gallus gallus		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	345			60			108		
Antimicrobials:	N	% r	n	N	% r	n	N	% r	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	345	0.0%	0	60	0.0%	0	108	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	345	0.3%	1	60	0.0%	0	108	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	345	1.4%	5	60	10.0%	6	108	2.8%	3
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	345	0.3%	1	60	0.0%	0	108	0.0%	0
Carbapenems - Imipenem	345	0.0%	0	60	0.0%	0	108	0.0%	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	345	61.2%	211	60	65.0%	39	108	76.9%	83
Macrolides - Erythromycin	345	1.4%	5	60	0.0%	0	108	0.0%	0
Penicillins - Amoxicillin / Clavulanic acid	345	0.0%	0	60	0.0%	0	108	0.0%	0
Penicillins - Ampicillin	345	28.4%	98	60	31.7%	19	108	43.5%	47
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	345	59.4%	205	60	56.7%	34	108	64.8%	70
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	345	31.3%	108	60	35.0%	21	108	32.4%	35
Number of multiresistant isolates									
fully sensitive	345	34.8%	120	60	31.7%	19	108	18.5%	20
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	345	37.4%	129	60	35.0%	21	108	53.7%	58
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	345	25.5%	88	60	25.0%	15	108	25.0%	27
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	345	2.3%	8	60	8.3%	5	108	2.8%	3
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	345	0.0%	0	60	0.0%	0	108	0.0%	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	345	0.0%	0	60	0.0%	0	108	0.0%	0

Table 71 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in humans, quantitative data, 2012

		<i>C. jejuni</i> human		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		345																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0.007	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
				n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	345	0.0%	0						251	93	1											
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	345	0.3%	1						20	140	153	31				1						
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	345	1.4%	5								292	47	1		2	2	1					
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	345	0.3%	1										229	83	32				1			
Carbapenems - Imipenem	345	0.0%	0					326	17	2												
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	345	61.2%	211					53	68	6	7	1	1	8	124	52	25					
Macrolides - Erythromycin	345	1.4%	5							34	138	138	28	2							5	
Penicillins - Amoxicillin / Clavulanic acid	345	0.0%	0									135	182	27	1							
Penicillins - Ampicillin	345	28.4%	98								1	13	41	102	90	15	14	69				
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	345	59.4%	205										59	63	15	3		10	91	104		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	345	31.3%	108						77	108	33	19		1		7	8	92				

Table 72 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler meat, quantitative data, 2012

		<i>C. jejuni</i> broiler meat																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		60																				
		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.0039	0.007	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
				n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	60	0.0%	0						49	11												
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	60	0.0%	0						6	39	15											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	60	10.0%	6								43	8	2	1	3	2	1					
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	60	0.0%	0										40	12	8							
Carbapenems - Imipenem	60	0.0%	0					55	5													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	60	65.0%	39					12	8	1	1			2	26	10						
Macrolides - Erythromycin	60	0.0%	0							11	24	18	6	1								
Penicillins - Amoxicillin / Clavulanic acid	60	0.0%	0									29	28	3								
Penicillins - Ampicillin	60	31.7%	19								3	2	7	18	11	2	6	11				
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	60	56.7%	34										12	11	3				3	13	18	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	60	35.0%	21						12	19	4	4	1		1		1	18				

Table 73 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler flocks - at slaughter - quantitative data, 2012

		<i>C. jejuni</i> Gallus gallus																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		108		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0.007	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
				n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	108	0.0%	0						94	13	1											
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	108	0.0%	0						10	48	45	5										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	108	2.8%	3								96	8		1	3							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	108	0.0%	0										78	15	11	4						
Carbapenems - Imipenem	108	0.0%	0					103	5													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	108	76.9%	83				12	11	2		1		4	55	14	9						
Macrolides - Erythromycin	108	0.0%	0						19	50	35	4										
Penicillins - Amoxicillin / Clavulanic acid	108	0.0%	0									48	50	10								
Penicillins - Ampicillin	108	43.5%	47							1	7	19	17	17	10	15	22					
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	108	64.8%	70										19	13	5	1	1	2	34	33		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	108	32.4%	35					18	28	16	11	3	1		3	1	27					

Table 74 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli*, 2012

Test method used	Broth dilution	x	Number of reporting laboratory			1
Standards used for testing		EUCAST	The methods are used for investigation of isolates from			
			Animals	x		
			Food	x		
			Humans	x		
<i>Campylobacter coli</i>		Standard for breakpoint	Breakpoint Resistant >	Dilution method Range tested (µg/ml)		highest
Aminoglycosides				lowest		
	Gentamicin	EUCAST	> 2	0,125		16
	Neomycin	EUCAST	> 4	0,125		8
	Streptomycin	EUCAST	> 4	0,5		32
Betalactam antibiotics/betalactamase inhibitor - combination						
	Amoxicillin/clavulanic-acid (2:1)	EUCAST	> 8	1		64
Quinolones und quinoxalines						
	Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	> 0.5	0,06		32
	Nalidixic acid	EUCAST	> 16	2		256
Macrolides						
	Erythromycin	EUCAST	> 8	0,25		128
Penicillines						
	Ampicillin	EUCAST	> 8	0,5		64
Phenicoles						
	Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	> 16	2		64
Polymyxins						
	Colistin	EUCAST	-	4		64
Tetracyclines						
	Tetracycline	EUCAST	> 2	0,125		64

Table 75 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli*, qualitative data, 2012

C. coli									
	humans			broiler meat			Gallus gallus		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	42			30			33		
Antimicrobials:	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	42	2.4%	1	30	0.0%	0	33	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	42	2.4%	1	30	0.0%	0	33	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	42	7.1%	3	30	3.3%	1	33	6.1%	2
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	42	0.0%	0	30	0.0%	0	33	0.0%	0
Carbapenems - Imipenem	42	0.0%	0	30	0.0%	0	33	0.0%	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	42	71.4%	30	30	73.3%	22	33	66.7%	22
Macrolides - Erythromycin	42	4.8%	2	30	0.0%	0	33	0.0%	0
Penicillins - Amoxicillin / Clavulanic acid	42	0.0%	0	30	6.7%	2	33	15.2%	5
Penicillins - Ampicillin	42	35.7%	15	30	46.7%	14	33	48.5%	16
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	42	71.4%	30	30	73.3%	22	33	66.7%	22
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	42	35.7%	15	30	33.3%	10	33	45.5%	15
Number of multiresistant isolates									
fully sensitive	42	23.8%	10	30	20.0%	6	33	18.2%	6
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	42	38.1%	16	30	53.3%	16	33	48.5%	16
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	42	31.0%	13	30	23.3%	7	33	30.3%	10
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	42	7.1%	3	30	3.3%	1	33	3.0%	1
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	42	0.0%	0	30	0.0%	0	33	0.0%	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	42	0.0%	0	30	0.0%	0	33	0.0%	0

Table 76 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in humans, quantitative data, 2012

Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	<i>C. coli</i> human			Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
	yes			<=0,0039	0.007	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	42			n																		
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	42	2.4%	1						6	30	5						1					
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	42	2.4%	1							4	26	11				1						
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	42	7.1%	3								8	26	3	2				3				
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	42	0.0%	0										7	30	5							
Carbapenems - Imipenem	42	0.0%	0					1	5	34	2											
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	42	71.4%	30					5	6	1				5	20	4	1					
Macrolides - Erythromycin	42	4.8%	2							4	18	7	10	1							2	
Penicillins - Amoxicillin / Clavulanic acid	42	0.0%	0										14	21	6	1						
Penicillins - Ampicillin	42	35.7%	15											8	19	9	2	4				
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	42	71.4%	30											8	4			1	25	4		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	42	35.7%	15						4	13	7	2	1							15		

Table 77 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in broiler meat - quantitative data, 2012

		<i>C. coli</i> broiler meat																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	30	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0.007	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512
				n																	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	30	0.0%	0						8	20	2										
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	30	0.0%	0							6	15	9									
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	30	3.3%	1								11	18				1					
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	30	0.0%	0										7	22	1						
Carbapenems - Imipenem	30	0.0%	0					1	5	22	2										
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	30	73.3%	22					3	5					5	14	2	1				
Macrolides - Erythromycin	30	0.0%	0								16	7	7								
Penicillins - Amoxicillin / Clavulanic acid	30	0.0%	0										9	16	5						
Penicillins - Ampicillin	30	46.7%	14										1	5	10	9		5			
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	30	73.3%	22										1	7				3	16	3	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	30	33.3%	10						4	10	6						1	9			

Table 78 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in broiler slaughter batches - quantitative data, 2012

		<i>C. coli</i> Gallus gallus		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		33																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0.007	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>= 512
				n																	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	33	0.0%	0						4	26	3										
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	33	0.0%	0							6	10	17									
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	33	6.1%	2								10	19	2				2				
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	33	0.0%	0										5	21	6	1					
Carbapenems - Imipenem	33	0.0%	0					1	8	23	1										
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	33	66.7%	22					6	4	1				6	10	5	1				
Macrolides - Erythromycin	33	0.0%	0							6	10	7	7	2	1						
Penicillins - Amoxicillin / Clavulanic acid	33	0.0%	0										9	16	8						
Penicillins - Ampicillin	33	48.5%	16											7	10	9		7			
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	33	66.7%	22										1	5	5			4	16	2	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	33	45.5%	15						4	10	3	1		1				14			

4.3. Listeriosis

4.3.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Listeriosis can be regarded as a relatively rare infectious disease in Austria with an annual incidence between 0.1 and 0.25 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in the years 1996 to 2007. In 2008 a total of 31 culturally verified human cases of listeriosis were recorded for Austria (incidence 0.38 per 100,000 inhabitants), four of them were associated with pregnancy. In 2009 a further increase had to be assessed, 46 cases what corresponds to an incidence of 0.6. Two cases were associated with pregnancy. In 2010, a reduction to 34 cases could be observed and also in 2011, n = 24 (incidence of 0.29). For 2012, two datasets are presented, one dataset of laboratory confirmed cases notified to EMS and the second dataset of the cases from which isolates were sent to from the National Reference Laboratory for Listeria (NRL-L). In the EMS dataset 36 cases are presented, in the NRL-L dataset 34 cases. The incidences are similar to those of most other western European countries (0.2-0.9). In 2012, lethality was reported via EMS in 1 case (2.8 % of cases) and via NRL-L in 4 cases (11.8 % of cases). This (usually) high rate and the sometimes severe permanent disabilities demand every effort to ascertain potential food-associated outbreaks as early as possible.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease.

The number of listeriosis cases presented in this report reflects (I) the number of laboratory confirmed cases reported to the EMS and (II) the cases where isolates were sent to the NRL-L for typing.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although dairy products and salmon are likely candidates, the source of an infection often remains unclear.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A monthly report is sent to the Ministry of Health by the National Reference Center, whereas outbreaks are reported immediately.

Restrictions tightened to sell unpasteurised milk in remote areas (Alps).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

More widespread information for pregnant and immunocompromised persons should be provided.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send those strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.3.2. Listeriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Listeriosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS, if not otherwise mentioned.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Listeriosis of newborns defined as Stillbirth or at least one of the following five in the first month of life:
 - Granulomatosis infantiseptica
 - Meningitis or meningoencephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Dyspnoea
 - Lesions on skin, mucosal membranes or conjunctivae
- Listeriosis in pregnancy defined as at least one of the following three:
 - Abortion, miscarriage, stillbirth or premature birth
 - Fever
 - Influenza-like symptoms
- Other form of listeriosis defined as at least one of the following four:
 - Fever
 - Meningitis or meningoencephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Localised infections such as arthritis, endocarditis, and abscesses

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally sterile site
- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally non-sterile site in a foetus, stillborn, newborn or the mother at or within 24 hours of birth

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the laboratory criteria

or

- Any mother with a laboratory confirmed listeriosis infection in her foetus, stillborn or newborn

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are Gram stained. Specimen from normally sterile sites are inoculated in blood culture broth or thioglycollate broth and Columbia blood agar plates, vaginal swabs are plated only directly on Columbia blood and colistin-nalidixic acid (CNA) agar. *L. monocytogenes* is identified by catalase and Api Listeria test.

Stool samples were examined after cold enrichment in Fraser enrichment broth and streaked onto selective chromogenic agar plate and Columbia blood-agar. All isolates obtained in Austria are sent to the National Reference Center for confirmation, subtyping by PCR and PFGE and comparison.

Notification system in place

Notification of listeriosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

History of the disease in chapter general evaluation.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

History of the disease

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although dairy products and salmon are likely candidates, the source of an infection often remains unclear.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 79 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2012

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Listeriosis	36	0,41
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2a</i>	13	0,15
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2b</i>	5	0,06
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2c</i>	1	0,01
<i>L. monocytogenes 4b</i>	16	0,19
unknown	1	0,01
deaths caused by listeriosis	1	0,01
<i>L. monocytogenes 4b</i>	1	0,01
Congenital cases*	1	0,01
<i>L. monocytogenes 4b</i>	1	0,01

* in the EMS data, congenital cases (mother and foetus, stillborn or newborn) are counted as two cases

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

Table 80 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (NRL-L), 2012

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Listeriosis	34	0.40
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2a</i>	12	0.14
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2b</i>	5	0.06
<i>L. monocytogenes 4b</i>	16	0.19
<i>L. monocytogenes 1/2c</i>	1	0.01
Deaths	4	0.04
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2a</i>	0	0.00
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2b</i>	1	0.01
<i>L. monocytogenes 4b</i>	3	0.03
Congenital cases*	4	0.04

* Congenital cases: mother and foetus, stillborn or newborn are counted as one case

Data source: National Reference Laboratory for Listeria as of April 22, 2013

Table 81 Listeriosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2012

Age group	Listeriosis			L. monocytogenes 1,2a			L. monocytogenes 1,2b			L. monocytogenes 1,2c			L. monocytogenes 4b		
	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female	all	male	female
< 1 year	3	-	3	2	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1
1 to 4 years	2	1	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-
5 to 14 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15 to 24 years	2	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-
25 to 44 years	4	3	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	2	1
45 to 64 years	7	1	6	3	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	1	3
65 years and older	18	9	9	6	4	2	5	1	4	1	1	-	6	3	3
All age groups	36	15	21	13	5	8	5	1	4	1	1	-	16	8	8

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

Table 82 Listeriosis in humans - age distribution (NRL-L), 2012

Age group	Listeriosis			<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2a</i>			<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2b</i>			<i>L. monocytogenes 4b</i>			<i>L. monocytogenes 1/2c</i>		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	3	-	3	2	-	2	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	1	-	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 to 14 years	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-
15 to 24 years	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-
25 to 44 years	4	3	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	3	2	1	-	-	-
45 to 64 years	7	1	6	3	-	3	-	-	-	4	1	3	-	-	-
65 years and older	17	8	9	5	3	2	5	1	4	6	3	3	1	1	-
All age groups	34	14	20	12	4	8	5	1	4	16	8	8	1	1	0

Data source: National Reference Centre for Listeria as of April 22, 2013

4.3.3. Listeria spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2012 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2012“ (BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2011) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2012, approximately 26,000 samples were planned (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that has to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail or at the producer.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for specific food items (about 60-65 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2012, 9 food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2011 BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2011). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002. (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). Therefore food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures. Therefore Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs indicates the quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

Frequency of the sampling

At the production plant

The producer is responsible for the process hygiene. The frequency of sampling therefore depends on the critical control points of the specific product.

At retail

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Diagnostic/analytical methods used at the production plant or at retail

Bacteriological method ISO 11290-1:2004 and ISO 11290-2:2005

For further investigations all isolates from foodstuffs are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for Listeria in Graz. This includes the isolates from process hygiene controls at the production plant, self monitoring as well as all isolates from regularly testing at retail.

In a first step the species *Listeria monocytogenes* is confirmed by different selective media (e. g. Palcam agar, Ottoviani Agosti agar, Rapid L.mono agar) and/or API. A serogroup-specific PCR according to

Doumith et al., 2004. Differentiation of the Major *Listeria monocytogenes* Serovars by Multiplex PCR. J Clin Microbiol 51, 3819-22 is performed routinely. Finally typing is realized with PFGE. For further questions Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time of flight (MALDI TOF) is available.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

All isolates from foodstuffs and process hygiene controls from any laboratories within Austria are gathered and typed at the National Reference Laboratory for *Listeria*. In the case of an outbreak the data of the outbreak strain are compared with the existing data base.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs; a folder was created by the AGES in cooperation with the Austrian Medical Chamber: Pregnancy – infections transmitted via food (Schwangerschaft – Infektionen durch Nahrungsmittel, http://www.ages.at/uploads/media/AGES_Folder_Schwangerschaft_Web.pdf). This folder was distributed to all gynaecologists. The folder contains advices to prevent food-borne infections during pregnancy, including listeriosis, toxoplasmosis, campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis as well as mycotoxicosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Listeria monocytogenes was not detected in samples of pasteurised cows' milk (0/70) and also not in raw cows' milk (0/68).

In 12 out of 148 (8 %) ready-to-eat pig meat product samples *L. monocytogenes* was found positive, 2-times <100 cfu/g, 5 out of 109 samples (4.6 %) of red meat products, cooked, ready-to-eat chilled were found positive in 25g and of red meat products, fermented sausages 6 out of 155 (3.9 %).

5.4 % of all samples from fishery products (9/168) revealed a contamination with *L. monocytogenes* (all of them below detection limit). 2 out of 72 smoked fish samples (2.8 %) were found positive for *L. monocytogenes*, 2-times <100 cfu/g.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-002-12: *Listeria* spp. in food - Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cheese analogue - at catering - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at restaurants by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January - March

Type of specimen taken

Cheese, cheese analogue, at least 300 g

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria monocytogenes* in 25 g

Results of the investigation

58 samples tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*: qualitative method: *Listeria monocytogenes* was not detected in any sample

Campaign A-039-12: *Listeria* spp. in food – Meat, mixed meat - meat products - at processing plant, at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - November

Type of specimen taken

Cured meat products, cured sausages

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria monocytogenes* in 25 g

Results of the investigation

19 samples tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*: qualitative method: 1 sample positive in 25 g, quantitative method: 1-time <10 cfu/g

Campaign A-802-12: *Listeria* spp. in food - Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods – chilled - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: June - August

Type of specimen taken

Cheese, sliced sausages;

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria monocytogenes* in 25 g

Results of the investigation

98 samples tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*: qualitative method: *Listeria monocytogenes* was not detected in any sample

Campaign A-803-12: *Listeria* spp. in food - Meat, mixed meat – meat products - pâté - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: July - September

Type of specimen taken

Meat pastries with or without poultry meat;

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria monocytogenes* in 25 g

Results of the investigation

56 samples tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*: qualitative method: *Listeria monocytogenes* was not detected in any sample

Campaign A-804-12: *Listeria* spp. in food – Meat from deer (venison) - meat products - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: August – November

Type of specimen taken

Meat from wild game, cured and raw sausages

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria monocytogenes* in 25 g

Results of the investigation

65 samples tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*: qualitative method: 1 sample positive in 25 g,
quantitative method: 1-time <10 cfu/g

Additional information

Samples were also tested for VTEC

Table 83 *Listeria monocytogenes* in milk and milky products, 2012

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Cheeses made from cows' milk	at retail	AT		42	0	42	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - curd	at processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
	at retail	AT		8	0	8	0	7	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at retail	IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	2	0	0
	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		DE		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		16	0	16	0	10	0	0
	at retail	AT		30	1	30	1	7	0	0
		CH		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		FR		4	0	4	0	0	0	0
		GB		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
IT		3	0	3	0	2	0	0		
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT		32	0	32	0	32	0	0
	at retail	AT		26	0	26	0	26	0	0
		CH		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		IT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
unspecified	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		86	0	86	0	77	0	0
	at retail	AT		114	1	114	1	73	0	0
		DE		20	0	20	0	19	0	0
		DK		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		FR		13	0	13	0	10	0	0
		IT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		NL		4	0	4	0	3	0	0
	XX		2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
unspecified	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT		44	0	44	0	44	0	0
	at retail	AT		32	0	32	0	32	0	0
		FR		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		IT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration	L. monocytogenes > detection	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Cheeses made from cows' milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	at retail	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
		DE		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		FR		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	at retail	AT		7	0	7	0	6	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft	at retail	AT		10	0	10	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		13	0	13	0	13	0	0
	at retail	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		FR		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
	at retail	AT		7	0	7	0	5	0	0
		FR		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk	at retail	AT		4	0	4	0	0	0	
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	5	0	0
	at retail	AT		7	0	7	0	6	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	IT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		16	0	16	0	16	0	0
	at retail	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		BG		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		GR		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
		IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection	L. monocytogenes presence in	Units tested with enumeration	L. monocytogenes > detection	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	CY		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		FR		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		GR		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	at retail	NL		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk	at processing plant	AT		13	0	13	0	13	0	0
	at retail	AT		18	0	18	0	17	0	0
		DE		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
		ES		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - curd	at processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft	at processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	at retail	AT		15	0	15	0	15	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses)	at processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	at retail	IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	at processing plant	AT		17	0	17	0	13	0	0
	at retail	AT		25	0	25	0	20	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - made from pasteurised milk	at retail	AT		11	0	11	0	0	0	0
		IE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - buttermilk	at processing plant	AT		11	0	11	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cheese analogue	at catering	AT	campaign A-002-12	37	0	37	0	0	0	0
		BE	campaign A-002-12	3	0	3	0	0	0	0
		DE	campaign A-002-12	6	0	6	0	0	0	0
		DK	campaign A-002-12	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		GL	campaign A-002-12	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		HU	campaign A-002-12	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		IT	campaign A-002-12	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		XX	campaign A-002-12	7	0	7	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - chocolate milk	at processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	0	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L. monocytogenes	Units tested with detection	L. monocytogenes presence in	Units tested with enumeration	L. monocytogenes > detection	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream	at processing plant	AT		14	0	14	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT		32	0	32	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts	at retail	AT		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	at processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	at retail	AT		8	0	8	0	7	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	at processing plant	AT		10	0	10	0	9	0	0
	at retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	at processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	2	0	0
	at retail	AT		4	0	4	0	2	0	0
		IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk	at retail	AT		37	0	37	0	0	0	0
		XX		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt	at processing plant	AT		21	0	21	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT		13	0	13	0	0	0	0
		CH		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		TR		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - pasteurised milk	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk	at catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		47	0	47	0	17	0	0
	at retail	AT		20	0	20	0	15	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk	at farm	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	2	0	0
	at retail	AT		18	0	18	0	16	0	0
	unspecified	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	at farm	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XX		40	0	40	0	0	0	0
Milk, sheep's - raw milk	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0

Table 84 *Listeria monocytogenes* in other foods, 2012

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in xg	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but ≤ 100	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Bakery products - cakes	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT		58	0	58	0	54	0	0
		SE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Bakery products - cakes - containing heat-treated cream	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - pastry	at processing plant	AT		10	0	10	0	10	0	0
	at retail	AT		136	1	136	1	108	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		GB		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans	at processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		FR		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Crustaceans - unspecified - cooked	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		NL		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Eggs - table eggs	at retail	NL		1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Fish - Fishery products which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine	at retail	DE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Fish - raw	at border control	MV		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		TR		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		11	0	11	0	5	0	0
		LK		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
unspecified	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Fish - raw - frozen	at retail	NL		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Fish - smoked	at retail	AT		28	2	28	2	2	2	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		IT		10	0	10	0	0	0	0
		XX		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	unspecified	XX		31	0	31	0	0	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g	
Fishery products, unspecified	at processing plant	AT		26	1	26	1	26	0	0	
		IT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
	at retail	AT		54	2	54	2	54	0	0	
		CZ		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		DE		18	0	18	0	18	0	0	
		DK		8	0	8	0	8	0	0	
		FR		9	0	9	0	9	0	0	
		GL		3	0	3	0	3	0	0	
		LT		2	1	2	1	2	0	0	
		NL		6	0	6	0	4	0	0	
		NO		6	1	6	1	6	0	0	
		PL		17	2	17	2	17	0	0	
	TR		2	0	2	0	2	0	0		
	XX		9	1	9	1	9	0	0		
	unspecified	CN		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
US			1	1	1	1	1	0	0		
Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat	at retail	IT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0	
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0	
Fruits	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Fruits - products - fruit purée	at processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0	
Infant formula	at processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	0	0	0	
	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0	
		DE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0	
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	at processing plant	AT		4	1	4	1	4	0	0	
	at retail	AT		7	1	7	1	7	0	0	
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT		1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0	
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - fermented sausages	at retail	AT		20	0	20	0	0	0	0	
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT		1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	at retail	AT		5	1	5	1	5	0	0	
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		campaign A-804-12		62	1	62	1	1	0	0	
		IT	campaign A-804-12		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		XX	campaign A-804-12		1	0	1	0	0	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at game handling establishment	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		4	1	4	1	4	0	0
		IT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat from farmed game - ratites - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products	at retail	LT		1	1	1	1	1	0	0
Meat from pig - fresh	at retail	AT		7	1	7	1	6	0	0
	unspecified	XX		6	0	6	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT		2	0	1	0	2	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	at retail	AT		61	11	61	11	17	2	0
		SI		2	1	2	1	1	0	0
	unspecified	XX		82	0	82	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT		2	1	2	1	2	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	at retail	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
		DE		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Meat from turkey - fresh	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from turkey - meat products	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from wild boar - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from wild game - birds - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from wild game - land mammals - meat products - fermented sausages	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from wild game - land mammals - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail	IT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	unspecified	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat products	at processing plant	AT	campaign A-039-12	9	0	9	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT	campaign A-039-12	10	1	10	1	1	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - pâté	at retail	AT	campaign A-803-12	30	0	30	0	0	0	0
		BE	campaign A-803-12	20	0	20	0	0	0	0
		CZ	campaign A-803-12	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		DE	campaign A-803-12	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		FR	campaign A-803-12	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		XX	campaign A-803-12	1	0	1	0	0	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	at retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	at processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	at retail	AT		21	3	21	3	21	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products	at processing plant	AT		21	0	21	0	21	0	0
	at retail	AT		33	0	32	0	33	0	0
		CH		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		DE		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
		ES		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		IT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
		SI		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
unspecified	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant	AT		39	1	39	1	39	0	0
	at retail	AT		69	4	69	4	68	0	0
		TR		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	at game handling establishment	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	at processing plant	AT		39	1	39	1	39	0	0
	at retail	AT		87	5	87	5	86	0	0
		DE		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		ES		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		HU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		IT		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
		SI		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
XX		8	0	8	0	8	0	0		
Mushrooms	at retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		CN		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		DE		1	1	1	1	1	0	0
		TH		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Other food	at processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		10	0	10	0	1	0	0
Other food of non-animal origin	at retail	NL		1	0	1	0	0	0	0

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L. monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but ≤ 100	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Mushrooms	at retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		CN		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		DE		1	1	1	1	1	0	0
		TH		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Other food	at processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	1	0	0
	at retail	AT		10	0	10	0	1	0	0
Other food of non-animal origin	at retail	NL		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	at processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT		24	0	24	0	21	0	0
		CI		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		XX		5	1	5	1	5	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles	at processing plant	AT		10	0	10	0	0	0	0
	at retail	AT		4	0	4	0	0	0	0
		DE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - chilled	at retail	AT	campaign A-802-12	93	0	93	0	0	0	0
		DE	campaign A-802-12	3	0	3	0	0	0	0
		IT	campaign A-802-12	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads	at processing plant	AT		15	0	15	0	5	0	0
	at retail	AT		54	0	54	0	9	0	0
		DE		2	0	2	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads - containing mayonnaise	at retail	AT		5	0	5	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings	at retail	AT		12	0	12	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise	at retail	AT		4	0	4	0	0	0	0
Spices and herbs	at retail	XX		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Vegetables	at processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	4	0	0
	at retail	AT		14	1	14	1	8	0	0
		DE		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		FR		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		HU		5	0	5	0	2	0	0
		IT		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
Vegetables - non-pre-cut	at retail	AT		4	0	4	0	0	0	0
Vegetables - products	at processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	at retail	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		DE		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Vegetables - products - cooked	at retail	GR		2	0	2	0	0	0	0

4.4. Verotoxic Escherichia coli

4.4.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2012, 127 laboratory confirmed cases were notified to the EMS; this number was similar as in 2011 (129 cases). In the years 2007 to 2010 less cases were reported annually, between 88 to 103 cases. Out of the 127 cases 17 cases of HUS were notified to the EMS (a further HUS-case was not laboratory confirmed).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

The number of VTEC cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2012, the prevalence of verotoxin producing E. coli isolated from animals remained similar compared to last year. In 35 % of samples from cattle (39% in 2011) and in 65 % of samples from sheep (68 % in 2011) VTEC could be isolated. Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), in cattle O157 (2 x), O26 (2 x) and O103 (1 x) were isolated and from sheep O157 (1 x).

The relevance of findings of VTEC in faeces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines and sheep. Meat samples of game show a higher prevalence of VTEC.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

An Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of VTEC prevalence in bovine animals and sheep was implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Orders. The sampling was carried out throughout 2012 and follow up programs will be implemented in the forthcoming years.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Increased awareness and information should be made available for parents, paediatricians and general practitioners in regard to food safety and the prevention of infection.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.4.2. Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of VTEC cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

STEC/VTEC diarrhoea

Any person with at least one of the following two symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain

HUS

Any person with acute renal failure and at least one of the following two:

- Microangiopathic haemolytic anaemia
- Thrombocytopenia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following three:

- Isolation of Shigatoxin/Verotoxin (STEC/VTEC) producing E. coli
- Detection of *vtx1* or *vtx2* gene(s) nucleic acid
- Detection of free shigatoxins.

Only for HUS the following can be used as laboratory criterion to confirm STEC/VTEC:

- E. coli serogroups specific antibody response

Isolation and additional characterisation by serotype, phage type, *eae* genes, and subtypes of *stx1/stx2* should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case of STEC-associated HUS

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria for HUS

Probable case of STEC/VTEC

• Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link or a laboratory confirmed case without clinical criteria

Confirmed case of STEC/VTEC

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

1. Detection of E. coli O157 (most prominent serotype in HUS cases):

- Bacteriology: Isolation of O157 colonies on Sorbitol-MacConkey agar (or CT-Sorbitol-MacConkey agar) after incubation for 24 hours at 37 °C (or 41°C). O157 is confirmed via the E. coli O157 Latex Test.

- Serology: This method is constantly used at the German HUS-"Konsiliarlabor"; anti-O157 antibodies of IgG and IgM types can be distinguished.

2. Detection of Verotoxin (VTEC)-producing strains (used at the National Reference Laboratory/Center for EHEC/VTEC/STEC): Stools are enriched overnight in a medium containing mitomycin C (EHEC Direct Medium, Heipha, Heidelberg, Germany). Enriched cultures are plated on selective agar (CT-Sorbitol-MacConkey, Enterohemolysin, and Sorbitol-MacConkey). After incubation for 18-24 hours at 37°C a representative mixture of the viable cells were subjected to PCR reactions analyzing *stx1*, *stx2*, *eae* and *Ehly* (Reischl et al. (2002), Journal of Clinical Microbiology, p. 2555-2565). Isolates are gained via colony picking and pathotyped with the same PCR scheme. Isolate identification is further confirmed by conventional biochemical tests (VITEK or Api 20E, bioMerieux, Marcy-l'Etoile, France).

All EHEC/STEC/VTEC isolates obtained in Austria are to be sent to the National Reference Laboratory for confirmation, subtyping and comparison. All Shiga toxin producing E. coli are serotyped with E. coli antisera (E. coli antisera, Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark). Comparison of the isolates is done by Pulsed-Field-Gel-Electrophoresis and Ribotyping.

Notification system in place

Notification of VTEC according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

See History of the disease

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

Relevance as a zoonotic disease

HUS is a rare complication of E. coli infection; however EHECs themselves are not rare, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, most of which are currently unknown. Although raw or undercooked meat and unpasteurised dairy products are likely candidates to transfer the bacterium to humans, the actual source of infection often remains unclear. The importance of hand hygiene after animal contact should be always considered.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH

Table 85 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli infections in human - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2012

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	unknown
HUS	17	0,20	11	4	2
- caused by O157 (VT+)	0	0	-	-	-
- caused by other VTEC	11	0,13	7	2	2
- unknown serovar	6	0,07	4	2	-
E.coli infect. (except HUS)	102	1,21	73	14	15
- caused by O157 (VT+)	16	0,19	13	1	2
- caused by other VTEC	59	0,70	41	7	11
- unknown serovar	27	0,32	19	6	2
HUS status not known	8	0,09	8	-	-
- caused by O157 (VT+)	1	0,01	1	-	-
- caused by other VTEC	4	0,05	4	-	-
- unknown serovar	3	0,04	3	-	-
VTEC gesamt	127	1,50	92	18	17

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

Table 86 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli infections in human - age distribution (EMS), 2012

age groups	E. coli infection (except HUS)			HUS			HUS status not known		
	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	9	4	5	1	1	-	1	-	1
1 to 4 years	56	36	20	11	1	10	5	2	3
5 to 14 years	15	4	11	5	2	3	2	2	-
15 to 24 years	6	4	2	-	-	-	-	-	-
25 to 44 years	8	5	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
45 to 64 years	5	1	4	-	-	-	-	-	-
65 years and older	3	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
Gesamtergebnis	102	54	48	17	4	13	8	4	4

Data source: EMS as of April 26, 2012

4.4.3. Pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2012 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2012“ (BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2011) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2012, approximately 26,000 samples were planned (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that has to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail or at the producer.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for specific food items (about 60-65 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2012, 9 food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2011 BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2011). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002. (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). Therefore food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures.

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat, meat preparations, fruits, vegetables etc.

Defintion of positive finding

Detection of *stx1*- and/or *stx2*-positive *E. coli*.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The sample is preenriched for 18-24 h at 37 °C (e. g. in buffered peptone water, modified trypton-soy broth containing novobiocin,). DNA is extracted and a multiplex PCR for detection of genes encoding Vero/Shigatoxin 1 (*stx1*), Vero/Shigatoxin 2 (*stx2*) is performed (according to ISO 20838). There is no further testing for negative PCR results. If the enrichment is PCR-positive, it is streaked on to solid media. Single colonies are tested for the presence of *stx1* and/or *stx2*, or a colony hybridization-blot for the detection of *stx1* and/or *stx2* is performed. The Shigatoxin producing *E. coli* is sent to the National Reference Center for *Escherichia coli* including verotoxin producing *E. coli* (VTEC) in Graz where the presence of the *stx*-genes, *eae*-genes and additional virulence factors is tested by PCR. Subsequently the VTEC is serotyped conventionally (antisera).

In 2013, a harmonisation of the method within all microbiological laboratories for foodstuff according to ISO 13136 is planned.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

In 2012, 533 samples of animal origin, 186 samples of non-animal origin and 22 samples of other processed food products and prepared dishes were tested for VTEC. 4 out of 63 (6.3 %) samples from milk, milk products and cheeses (all from cows', sheeps' or goats' milk) were positive for VTEC. Three of the positive findings were cheeses made of raw milk or low heat-treated milk.

124 samples of fresh meat of several animals (bovine animals, deer, pig, poultry, rabbit, sheep, turkey, wild boar, wild game birds) were tested for VTEC resulting in 12 positive samples (9.7 %). The highest prevalence of VTEC was detected in fresh meat from deer (venison) in 33.3 % (10 out of 30). 345 samples of different meat products, meat preparations, mixed meat etc. were tested for VTEC showing 7 positive findings (2 %).

0.5% of all vegetables, fruits, mushrooms and other food of non-animal origin were positive for VTEC (1 out of 186), but none of other processed food products and prepared dishes.

Due to the O104-outbreak in 2011 with sprouts as the source of infection two campaigns focused on fruits and vegetables, testing 135 samples without finding a single VTEC. A third campaign investigated meat products from deer, where 2 of 65 samples were found positive (3.1 %).

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-006-12: VTEC in food - fruits and vegetables - at border control - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

40 samples at border control (Vienna Airport)

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January - April

Type of specimen taken

Padan leaves, Sadau leaves, Yellow Turmanic, Yodkhea, Cha Om, young green pepper, Morminy fly, Chinese Chive Leaves, lemon grass, tomatoes, strawberries, Pak Waan, Okra, Kra Chai, Tamlueng, others

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *stx1*- and/or *stx2*-positive E. coli.

Results of the investigation

No VTEC detected in 40 samples tested.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Salmonella

Campaign A-801-12: VTEC in food - fruits and vegetables - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May - July

Type of specimen taken

packaged sprouts, strawberries and cutted salad

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *stx1*- and/or *stx2*-positive E. coli.

Results of the investigation

No VTEC detected in 95 samples tested.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Salmonella

Campaign A-804-12: VTEC in food – Meat from deer (venison) - meat products - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: August – November

Type of specimen taken

Meat from wild game, cured and raw sausages

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *stx1*- and/or *stx2*-positive E. coli.

Results of the investigation

Two VTEC isolated from 65 samples tested (Orough:Hrough and O166:H12).

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Listeria

Table 87 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli in food, 2012 part 1

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive	VTEC O22:H8 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O51:H49 - eae positive vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O74:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O76:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O107:H4 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O128abc:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O143:H8 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H28 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O166:H12 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O181:H49 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC ONT:H9 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H30 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC OX185:H16 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	
Cheeses made from cows' milk - curd	at processing plant	AT	single	1	Gram	1	0																						
				2	Gram	1	0																						
Cheeses made from cows' milk - curd	at retail	AT	single	3	Gram	1	0																						
				25	Gram	1	1																	1					
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at retail	AT	single	1	Gram	1	0																						
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25	Gram	1	1					1																	
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT	single	25	Gram	1	0																						
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single	1	Gram	1	0																						
				2	Gram	1	0																						
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	at retail	AT	single	4	Gram	1	0																						
				1	Gram	3	0																						
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single	25	Gram	1	0																						
				1	Gram	4	0																						
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT	single	4	Gram	1	0																						
				5	Gram	2	0																						
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	AT	single	1	Gram	5	0																						
				FR	single	1	Gram	1	0																				
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at retail	IT	single	25	Gram	1	0																						
				XX	single	1	Gram	1	0																				
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single	1	Gram	1	0																						
				at retail	AT	single	25	Gram	1	1																			
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	at processing plant	AT	single	1	Gram	1	0																						
				5	Gram	1	0																						
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	at processing plant	AT	single	1	Gram	2	0																						

Table 90 Verocytotoxic Escherichia coli in food, 2012 part 4

Food	Sampling Details		Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive	VTEC O2:H8 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O5:1:H49 - eae positive vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O7:4:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O7:6:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O7:6:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O1:07:H4 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O1:28abc:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O1:43:H8 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O1:46:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O1:46:H28 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O1:46:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O1:66:H12 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O1:81:H49 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC ONT:H9 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H30 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:through - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC OX:185:H16 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive								
	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage																																			
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	at processing plant	AT	single	25	Gram	8	0																														
		at retail	AT	single	25	Gram	5	0																													
			IT	single	25	Gram	1	0																													
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	at game handling establishment	AT	single	25	Gram	1	0																														
		AT	single	25	Gram	38	1																														
	at retail	AT	single	25	Gram	87	2	1				1																									
		DE	single	25	Gram	4	0																														
		ES	single	25	Gram	3	0																														
		IT	single	25	Gram	5	0																														
SI	single	25	Gram	3	0																																
XX	single	25	Gram	8	0																																
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	at retail	AT	single	25	Gram	7	0																														
Milk, cows' - raw milk	at farm	AT	single	25	Gram	1	0																														
	at processing plant	AT	single	25	Gram	2	0																														
	at retail	AT	single	25	Gram	3	0																														
Milk, cows' - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat treated products	at farm	AT	single	25	Gram	1	0																														
	at retail	AT	single	25	Gram	1	0																														
Milk, sheep's - raw milk	at retail	AT	single	25	Gram	1	0																														
Mushrooms	at retail	AT	single	25	Gram	3	0																														
		DE	single	25	Gram	2	0																														
		HU	single	25	Gram	1	0																														
		TH	single	25	Gram	1	0																														
Other food of non-animal origin	at retail	AT	single	1	Gram	1	0																														
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	at catering	AT	single	25	Gram	1	0																														
	at retail	AT	single	1	Gram	7	0																														
		IT	single	25	Gram	13	1	1																													
Vegetables	at processing plant	AT	single	25	Gram	3	0																														
	at retail	AT	single	25	Gram	13	0																														
		DE	single	25	Gram	2	0																														
		FR	single	25	Gram	2	0																														
		HU	single	25	Gram	3	0																														
		IT	single	25	Gram	4	1																														
MA	single	25	Gram	1	0																																
Vegetables - products	at processing plant	AT	single	25	Gram	5	0																														

4.4.4. Pathogenic Escherichia coli in animals

A. Verotoxigenic Escherichia coli in cattle (bovine animals)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

The monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in slaughtered cattle was continued. The sampling was stratified based on the number of processed animals per abattoir in Austria. The date of sampling was randomized over the year 2012. Sampling was performed in the 25 abattoirs which processed more than 80 % of Austria's cattle in 2011.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at slaughter

The sampling was distributed randomly over the period of the study from January to December 2012.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at slaughter

A part of the intestine containing rectum and anus.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at slaughter

The sampling is performed by qualified veterinarians who carry out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration, a part of rectum and anus was sampled. After cooling down to 4 °C, the sample had been sent to the AGES Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz the same day, in a hobbox or polystyrene box along with cooling packs. In the laboratory, a swab from the rectum-anal mucosa was incubated in a broth.

Case definition

Animals at slaughter

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verotoxin producing E. coli irrespective of intimin) from its recto-anal mucosa.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at slaughter

In a first step the samples were screened for presence of verotoxins by ELISA, secondly the positive samples were processed for VTEC isolation.

At first the swab was pre-enriched using modified tryptic soy broth containing novobiocin (mTSB + n) for 5 hours at 37 °C on a shaker. Then 1 ml of each pre-enrichment was inoculated into mTSB + n containing mitomycin C for 18-20 hours at 37 °C on a shaker too. The process was followed by testing the enrichment for the presence of verotoxin in an enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA, Premier TM EHEC). Sediment of positive enrichments were plated on sorbitol MacConkey (SMAC) -, on cefixime tellurite sorbitol MAC (CTSMAC) - and on enterohemolysin agar and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. 5 colonies from each sample were subcultured on SMAC as well as on CTSMAC. Afterwards the genomes of subcultured E. coli were investigated in a real time PCR for harboring the genes for Verotoxin 1, Verotoxin 2, Intimin and Enterohemolysin (Reischl U. et al. 2002: Real-Time Fluorescence PCR Assays for Detection and Characterization of Shiga Toxin, Intimin and Enterohemolysin Genes from Shiga Toxin-Producing Escherichia coli. Journ of Clin Microb, 40, p 2555-2565).

The serotyping was carried out by the National Reference Center for VTEC in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen

Notification system in place

No notification system in place at this time.

Results of the investigation

See table.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from bovine remained high (35 %); we hypothesize that this is due to a high sensitivity of the ELISA, the sampling material (recto-anal swabs) and the improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques especially the use of the enterohemolysin-agar. Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), O157 (2 x), O26 (2 x) and O103 (1 x) were isolated from cattle.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in feces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC) in animal - Sheep

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in sheep at farm:

The monitoring in 2012 was directed towards sheep at farms. 124 sheep (out of 124 different farms) had to be tested, calculated on a population of sheep of 350,000 in Austria in 2011. The sampling had been stratified on the number and size of sheep holdings in Austrian provinces.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at farm:

The sampling was done after blood sampling in course of the Brucella melitensis control program.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at farm:

Recto-anal swabs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at farm:

The swab was sent in transport medium cooled down to 4 °C and the fleece in a separate plastic bag in a hobbox or polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the AGES Institute of Veterinary Diseases Control (IVET) in Graz. In the laboratory, the swab and fleece were inoculated into separate broths.

Case definition

Animals at farm

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verotoxin producing E. coli irrespective of intimin) from one of the samples tested.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at farm

In a first step the samples were screened for presence of verotoxins by ELISA, secondly the positive samples were processed for VTEC isolation, see chapter cattle.

The serotyping was carried out by the National Reference Laboratory for VTEC in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen

Notification system in place

No notification

Results of the investigation

See table.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from sheep remained high (65 %) but we hypothesize that this is due to a higher sensitivity of the new ELISA, the sampling material (recto-anal swabs) and the improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques especially the use of the enterohemolysin-agar. Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), only O157 (1 x) was isolated from sheep.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in/on sheep seems to be low because sheep meat is consumed well-done.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 91 Verotoxin producing Escherichia coli in animals, 2012

animal species	sampling context	Sampling stage	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	Verotoxin ELISA positive	units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC O5:H5 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O5:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O5:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O5:HNM - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O6:H10 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O15:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O15:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O22:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O26:HNM - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O27:H30 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O36:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O36:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O39:H48 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O43:H2 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O43:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O46:H2 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O74:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O75:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O76:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O76:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O76:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O76:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O79:H12 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O81:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O81:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O87:H16 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive		
Cattle (bovine animal(s) - adult cattle over 2 years	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum- anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	56	25	18	0	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cattle (bovine animal(s) - calves (under 1 year)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum- anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	4	4	3	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cattle (bovine animal(s) - young cattle (1-2 years)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum- anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	56	24	20	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	2	3	-	1	1	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sheep	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	IVET Graz	Animal	124	87	80	1	1	9	8	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	1	-	1	1	4	1	3	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	

In some samples more than 1 VTEC-isolate could be identified.

animal species	sampling context	Sampling stage	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	Verotoxin ELISA positive	units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC O89:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H10 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O103:H2 - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O107:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O109:H16 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O112ab:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O113:H4 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:H4 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O128abc:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O128abc:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O129:HNM - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O137:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O150:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O150:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O157:H7 - eae positive vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O157:HNM - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O166:H28 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O166:H28 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O166:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative			
Cattle (bovine animal(s) - adult cattle over 2 years	Monitoring - official sampling - objective	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	56	25	18	0	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Cattle (bovine animal(s) - calves (under 1 year)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	4	4	3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Cattle (bovine animal(s) - young cattle (1-2 years)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	56	24	20	1	-	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Sheep	Monitoring - official sampling - objective	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	IVET Graz	Animal	124	87	80	1	1	-	-	-	2	1	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	7	4	2	1	1	1	1	1	4	2	1	

In some samples more than 1 VTEC-isolate could be identified.

animal species	sampling context	Sampling stage	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	Verotoxin ELISA positive	units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC O168:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O174:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O174:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O176:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O178:H7 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O178:H12 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O178:H19 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O178:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O178:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O179:H8 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O179:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O179:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O183:H18 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O185:H5 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC ONT:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC ONT:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H8 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative			
Cattle (bovine animal(s) - adult cattle over 2 years	Monitoring - official sampling - objective	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum- anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	56	25	18	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Cattle (bovine animal(s) - calves (under 1 year)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum- anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	4	4	3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cattle (bovine animal(s) - young cattle (1-2 years)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum- anal)	IVET Graz	Animal	56	24	20	1	2	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	2	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sheep	Monitoring - official sampling - objective	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	IVET Graz	Animal	124	87	80	1	-	1	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

In some samples more than 1 VTEC-isolate could be identified.

4.5. Tuberculosis

4.5.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human tuberculosis has steadily declined during the last decades. Commission Decision 1999/467/EC of 15 July 1999 declared bovine herds of Austria officially tuberculosis-free.

In humans the number of tuberculosis cases is decreasing. Cases of *M. bovis* or *M. caprae* are very seldom and reactivations of past infections. All *M. caprae* cases in humans in the last years showed different molecular typing patterns than the *M. caprae* isolated from cattle; therefore no human cases could be attributed to the recently cases in bovines.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Bovine tuberculosis poses no public health problem in Austria. Sheep, goats and pigs are free of bovine tuberculosis. Although in spring 2008 infective lung tuberculosis caused by *M. caprae* was diagnosed in one slaughtered cattle. All cattle of that holding were culled following an intra cutan testing showing several positive reactors. Two more cattle holdings with several reactors were culled and some single reactors in contact holdings. In 21 cattle out of 14 holdings *M. caprae* was isolated in 2008. In 2009 again 6 cattle out of 3 holdings were bacteriologically confirmed and in 2010 eight cattle were identified as infected with *M. caprae* and 2011 three cases were found to be positive for *M. caprae*. In 2012, 25 bovines out of three herds were infected with *M. caprae*. Since several years a reservoir of *M. caprae* in red deer in an Austrian region has been confirmed and cattle are exposed to the bacteria in the summertime grazing on contaminated pastures in the Alps.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings of *M. bovis* in animals, although *M. caprae* was detected. The single case of *M. caprae* in humans in 2012 is epidemiologically not linked to the *M. caprae* cases in animals.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2011 a new regulation has been implemented to control *M. caprae* in red deer (BGBl. II Nr. 181/2011). The regulation (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322) obliges the intracutan testings (using simultaneously bovine and avium tuberculin) of all cattle and goats that are kept together with cattle in given districts due to the epidemiological situation.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

Nil

4.5.2. Tuberculosis in humans

A. Tuberculosis due to *Mycobacterium bovis* in humans

Case definition

Definite: A case with isolation of *M. tuberculosis* complex (except *M. bovis* BCG) from any clinical specimen.

Other than definite: A case that meets the clinical criteria above but does not meet the laboratory criteria of a definite case.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Definite: Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen, Auramin-Rhodamin stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material
- Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC-NaOH and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and MGITmedium. The media are incubated at 37 °C for up to 8 weeks. Confirmation of the species by Amplicor (Roche)
- Other than definite: A skin test and an X-Ray of the thorax are performed.

Notification system in place

The person who diagnoses (laboratory/hospital/general practitioner) has to notify definite (*M. tuberculosis* and *M. bovis*) and other than definite cases (this excludes radiologists) to the local health authority (Federal Law BGBl. 127/1968: Tuberkulosegesetz, as amended; Epidemiegesetz 1950, as amended). *M. bovis* is notifiable since 2004 (National Regulation BGBl. Nr. 254/2004: Anzeigepflichtige übertragbare Krankheiten 2004).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The National Reference Center for Tuberculosis (NRC-T) has been nominated since 1995. Since 1998 all data are compiled in a national database.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

One case of *M. bovis* and one case of *M. caprae* were identified; the human *M. caprae* case was epidemiologically not linked to the cases in cattle.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

The relevance is inconsiderable.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.
Annual report of the National Reference Center

Table 92 Tuberculosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (NRC), 2012

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Tuberculosis	404	4,79		
<i>M. bovis</i>	1	0,01	unknown	unknown
<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	385	4,56	unknown	unknown
<i>M. caprae</i>	1	0,01	1	0
<i>M. tuberculosis</i> complex (not differentiated)	16	0,19	5	11
<i>M. africanum</i>	1	0,01	0	1
Reactivation of previous cases	0	0	0	0

Data source: National Reference Center for Tuberculosis as of June 7, 2013

Table 93 Tuberculosis in humans - age distribution (NRC), 2012

Age group	Tuberculosis due to <i>M. tuberculosis</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. bovis</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. caprae</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. africanum</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. tuberculosis</i> complex (not differentiated)		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	3	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	9	3	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	68	38	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
25 to 44 years	134	78	56	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	3	1	2
45 to 64 years	94	64	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	5	1
65 years and older	76	44	32	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	6	3	3
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	385	229	156	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	16	10	6

Data source: National Reference Center for Tuberculosis as of June 7, 2013

4.5.3. Mycobacterium spp. in animals

A. Mycobacterium bovis in bovine animals

Status as officially free of bovine tuberculosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Council Directive 64/432/EWG from June 26, 1964, Austria has the status Officially Tuberculosis Free Member State declared in the Commission Decision 1999/467/EC from July 15th, 1999, replaced by Commission Decision 2003/467/EC from June 23rd, 2003. The monitoring programme is based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection in which all cattle and goats originating from an official tuberculosis free holding have to be tested for tuberculous alterations. A national Regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008). This Regulation includes provisions which apply for all Mycobacteria belonging to the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex; therefore also a compulsory notification exists.

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Specimens are taken from carcasses with macroscopically observable alterations, characteristic for tuberculosis. They are sampled in slaughterhouses and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

All cattle in holdings of designated regions according article 2 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008) and published in the Official Veterinary Bulletin were subjected to simultaneous intracutan testing.

Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered bovine and caprine animal.

Intracutan testing: All cattle in holdings of designated regions according article 2 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008) and published in the Official Veterinary Bulletin.

Type of specimen taken

Organs/tissues: Tissues that are macroscopically altered due to tuberculosis, inclusive lymph nodes (according to Annex 4 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008).

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The alterations and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

Case definition

According to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008 idgF - Tuberculosis: Infection with Mycobacteria of the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex. Results of the intracutan test: A reactor is each animal which is not negative (either doubtful or positive). Doubtful and positive reactions are defined (see Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008 idgF).

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Intracutan testing (simultaneous testing using bovine and avium tuberculin): The test is performed according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, as amended and the national Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals in Mödling - After decontamination of the homogenised sample material (2g, homogenised, add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörens. Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (heipha/biotest: Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing antibiotics (PACT) and Stonebrink agar containing pyruvate and PACT). The media are incubated at 37°C ± 1°C up to 12 weeks. MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany).

Vaccination policy

Due to the importance of the intracutan tests for diagnostic purposes, vaccinations are prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered bovine and caprine carcasses originating from official tuberculosis free holding and intracutan tests in animals of given regions according to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered bovine and caprine carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding. Intracutan tests are performed in animals in holdings of given regions according to the epidemiological situation, defined in the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A national Regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008). This Regulation includes provisions which apply for all mycobacteria belonging to the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex; therefore also a compulsory notification exists.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned.

Loss of the status OTF for the holding from which the animal was originated and for contact holdings. It is prohibited to bring bovines and goats in and out of the holding. Slaughtering of cows and goats can only be allowed by the official veterinarian and has to be performed using a special testing and slaughtering frame. Epidemiological investigations have to be done.

Prohibition of keeping these animals together with animals from OTF-holdings on pastures or market places etc.

Regaining the status OTF:

There must be no animals in the holding showing signs of clinical tuberculosis

All animals are recruited from an OTF-holding

Animals have to be tested according to the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

No reactors are identified after two intradermal testings of all animals in the holding older than 6 months examined earliest 60 days (first tuberculin test) and earliest 4 months (second tuberculin test) but latest 12 months after elimination of the last reactor.

Notification system in place

A suspected case of tuberculosis must be notified.

Results of the investigation

In 2012 no findings of *M. bovis* in cattle. In total 25 bovines from 3 herds were infected with *M. caprae*.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of *M. bovis* in cattle. In total 25 bovines from 3 herds were infected with *M. caprae*. Due to the fact that *M. caprae* is endemic in wildlife deer in Western parts of Austria (and South-Western parts of Germany), cattle in this areas has been observed with higher sensitivity.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

M. caprae is differentiated in Austria.

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Mycobacterium* spp. in animal - all animals - at slaughter – Control programme - mandatory - official sampling (all slaughtered animals except those mentioned above)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Samples from suspected swine are taken in slaughterhouses. Sampling is performed when tissue of slaughtered animals is visibly altered, seen by the unaided eye.

Goats in defined regions that are kept together with cattle are subjected to intracutan testing (see chapter *Mycobacterium bovis* bovine animals; Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008).

Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered animal

Type of specimen taken

Other: Macroscopic tuberculous alterations and lymphnodes

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The altered tissue and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the laboratory

Case definition

Tubercles pathognomically for tuberculosis detected in course of the post-mortem inspection or *Mycobacteria* of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex isolated from suspected material.

Tuberculosis (for bovines and goats which are kept together with bovines): Infection with *Mycobacteria* of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex.

Results of the intracutan test: A reactor is each animal which is not negative (either doubtful or positive).

Reactions are defined (see Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008).

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals in Mödling - After decontamination of the homogenised sample material (2g, homogenised, add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörens. Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (heipha/biotest: Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing antibiotics (PACT) and Stonebrink agar containing pyruvate and PACT). The media are incubated at 37°C ± 1°C up to 12 weeks. MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany).

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

See other chapters.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No need at the moment

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned. Further measures are performed according to Tierseuchengesetz RGBL. 1909/177, as amended.

Notification system in place

The detection of tuberculosis is notifiable.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No cases in Austria in 2012.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No cases in Austria in 2012.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 94 Bovine tuberculosis in countries and regions that do not receive Community co-financing for eradication programme, 2012

Member State: Austria..... Date of the report: 13.05.2013..... Year: 2012.....

The official post-mortem examination for all slaughtered bovine animals is implemented: Yes

Region (¹)	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds * all <i>M. caprae</i>		Routine tuberculin testing		Number of tuberculin tests carried out before the introduction into the herds (Annex A(I)(2)(c) third indent (¹) of Directive 64/432/EEC)	Number of animals with suspicious lesions of tuberculosis examined and submitted to histopathological and bacteriological examinations	Number of animals detected positive in bacteriological examination*
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Interval between routine tuberculin tests (²)	Number of animals tested			
Austria	69,430	1,976,698	69,427	99.996	3	0.004	a) and g)	6,501	123	77	25
Total	69,430	1,976,698	69,427	99.996	3	0.004	a) and g)	6,501	123	77	25

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Use the following letter codes: (a) no routine tests; (b) tests once a year; (c) tests every two years; (d) tests every three years concerning 24 month-old animals; (f) tests every 4 years; (g) others (please give details) Sonderuntersuchungs- bzw. überwachungsgebiet.

* In 2012, 25 bovines of 3 herds (0,004 %) were infected with *M. caprae* : The control program is identical to the program to control *M. bovis*.

Table 95 Tuberculosis in other animals, 2012

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Mycobacteriaspp.</i>	<i>M. bovis</i>	<i>M. caprae</i>
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	130,756	0	0	0
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	5,147	0	0	0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	5,396,345	0	0	0
Cattle*	at farm – animal sampling	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - selective sampling	tuberculin testing in special tuberculosis examination and control areas	CVS	animal	6,501	25*	0	25*

*TBC-Sonderuntersuchungsgebiete sowie TBC-Sonderüberwachungsgebiete

CVS: Central veterinary services

* all cases microbiologically verified as *M. caprae* cases

4.6. Brucellosis

4.6.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In Austria, human brucellosis cases are considered to be an imported infectious disease. The Austrian cattle, sheep and goat population bears the status Officially Brucellosis Free (OBF) and Officially Brucella melitensis free (OBmF).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Three human cases were identified in 2012. The number of Brucellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings in Austria, OBF and OBmF

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A national regulation has been implemented. The examination of milk- and bloodsamples in cattle (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 2007/305).

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.6.2. Brucellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Brucellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with fever

AND at least one of following seven symptoms:

- Sweating (profuse, malodorous, specially nocturnal)
- Chills
- Arthralgia
- Weakness
- Depression
- Headache
- Anorexia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Brucella* spp. from a clinical specimen
- *Brucella* specific antibody response (Standard Agglutination Test, Complement Fixation, ELISA)

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Serological examination: Serum samples are tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT.

- Bacteriological: Multiple blood samples are inoculated in blood culture broth over several consecutive days. The incubation lasted 4 to 6 weeks, once per week medium is transferred on brucella agar and incubated 5-10 % CO₂ atmosphere (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123- 126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 56).

- The genus is identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species is identified by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.)

Notification system in place

Notification of Brucellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is OBF and OBmF. All cases reported in Austria are epidemiologically linked to travel in endemic countries or to foreign workers from endemic countries.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This zoonosis has no relevance in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 96 Brucellosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2012

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	Unknown cases
Brucellosis	3	0.04	1	1	1
B. abortus	0	-	-	-	-
B. melitensis	1	0.01	-	1	-
B. suis	0	-	-	-	-
Brucella spp.	2	0.02	1	-	1

Data source: EMS (as of 28.04.2013)

Table 97 Brucellosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2012

Age group	Brucella melitensis			Brucella not specified		
	all	M	F	all	M	F
< 1 year	-	-	-	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 to 14 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
15 to 24 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
25 to 44 years	1	-	1	1	1	-
45 to 64 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
65 years and older	-	-	-	1	1	-
Age unknown	-	-	-	-	-	-
All age groups	1	0	1	2	2	0

Data source: EMS (as of 28.04.2013)

4.6.3. Brucella in foodstuffs

Due to the fact that Austria is OBF and OBmF, food is not investigated for Brucella spp.

4.6.4. Brucella spp. in animals

A. Brucella abortus in Bovine Animals

Status as officially free of bovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

Upon the request of the Commission Decision of July 15th 1999, CD 1999/466/EC, as amended, by the Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, Austria achieved the status: officially brucellosis-free for bovine herds.

A national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and bloodsamples in cattle (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 305/2007). In the case of dairy herds, the examination of milk samples in accordance with Annex C of Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964 can be performed.

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Nationwide all bovine milk producing holdings were subjected to bulk milk testing.

In non-milk producing holdings a risk based sampling plan was performed.

Abortion or premature birth: Abortive material and blood of the cow is sampled

Frequency of the sampling

Bulk milk sampling: All milk producing holdings had been sampled minimum once per year according to the regulation (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 305/2007). In case of not-negative bulk milk samples, blood samples in the affected holding were investigated.

Holdings without milk production: A risk based sampling plan has been calculated stratified according to the different provinces (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 2007/305). If blood serology does not show a definitive negative result diagnostic slaughtering of the affected animal has to be carried out.

- Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood from the cow is sampled immediately post abortion. If the result of the first serological examination was negative, a second blood sample was taken 2 weeks post abortion for serological testing. If this result was negative again, sampling and testing was repeated after two weeks.

Type of specimen taken

Bulk milk

Blood samples

Diagnostic slaughtering: organs and lymph nodes of the genital tract; udder and accessory lymph nodes; fetus (stomach, lungs); retropharyngeal lymph node.

Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood samples from the animal that had an abortion.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Bulk milk sampling: §6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 305/2007.

Holdings without milk production: According to the sampling plan individual blood samples are taken in the holdings and sent to the laboratories (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 2007/305).

Diagnostic slaughtering: §6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 305/2007.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted tissue and blood samples sent to a veterinary laboratory.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be positive for *Brucella abortus*, in case of positive blood-serological test result and the epidemiological situation of the herd indicates the possibility that a brucella infection has been introduced to the herd or in case of bacteriological isolation. If a single animal reactor is detected in the holding, tracing back is an important tool to get more information about the animal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bulk milk: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE.

Blood samples: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE: Routinely single serum samples or serum pools (5 sera in one pool) were tested in the Indirect-ELISA (I-ELISA) using the three OIE ELISA Brucella Standard Sera (OIE ELISAwSS, OIE ELISAspSS, OIE ELISAnSS) and the OIE Brucella abortus Positive International Standard Antiserum (OIEISS) to calibrate the method (Commission Regulation 535/2002/EC of 21 March 2002 amending Annex C to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and amending Decision 2000/330/EC). Following a positive or suspected test result in the IELISA single serum samples were also tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT), Rose Bengal test (RBT) and Competitive ELISA (C-ELISA).

Participation in international ring trials: Participation in international ring trials (Weybridge, AFSSA and other) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted material was tested bacteriologically and serologically as described above.

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method. Brucella agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives were used (Oxoid). After inoculation the media were incubated for 4-10 days at 37°C in an atmosphere containing 10% CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not allowed (BGBl. 147/1957, Bangseuchengesetz, § 13 Impfung)

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Control programme according to the National Regulation (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 305/2007). Abortion or premature birth: Compulsory notification according BGBl 147/1957, Bangseuchengesetz, as amended, §11 Anzeigepflicht;

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions, because OBF

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to BGBl 147/1957, Bangseuchengesetz, as amended, and BGBl 177/1909, Tierseuchengesetz, as amended

Notification system in place

Abortion or premature birth: Notification of abortions: The livestock owner has to notify each abortion within 24 hours to the mayor (Gemeinde). The mayor has to forward the notification to the local authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde) (BGBl. 147/1957, Bangseuchengesetz, § 11 Anzeigepflicht). If the cow is being treated by a veterinarian or the veterinarian has been informed about the abortion, then the veterinarian has to notify to the official authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

OBF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Brucella melitensis* in Sheep and Goats

Status as officially free of ovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Commission Decision Nr. 93/52/EWG, as amended, Austria has the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free (ObmF).

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. II 184/2002 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples were examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a target prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling was performed by the competent authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it had delegated this responsibility. Samples were taken in the holdings. Aborted material and blood samples from the animal were also investigated.

Frequency of the sampling

Principally the sampling was performed during the cold season, between November and May when the animals were kept in the stables.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples according to a sampling plan.
- Clinical cases: Aborted material and blood samples from the affected animal.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and aborted material are taken within the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be infected with *B. melitensis* in case of bacteriological isolation or positive serological test result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Routinely single serum samples were tested in the Indirect ELISA. Confirmation of suspected or positive results was performed by the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials on Brucellosis (Weybridge and other) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all national Veterinary Institutes.

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples were stained by Stableforth's method. *Brucella* agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media are incubated for 4 - 10 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The

genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

According to BGBl. II 184/2002 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, §4, Impfverbot) vaccination is not allowed.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Monitoring program and investigation of abortions

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples have to be examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling is performed by the appropriate authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it has delegated this responsibility. Samples are taken in the holdings.

Notification and clarification of each clinical case by bacteriology and serology.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

ObmF

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, §3, Ausmerzung von Reagenten) reactors have to be culled, the carcasses have to be incinerated in an incineration plant.

Notification system in place

Notification of brucellosis or a suspicion of brucellosis according to BGBl. II 184/2002 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

ObmF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

D. *Brucella suis* in animal – Pigs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

According to Guideline 64/432/EEC as amended.

Frequency of the sampling

Targeted, following abortion and in positive cases contact holdings.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples;
- Clinical cases: Abortion material and blood samples from the affected animal; tissues: according to decree 74700/0132-IV/B/5/2008

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and abortion material are taken from animals in the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be serologically positive for brucellosis following one/more positive CFT Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and RBT Rose Bengal test (RBT) results (*B. abortus* used antigen). A bacteriological isolation may also be possible as in the case of *B. suis*.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Due to the fact that a *Brucella suis* antigen is not available, the *B. abortus* antigen is used for the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and the Rose Bengal test (RBT) because *B. abortus* shows cross reactions with *B. suis* antibodies.
 - ELISA and CFT is not available, the *B. abortus* ELISA and CFT are used because these tests show cross reactions with *B. suis* antibodies.
 - Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes.
- Bacteriology: Quality control: Laboratory strains
- Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method
 - *Brucella* agar and Columbia agar (Merck) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media are incubated for 4-10 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using brucella serum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific sera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No mandatory measures but notification is required.

Notification system in place

B. suis has been a notifiable disease since 1993 according to BGBl 1993/756, Tierseuchen-Anzeigepflichtverordnung, as amended.

Results of the investigation

There was no case of Brucella suis in 2012.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Due to the results of the passive monitoring in pigs we conclude that there is no need for an active monitoring program.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 98 Bovine Brucellosis data from countries and regions that do not receive Community co-financing (non co-financed), 2012

Member State: Austria Date of report: 13.05.2013..... Year: 2012.....

Region ⁽¹⁾	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance ⁽²⁾						Investigations of suspect cases								
			Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Serological tests			Examination of bulk milk samples			Information on abortions			Epidemiological investigation					
	Herds	Animals					Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals or pools tested	Number of infected herds	Number of notified abortions whatever cause	Number of isolations of <i>Brucella</i> infection	Number of abortions due to <i>Brucella abortus</i>	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of suspended herds	Number of positive animals		Number of animals examined microbiologically	Number of animals positive microbiologically
Austria	69,430	1,976,698	69,430	100	0	0	3,492	29,092	0	31,241	31,244	0	1,118	0	0	1,775	139	0	0		
Total	69,430	1,976,698	69,430	100	0	0	3,492	29,092	0	31,241	31,244	0	1,118	0	0	1,775	139	0	0	0	0

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Table 99 Ovine and caprine brucellosis - data from countries that do not receive co-financing for control or eradication programme, 2012

Member State: Austria..... Date of report: 21.05.2013..... Year: 2012.....

Region (¹)	Total number of existing ovine/caprine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance (²)			Investigations of suspect cases				
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Number of herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of animals positive serologically	Number of animals examined micro-biologically	Number of animals positive micro-biologically	Number of suspended herds
Austria	23,787	515,913	23,787	100	0	0	1,459	17,367	0	8	0	0	0	2
Total	23,787	515,913	23,787	100	0	0	1,459	17,367	0	8	0	0	0	2

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services, Provincial Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Total number of existing ovine/caprine herds: Number is less than in Table 1 (Susceptible animal populations) because mixed farms are deducted from the sum.

4.7. Yersiniosis

4.7.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is not considered a major food borne illness in Austria. The incidence of human disease is low when compared to salmonellosis or campylobacteriosis and has been stable over the last years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of Yersiniosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

The sources of infections are unclear. Neither studies on sporadic cases nor scientific outbreak investigations were performed in Austria so far.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.7.2. Yersiniosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Yersiniosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following five symptoms:

- Fever
- Diarrhoea
- Vomiting
- Abdominal pain (pseudoappendicitis)
- Tenesmus

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of human pathogenic *Yersinia enterocolitica* or *Yersinia pseudotuberculosis* from a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Faecal (*Yersinia enterocolitica*) or resection (*Y. pseudotuberculosis*) sample material is plated directly on cefsulodin-irgasan-novobiocin (CIN) agar and incubated for 18 hours at 30 °C. Suspicious colonies are identified in an Api 20 E reaction and API 50 CHE reaction. *Y. enterocolitica* is agglutinated with sera against serogroups O:3, O:5, O:9 and O:8. Biovar and pathogenicity are defined.

Notification system in place

Notification of Yersiniosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is the third most bacterial food borne pathogen in Austria although compared to salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, the number of notified cases are much lower.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of human cases has been similar in the last years.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Yersiniosis is the third most bacterial food borne pathogen in Austria although compared to salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, the number of notified cases are much lower.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 100 Yersiniosis in human - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2012

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Imported cases	Unknown status
Yersiniosis	130	1,54	14	21
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	113	1,34	12	19
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:3	65	0,77	8	12
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:9	12	0,14	-	-
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> biovar 4	3	0,04	-	-
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:5_27	2	0,02	-	-
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:1	1	0,01	-	-
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> biovar 1A	1	0,01	-	1
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> biovar 3	1	0,01	-	-
serotype unknown	28	0,33	4	6
<i>Y. pseudotuberculosis</i>	3	0,04	-	-
<i>Yersinia</i> spp. (species unknown)	14	0,17	2	2

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

Table 101 Yersiniosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2012

age groups	<i>Yersinia</i> spp			<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i>			<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:3			<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:9			<i>Yersinia pseudotuberculosis</i>		
	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	2	1	1	2	1	1	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	32	13	19	30	11	19	23	8	15	2	1	1	-	-	-
5 to 14 years	27	16	11	23	12	11	16	7	9	3	2	1	1	-	1
15 to 24 years	18	9	9	15	8	7	6	3	3	2	-	2	-	1	1
25 to 44 years	14	11	3	11	9	2	6	4	2	-	-	-	-	-	-
45 to 64 years	30	12	18	25	9	16	11	5	6	4	3	1	-	1	1
65 years and older	7	2	5	7	2	5	3	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
Gesamtergebnis	130	64	66	113	52	61	65	27	38	12	7	5	1	2	3

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

4.7.3. Yersinia spp. in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not relevant in Austria therefore no testing.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

EU wide harmonized monitoring program.

Notification system in place:

Findings of Yersinia are not notifiable in animals.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No changes in recent years.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance has not been investigated.

Additional information

Nil

4.8. Trichinellosis

4.8.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

No documented autochthon human infestations since several years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of Trichinellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of cases reported to the EMS. No documented autochthone human infestations in 2012.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No cases in animals in 2012.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No new measures implemented

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the necessity of routine trichinella meat inspection in pig carcasses

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.8.2. Trichinellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Trichinellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least three of the following six symptoms:

- Fever
- Muscle soreness and pain
- Diarrhoea
- Facial oedema
- Eosinophilia
- Subconjunctival, subungual and retinal haemorrhages

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Demonstration of Trichinella larvae in tissue obtained by muscle biopsy
- Trichinella specific antibody response (IFA test, ELISA or Western Blot)

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot

Notification system in place

Notification of Trichinellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The last autochthonous cases have been reported in 1970

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

No relevance in Austria

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry of Health. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 102 Trichinellosis in human - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2012

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Imported cases	Unkown
Trichinellosis	0	0.00	0	0
Trichinella spiralis	0	0.00	0	0

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

4.8.3. Trichinella in animals

A. Trichinella spp. in pigs

Number of officially recognised Trichinella-free holdings

Categories of holdings officially recognised Trichinella-free

Officially recognised regions with negligible Trichinella risk

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

General

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered pigs except pigs slaughtered by the farmer for his own consumption; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

General

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered pig

Type of specimen taken

General

Muscles: Diaphragm (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

General

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

General

Trichinella spp. detected with one of the given methods

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Preventive measures in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004, as amended.

The contingency plan in place

Notification system in place

Results of the investigation including description of the positive cases and the verification of the Trichinella species

No cases detected

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of Trichinella in pigs.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. Trichinella spp. in horses

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered horses; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered horse

Type of specimen taken

Muscles from tongue, masseter, diaphragm and neck.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

Trichinella spp. detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

Results of the investigation

No findings in horses.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. *Trichinella* spp. in animal - wild boars

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Sampling of all hunted or harvested wild boars; the sampling is performed by hunters with special knowledge about trichinella investigation or by competent authorities; the sampling is stratified by geographical regions depending to the habitats of wild boar in Austria; samples are taken either immediately after shooting the animal or at the cold storage depots; the sampling is part of a monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

All farmed wild boars are controlled for trichinella.

Type of specimen taken

Diaphragm muscles (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

Trichinella spp. detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2012, *Trichinella* spp. was not detected neither in farmed nor in wild animals.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 103 *Trichinella* spp. in animals, 2012

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Trichinella</i> spp.
Pigs							
fattening pigs raised under controlled housing conditions in integrated system							
fattening pigs not raised under controlled housing conditions in integrated system	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	5,396,345	0
breeding animals -unspecified - sows and boars							
Domestic solipeds							
horses	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	933	0
Wild boars							
wild	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	33,426	0
farmed	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	731	0
Foxes							
Badger				CVS	animal	28	0
Bears							
Rodents							
Rats							

CVS: Central Veterinary Services

4.9. Echinococcosis

4.9.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is a low risk country for both forms of echinococcosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of echinococcosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases reported to the EMS. Two additional cases (one case cystic, one of alveolar echinococcosis) were reported as not laboratory confirmed (not contained in tables).

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Alveolar echinococcosis: Due to the infestation rates of red foxes in Austria (0-40 %) there is a relatively elevated risk for hunters, cat owners and farmers.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Tools for preventive serological screening of hunters (and also other persons) have been established to detect *Echinococcus multilocularis* infections in an early stage. The early detection of the infection is the prerequisite for a successful curative treatment.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.9.2. Echinococcosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Echinococcosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Not relevant for surveillance purposes

Diagnostic criteria

At least one of the following five findings:

- Histopathology or parasitology compatible with *Echinococcus multilocularis* or *granulosus* (e.g. direct visualisation of the protoscolex in cyst fluid)
- Detection of *Echinococcus granulosus* pathognomonic macroscopic morphology of cyst(s) in surgical specimens
- Typical organ lesions detected by imaging techniques (e.g.: computerised tomography, sonography, MRI) AND confirmed by a serological test
- *Echinococcus* spp. specific serum antibodies by high-sensitivity serological test AND confirmed by a high specificity serological test

- Detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* or *granulosus* nucleic acid in a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- NA

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the diagnostic criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot technique, participant of the UK National External Quality Assessment Service for Microbiology, National Reference Laboratory for Echinococcosis.

Notification system in place

Notification of echinococcosis according to the Federeal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

- Alveolar echinococcosis has been known in Austria since 1897; annual incidence (1897- 2004): 0-6 cases, mean incidence: 2.4 cases/year (only autochthonous cases); geographic distribution in Austria: mainly in the western provinces (Vorarlberg, Tyrol, Salzburg), but cases have been reported in every province; outbreaks are not known.
- Cystic echinococcosis has been known in Austria at least since 1819; Cases of cystic echinococcosis have been registered in the Clinical Institute of Hygiene and Medical Microbiology (Medical University Vienna) regularly since the beginning of the 1980ies. Annual incidence (1984 - 2006): 20 - 60 cases; mean incidence: 31 cases per year, one third of patients are of Austrian origin; two thirds are from abroad. Geographic distribution in Austria is unknown; a few autochthonous infections could be observed mainly in the eastern and southern provinces (Lower Austria, Burgenland, and Styria); outbreaks are not known.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

- Alveolar echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: fox faeces (contaminated hands and fingers, vegetables, water).
- Cystic echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: dog faeces, presumably in a very few foci (in or around farmers houses)

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Low incidence of both forms of echinococcosis

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 104 Echinococcosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2012

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochtone cases	imported cases	unknown
Echinococcosis	3	0.03	1	1	1
E. granulosus	2	0.02	1	1	-
E. multilocularis	1	0.01	-	-	1

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

Table 105 Echinococcosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2012

Age group	Echinococcosis			<i>E. multilocularis</i>			<i>E. granulosus</i>		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
45 to 64 years	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
65 years and older	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	3	2	1	1	1	0	2	1	1

Data source: EMS as of April 28, 2013

4.9.3. Echinococcus in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all in abattoirs slaughtered animals; the sampling is performed by competent authorities in course of the post-mortem meat inspection; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered animal

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption

Case definition

Each carcass in which cysts, cystic or alveolar hydatids are detected in muscles or organs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption were visually inspected, palpated and cuttings were performed

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Post-mortem meat inspection act according to BGBl. 1982/522, Fleischuntersuchungsgesetz, as amended

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Cystic or alveolar echinococcosis in animals that are used for food production do not play a role for the infection of humans; it is primarily a hygienic problem.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 106 Echinococcus sp. in animals, 2012

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Echinococcus spp.	<i>E. multilocularis</i>	<i>E. granulosus</i>	<i>Echinococcus</i> spp., unspecified
Cattle*	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	679,772	135			135
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	130,756	278			278
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	5,147	0			0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	5,396,345	0			0

* cattle including calves

All detected cysts are reported as echinococcus but not differentiated (could also be other species than *Echinococcus* spp.).

x: Central Veterinary Services, Statistics Austria

4.10. Toxoplasmosis

4.10.1. General evaluation

Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable. Samples from pregnant women (amniotic liquor) in Austria are tested in the Toxoplasmosis-Laboratory via PCR. If toxoplasma is detected, umbilical cord blood is tested as a kind of quality control. Neonates from infected mothers are controlled as follow-up.

4.10.2. Toxoplasma in humans

Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable. Samples from pregnant women (amniotic liquor) in Austria are tested in the Toxoplasmosis-Laboratory via PCR. If toxoplasma is detected, umbilical cord blood is tested as a kind of quality control. Neonates from infected mothers are controlled as follow-up.

4.10.3. Toxoplasma in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Toxoplasma* spp. in animals. Sampling of cattle, sheep, goats or pigs is performed depending on clinical suspicion of toxoplasmosis and if ordered by the sender in cases after abortion. Other animal species are also occasionally sampled.

Frequency of the sampling

In case of clinical suspicion and abortion and if ordered.

Type of specimen taken

Blood, organ, faeces

Case definition

A case is defined as an animal that tested positive serologically ($\geq 1:40$) or if the pathogen is detected microscopically. The animal is the epidemiological unit.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic methods used for serology is the microagglutination test.

Vaccination policy:

No vaccination

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place:

Control programme/ mechanisms:

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases:**Notification system in place:**

Toxoplasmosis is not notifiable in animals.

Results of the investigation

see table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection:

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection):**Additional information**

Nil

Table 107 Toxoplasmosis in animals, 2012

animal species	sampling context	sampling details	sampling unit	Source of information	Units tested	Total units positive for Toxoplasma
cat	clinical investigation	organs	animal	AGES IVET	2	0
cattle	clinical investigation	blood	animal	AGES IVET	18	1
sheep	clinical investigation	blood	animal	AGES IVET	41	31
sheep	clinical investigation	organs	animal	AGES IVET	9	0
goat	clinical investigation	blood	animal	AGES IVET	29	4
goat	clinical investigation	organs	animal	AGES IVET	1	0

4.11. Rabies

4.11.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Rabies in humans was a major public health issue in the 1960s.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2012, there was no case of rabies detected in animals in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2012, vaccination programmes were carried out in fox populations in areas of higher risk.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Nil

4.11.2. Rabies in humans

Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with an acute encephalomyelitis

AND

At least two of the following seven symptoms:

- Sensory changes referred to the site of a preceding animal bite
- Paresis or paralysis
- Spasms of swallowing muscles
- Hydrophobia
- Delirium
- Convulsions
- Anxiety

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following four:

- Isolation of Lyssa virus from a clinical specimen
- Detection of Lyssa virus nucleic acid in a clinical specimen (e.g. saliva or brain tissue)
- Detection of viral antigens by a DFA in a clinical specimen
- Lyssa virus specific antibody response by virus isneutralisation assay in serum or CSF

Laboratory results need to be interpreted according to the vaccination or immunisation status

Case classification

Possible case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Liquor, smears from pharynx, swab from conjunctivae biopsy at the nape of the neck and serum were examined in the fluorescent antibody test (FAT), immunohistochemistry and RT-PCR (Ito M., Itou T., Sakai T., et al. (2001). Detection of Rabies Virus RNA isolated from several species of animals in Brazil by RT-PCR. Journal of Veterinary medicine Science 63(12): 1309-1313.).

Notification system in place

Notification of rabies according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Nil

Table 108 Rabies in humans, 2012

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Rabies	0	0	0	0
Human expose	0	0	0	0

Data source: NRL Rabies as of April 28, 2013

4.11.3. Lyssavirus (rabies) in animals

A. Rabies virus in animal - Wildlife - foxes

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy**

According to Fuchs-Tollwutbekämpfungsverordnung, BGBl II 2010/329: 8 foxes per 100 km² in rabies infected and rabies endangered areas, 4 foxes per 100 km² in not endangered and free areas (definition of areas).

Frequency of the sampling

8 foxes per 100 km² in rabies infested and rabies endangered areas, 4 foxes per 100km² in not endangered and free areas.

Type of specimen taken

Brain (brain stem or hippocampus)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Whole animals or heads of the dead animals are sent to the laboratories; sometimes brain tissue (derived from other laboratories). Brain tissue (e.g. 1 cm²) is examined.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody test (FAT) shows a positive signal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT (mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Delivery of vaccine containing baits in the southern part of East Tyrol, Carinthia, Styria and Burgenland; the requirement is 25 baits/km² in an area of approximately 5,620 km².

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Fuchs-Tollwutbekämpfungsverordnung 2010 BGBl II 2010/329, Tierseuchengesetz TSG RgBl 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76 TSG-DVO zum IV. Abschnitt Wutkrankheiten.

Control of vaccination: Detection of tetracycline in jaw bones of randomly chosen foxes from the vaccination area; additionally an ELISA is performed to proof seroconversion.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Baits-distribution is done by plane; recommendation of vaccination for dogs and cats in the southern border area and public awareness through BMGs (FMH) homepage.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Probably the reduction of the number of the animals (foxes) for investigation.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RgBl 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, and vaccination of the fox population.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RgBl 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Austria is declared as rabies free since 28.9.2008.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

B. Rabies virus in animal - all animals except foxes

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Sampling is targeted when animals are observed with central nerval symptoms or after biting a person. The suspicious animal is killed or euthanized and the carcass or head is sent to the laboratory.

Frequency of the sampling

If a case is suspected

Type of specimen taken

Brain (hippocampus and brain stem)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Routinely a sample will be taken from one site of the brain: a part from the hippocampus, brain stem or cerebellum. If an animal has bitten a person then 2 parts from the brain will be taken: hippocampus and brain stem.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody tests (FAT) or the rabies tissue culture infection test or the mouse inoculation test show a positive result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT (mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Voluntary vaccination of pets.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42;

Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42. If a rabies suspicious pet bites a person, the person is treated.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

On 28th of September 2008, Austria has been declared free of rabies.
Vaccination areas, rabies endangered and rabies free areas were redefined.

Table 109 Rabies in animals, 2012

Animal species	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Lyssa virus (rabies)
Cattle	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	11	0
Sheep	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain		1	0
Goats	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	1	0
Domestic solipeds	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	1	0
Dogs	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	53	0
Cats	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	58	0
Wildlife							
Bats-wild, passive surveillance	NRL	Found dead	not applicable	brain	Animal	17	0
Foxes- wild, monitoring	NRL	monitoring	official sampling	brain	Animal	2,747	0
Foxes	NRL	clinical suspect	not applicable	brain	Animal	95	0
Other farm, wild or pet animals (please add the relevant species)							
Badgers	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	6	0
Martens	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	26	0
other mustelide	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	4	0
Wild boar	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	1	0
Deer	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	2	0
Chamois	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	1	0
Others (e.g. squirreles, mice, rats)	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	4	0

Immunofluorescence antibody test (IFAT)

Data source: NRL Rabies as of 26.04.2013

4.12. Q-Fever

4.12.1. General evaluation of the situation

No information

4.12.2. Q-fever in humans

Not notifiable in Austria, therefore no data available

4.12.3. *Coxiella burnetii* in animals

Not notifiable in Austria

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Coxiella burnetii* in animals.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic method is the complement fixation reaction, detecting phase 1 and phase 2 antigens. Organs and swabs are tested by real time PCR.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place:

Nil

Control programme/ mechanisms

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Notification system in place

Q-fever in animals is not a notifiable disease

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Q-fever in humans is not a notifiable disease. In Austria the number of sheep per holding is low (3.9 animals per holding in average) compared to countries that have a problem with Q-fever; therefore no change of the epidemiological situation in Austria is expected.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

Table 110 Q-fever in animals, 2012

Animal species	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Analytical method	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Coxiella</i> (Q-fever)
Cattle								
Cattle, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES	suspect sampling	official sampling	blood	KBR	animal	508	13
Cattle, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES	suspect sampling	official sampling	blood	ELISA	animal	5	0
Cattle, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES	suspect sampling	official sampling	swabs, organs	PCR	animal	4	0
Sheep								
Sheep, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES	suspect sampling	official sampling	blood	KBR	animal	1120	6
Sheep, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES	suspect sampling	official sampling	swabs, organs	PCR	animal	5	0
Goats								
Goats, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES	suspect sampling	official sampling	blood	KBR	animal	46	3
Goats, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES	suspect sampling	official sampling	swabs, organs	PCR	animal	4	0

5. Information on Specific Indicators of Antimicrobial Resistance

5.1. E. coli Indicators

5.1.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004 and has been continued annually.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of antimicrobial resistance of E. coli in broiler slaughter batches, bovine animals and pigs has been implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Order Überwachungsprogramme-Verordnung (as amended). The sampling was carried out from January to December 2012 in slaughterhouses.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Europe wide harmonized standards for antimicrobial resistance monitoring are be highly welcome.

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

5.1.2. Antimicrobial resistance in Escherichia coli isolates

A. Antimicrobial resistance of E. coli in animal - All animals - farmed - at slaughterhouse - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

A sampling plan was created according to the federal monitoring program „ Durchführungserlass Zoonosenmonitoring 2012 - Überwachung ausgewählter Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen (BMG-74600/0262-II/B/10/2011)“. The sampling plan for E. coli included cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches. In 2012 for the first time three unique sampling plans were calculated for each of three age groups of cattle: one for calves, one for young cattle and one for cattle older than 2 years.

Type of specimen taken

E. coli was isolated from the caecum of slaughtered cattle (one sampling plan for each age group), pigs and broiler. The caecum from one bovine or pig or the whole intestines from ten slaughtered broilers within a single slaughter batch at each slaughterhouse were collected.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The intestines were refrigerated to 4 °C and samples were sent to the Institute of Veterinary Disease Control (IVET) in Graz, where each pathogen was isolated and further characterized. The national Reference Lab for antimicrobial resistance in the Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz performed the antimicrobial susceptibility testing for all strains.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

The number of samples was calculated by experts of the Division for Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES based on the expected prevalence of E. coli among the different animal species or age groups (cattle-calves, young cattle, cattle older than 2 years; pigs, broiler flocks). All isolated strains of E. coli were sent to the IMED Graz for antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals and the sampled slaughterhouses were recorded in a questionnaire. In the laboratory, the data were entered into a database and later analysed in Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The intestinal contents are streaked onto the MacConkey-agar plates (Merck Nr. 1.05465) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The process is repeated for colonies which are suspected for E. coli. These colonies are streaked onto a blood-agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The confirmation of the identification of E. coli is done with an oxidase- (Merck Nr. 1.13300.0001) and spot indol test (Remel, Nr. R8309002).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

E. coli samples isolated from cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches are tested for antimicrobial susceptibility against gentamicin, kanamycin, streptomycin, ceftotaxim, sulfamethoxazol, trimethoprim, ciprofloxacin, nalidixin acid, ampicillin, chloramphenicol and tetracycline.

Breakpoints used in testing

EUCAST

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

None

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

None

Results of the investigation

See respective tables.

National evaluation of the recent situation

Resistance rates in *E. coli* from broiler are high for some antimicrobials, e.g. fluroquinolones, streptomycin, ampicillin, nalidixic acid, sulfamethoxazol, tetracycline and trimethoprim and from pigs for streptomycin and tetracycline. In cattle low resistance rates a found. A census on the use of antimicrobials in veterinary medicine is planed.

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

Table 111 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *E. coli* in animals, 2012

Test method used: Broth dilution		Number of reporting laboratory: 1	
Standards used for testing		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from	
CLSI		Feedingstuff	-
EUCAST		Animals	x
		Food	-
		Humans	-
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Standard	Dilution method Cut-off value concentration (µg/ml) Resistant >	Diffusion method Cut-off value Zone diameter (mm) Resistant <=
Aminoglycosides			
Gentamicin	EUCAST	2	-
Streptomycin	EUCAST	16	-
Amphenicol			
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	16	-
Cephalosporins			
Cefotaxim	EUCAST	0.25	-
Ceftazidime	EUCAST	0.5	-
Fluroquinolones			
Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	0.06	-
Penicillins			
Ampicillin	EUCAST	8	-
Quinolones			
Nalidixic acid	EUCAST	16	-
Sulfonamides			
	EUCAST	64	-
Tetracyclines			
Tetracycline	EUCAST	8	-
Trimethoprim			
	EUCAST	2	-
Carbapeneme			
Meropenem	EUCAST	0.12	-

Table 112 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in animals (qualitative tables), 2012

<i>E. coli</i>															
	Gallus Gallus			Calves			young cattle (1-2 years)			cattle > 2 years			Pigs		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	130			151			73			49			140		
Antimicrobials:	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	130	0.8%	1	151	1.3%	2	73	0.0%	0	49	0.0%	0	140	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	130	42.3%	55	151	18.5%	28	73	5.5%	4	49	4.1%	2	140	52.1%	73
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	130	8.5%	11	151	3.3%	5	73	0.0%	0	49	2.0%	1	140	2.1%	3
Carbapenems - Meropenem	130	0.0%	0	151	0.0%	0	73	0.0%	0	49	0.0%	0	140	0.0%	0
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	130	3.1%	4	151	1.3%	2	73	0.0%	0	49	0.0%	0	140	0.0%	0
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	130	3.1%	4	151	0.7%	1	73	0.0%	0	49	0.0%	0	140	0.0%	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	130	65.4%	85	151	3.3%	5	73	0.0%	0	49	0.0%	0	140	4.3%	6
Penicillins - Ampicillin	130	26.9%	35	151	10.6%	16	73	0.0%	0	49	0.0%	0	140	12.9%	18
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	130	65.4%	85	151	3.3%	5	73	0.0%	0	49	0.0%	0	140	5.0%	7
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	130	44.6%	58	151	17.2%	26	73	4.1%	3	49	4.1%	2	140	22.9%	32
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	130	30.8%	40	151	22.5%	34	73	5.5%	4	49	4.1%	2	140	50.7%	71
Trimethoprim	130	25.4%	33	151	6.6%	10	73	2.7%	2	49	0.0%	0	140	10.0%	14
Number of multiresistant isolates															
fully sensitive	130	16.9%	22	151	74.2%	112	73	94.5%	69	49	93.9%	46	140	37.1%	52
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	130	23.1%	30	151	4.6%	7	73	0.0%	0	49	2.0%	1	140	15.7%	22
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	130	16.9%	22	151	4.0%	6	73	0.0%	0	49	0.0%	0	140	22.9%	32
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	130	10.0%	13	151	7.3%	11	73	4.1%	3	49	4.1%	2	140	12.9%	18
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	130	16.9%	22	151	5.3%	8	73	1.4%	1	49	0.0%	0	140	4.3%	6
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	130	16.2%	21	151	4.6%	7	73	0.0%	0	49	0.0%	0	140	7.1%	10

N = number of isolates tested

n = number of resistant isolates

r% = % isolates resistant

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For E. coli this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazol

Table 113 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme – active monitoring (slaughter batch) - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

		<i>E.coli</i> Gallus gallus, broiler		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		130																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	130	0.8%	1						1	36	89	3			1									
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	130	42.3%	55										16	49	10	8	17	7	23					
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	130	8.5%	11									2	25	84	8	1	2	8						
Carbapenems - Meropenem	130	0.0%	0	96	34																			
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	130	3.1%	4				102	22	2	1	1	1				1								
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	130	3.1%	4					87	38	1	2			1	1									
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	130	65.4%	85	2	35	8		4	36	24	13	4	4											
Penicillins - Ampicillin	130	26.9%	35								5	39	48	3			35							
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	130	65.4%	85									38	7				15	31	39					
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	130	44.6%	58											12	39	19	2				58			
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	130	30.8%	40								11	76	3			1	39							
Trimethoprim	130	25.4%	33					51	43	3			1		32									

Table 114 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in Calves (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

		<i>E.coli</i> Calves		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		151																					
Antimicrobials:	N	n		=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n	n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	151	1.3%	2						50	96	3				2								
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	151	18.5%	28										24	98	1	3	9	6	10				
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	151	3.3%	5									1	37	98	10			5					
Carbapenems - Meropenem	151	0.0%	0	88	63																		
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	151	1.3%	2				134	14	1	1						1							
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	151	0.7%	1					118	32			1											
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	151	3.3%	5	14	118	13	1		1	1				3									
Penicillins - Ampicillin	151	10.6%	16								4	46	79	6			16						
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	151	3.3%	5									104	42			1			4				
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	151	17.2%	26											31	54	34	6			26			
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	151	22.5%	34								20	93	3	1		1	33						
Trimethoprim	151	6.6%	10						56	74	11				10								

Table 115 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in Cattle 1-2 years (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

		<i>E.coli</i> Cattle 1-2 years		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		73																					
Antimicrobials:	N		n	=<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n	=																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	73	0.0%	0						1	22	50												
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	73	5.5%	4											19	50		1	2		1			
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	73	0.0%	0										11	60	2								
Carbapenems - Meropenem	73	0.0%	0		41	32																	
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	73	0.0%	0				66	7															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	73	0.0%	0					47	24	2													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	73	0.0%	0	5	61	7																	
Penicillins - Ampicillin	73	0.0%	0										30	42	1								
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	73	0.0%	0									49	24										
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	73	4.1%	3											11	30	21	8				3		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	73	5.5%	4								8	57	4				4						
Trimethoprim	73	2.7%	2						32	34	5				2								

Table 116 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in Cattle > 2 years (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

		<i>E.coli</i> Cattle > 2 years		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		49																					
Antimicrobials:	N	n		=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	49	0.0%	0						13		34	2											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	49	4.1%	2										12	34	1				2				
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	49	2.0%	1										15	29	4				1				
Carbapenems - Meropenem	49	0.0%	0	1	32	15	1																
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	49	0.0%	0				41	8															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	49	0.0%	0					34	14	1													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	49	0.0%	0	4	31	14																	
Penicillins - Ampicillin	49	0.0%	0								2	15	28	4									
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	49	0.0%	0									35	12	2									
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	49	4.1%	2											16	16	14	1				2		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	49	4.1%	2								12	32	3				2						
Trimethoprim	49	0.0%	0						25	19	5												

Table 117 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

		<i>E.coli</i> Pigs		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		140																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	140	0.0%	0							17	117	6												
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	140	52.1%	73										9	54	4	12	22	26	13					
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	140	2.1%	3									1	43	91	2	1	1	1						
Carbapenems - Meropenem	140	0.0%	0	98	42																			
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	140	0.0%	0				134	6																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	140	0.0%	0					103	35	2														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	140	4.3%	6	20	94	19	1		1	1				4										
Penicillins - Ampicillin	140	12.9%	18								7	51	60	4			18							
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	140	5.0%	7									102	31			1			6					
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	140	22.9%	32											33	45	22	8	1	31					
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	140	50.7%	71								13	53	2	1	2	2	67							
Trimethoprim	140	10.0%	14						56	68	2				14									

5.2. Enterococcus Indicators

5.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004 and continued in 2012.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of antimicrobial resistance of Enterococcus in broiler slaughter batches, bovine animals and pigs has been implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Order Überwachungsprogramme-Verordnung (as amended). The sampling was carried out from January to December 2012 in slaughterhouses.

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Europe wide harmonized standards for antimicrobial resistance monitoring would be highly welcome.

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

5.2.2. Antimicrobial resistance in Enterococcus spp. isolates

A. Antimicrobial resistance of Enterococcus spp. in animal - All animals - farmed - at slaughterhouse - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

A sampling plan was created according to the federal monitoring program „Durchführungserlass Zoonosenmonitoring 2012 - Überwachung ausgewählter Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen (BMG-74600/0262-II/B/10/2011)“. The sampling plan for enterococci includes cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches. In 2012 for the first time three unique sampling plans were calculated for each of three age groups of cattle: one for calves, one for young cattle and one for cattle older than 2 years.

Type of specimen taken

Enterococci are isolated from the caecum of slaughtered cattle (one sampling plan for each age group), pigs and broiler. The caecum from one cow or pig or the whole intestines from ten slaughtered broilers within a single slaughter batch at each slaughterhouse are collected.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The intestines were refrigerated to 4 °C and samples were sent to the Institute of Veterinary Disease Control (IVET) in Graz, where each pathogen was isolated and further characterized. The Institute of

Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz performed the antimicrobial susceptibility testing for all strains.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

The number of samples was calculated by experts of the Division for Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES based on the expected prevalence of *Enterococcus faecalis* and *E. faecium* in the different animal species or age groups (cattle-calves, young cattle, cattle older than 2 years; pigs, broiler flocks). From each sample up to five enterococci were differentiated. Only *E. faecalis* and *E. faecium* strains were sent to the IMED Graz for antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals and the sampled slaughterhouses were recorded in a questionnaire. In the laboratory, the data were entered into a database and later analysed in Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Approximately 1 g of the samples are enriched in brain-heart infusion bouillon for 17-22 hours at 37°C ±1°C. A few drops of the enrichment from cattle or pigs are cultured on Citrate Azide Tween Carbonate agar (CATC-AGAR, Merck Art.Nr. 1.10279) and from poultry on Slanetz agar and incubated at 37 °C ± 1°C for 48 h. Potential colonies are subcultivated on blood agar (COS) for 24 h at 37 ±1 °C followed by subcultivation on Mueller Hinton agar the differentiation of *E. faecalis* and *E. faecium* is performed using Gram's staining method, Catalase Test, Arabinose- and Pyruvate-breakdown.

Laboratory used for detection for resistance

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

E. faecalis/faecium samples isolated from cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches are tested for antimicrobial resistance against gentamicin, streptomycin, vancomycin, ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, linezolid, ampicillin, chloramphenicol, daptomycin, tetracycline, tigecycline and daptomycin.

Breakpoints used in testing

EUCAST

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

None

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

None

Results of the investigation

See respective tables.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Resistance rates in isolates from cattle are generally low. High levels of resistance can be found in *E. faecalis* from pigs against erythromycin and tetracycline, from broilers against erythromycin and tetracycline and streptomycin, and calves against streptomycin and tetracycline, and in *E. faecium* from broilers against erythromycin and tetracycline and pigs and calves against erythromycin.

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

Table 118 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *Enterococcus faecalis* in animals, 2012

Test method used: Broth dilution		Number of reporting laboratory: 1	
Standards used for testing		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from	
	CLSI	Feedingstuff	-
	EUCAST	Animals	x
		Food	-
		Humans	-
		Dilution method	Diffusion method
		Cut-off value	Cut-off value
		concentration (µg/ml)	Zone diameter (mm)
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	Standard	Resistant >	Resistant <=
Aminoglycosides			
	Gentamicin	EUCAST	32
	Streptomycin	EUCAST	512
Amphenicol			
	Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	32
Cyclic Lipopeptides			
	Daptomycin	EUCAST	4
Fluoroquinolones			
	Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	4
Penicillins			
	Ampicillin	EUCAST	4
Glycopeptides			
	Vancomycin	EUCAST	4
	Teicoplanin	EUCAST	2
Macrolides			
	Erythromycin	EUCAST	4
Tetracyclines			
	Tetracycline	EUCAST	4
Oxacolidinone			
	Linezolid	EUCAST	4

Table 119 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in animals (qualitative tables), 2012

<i>E. faecalis</i>															
	Gallus Gallus			Calves			Young cattle (1-2 years)			Cattle > 2 years			Pigs		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	38			103			110			105			94		
Antimicrobials:	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	38	0.0%	0	103	2.9%	3	110	0.0%	0	105	0.0%	0	94	7.4%	7
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	38	31.6%	12	103	26.2%	27	110	4.5%	5	105	5.7%	6	94	19.1%	18
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	38	13.2%	5	103	9.7%	10	110	0.9%	1	105	1.0%	1	94	8.5%	8
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	38	0.0%	0	103	0.0%	0	110	0.0%	0	105	0.0%	0	94	0.0%	0
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Daptomycin	38	0.0%	0	103	1.0%	1	110	0.9%	1	105	1.0%	1	94	0.0%	0
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Teicoplanin	38	0.0%	0	103	0.0%	0	110	0.0%	0	105	0.0%	0	94	0.0%	0
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Vancomycin	38	0.0%	0	103	0.0%	0	110	0.0%	0	105	0.0%	0	94	0.0%	0
Macrolides - Erythromycin	38	57.9%	22	103	13.6%	14	110	8.2%	9	105	4.8%	5	94	24.5%	23
Oxazolidines - Linezolid	38	0.0%	0	103	0.0%	0	110	0.0%	0	105	0.0%	0	94	0.0%	0
Penicillins - Ampicillin	38	0.0%	0	103	0.0%	0	110	0.0%	0	105	0.0%	0	94	0.0%	0
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	38	57.9%	22	103	49.5%	51	110	19.1%	21	105	23.8%	25	94	54.3%	51
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	38	26.3%	10	103	47.6%	49	110	75.5%	83	105	76.2%	80	94	43.6%	41
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	38	23.7%	9	103	26.2%	27	110	19.1%	21	105	15.2%	16	94	27.7%	26
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	38	26.3%	10	103	13.6%	14	110	2.7%	3	105	5.7%	6	94	11.7%	11
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	38	10.5%	4	103	1.9%	2	110	1.8%	2	105	1.9%	2	94	6.4%	6
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	38	13.2%	5	103	9.7%	10	110	0.9%	1	105	1.0%	1	94	9.6%	9
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	38	0.0%	0	103	1.0%	1	110	0.0%	0	105	0.0%	0	94	1.1%	1

N = number of isolates tested
n = number of resistant isolates
r% = % isolates resistant

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For enterococci this includes resistance to streptomycin, gentamicin, chloramphenicol, ampicillin, vancomycin, erythromycin, daptomycin, and tetracycline

Table 120 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in Calves (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

<i>E. faecalis</i> Calves		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	103																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	103	2.9%	3								7	50	43			2					1
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	103	26.2%	27											5	36	35					27
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	103	9.7%	10								27	64	2		8	1	1				
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	103	0.0%	0					28	64	10	1										
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Daptomycin	103	1.0%	1		2	1	12	55	30	2	1										
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Teicoplanin	103	0.0%	0				103														
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Vancomycin	103	0.0%	0						58	44	1										
Macrolides - Erythromycin	103	13.6%	14					11	28	29	21	1	1		12						
Oxazolidines - Linezolid	103	0.0%	0					1	20	82											
Penicillins - Ampicillin	103	0.0%	0				4	15	77	7											
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	103	49.5%	51					48	3		1		1	7	43						

Table 121 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in young Cattle (1-2 years) (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

<i>E. faecalis</i> Young cattle (1-2 years)		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	110																					
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	110	0.0%	0								3	38	67	2								
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	110	4.5%	5										1	1	40	62		1	1	4		
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	110	0.9%	1								18	91			1							
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	110	0.0%	0				3	13	76	16	2											
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Daptomycin	110	0.9%	1				1	3	37	55	13	1										
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Teicoplanin	110	0.0%	0				109	1														
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Vancomycin	110	0.0%	0						45	58	7											
Macrolides - Erythromycin	110	8.2%	9					27	10	32	32	4			5							
Oxazolidines - Linezolid	110	0.0%	0						7	102	1											
Penicillins - Ampicillin	110	0.0%	0				2	10	88	10												
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	110	19.1%	21					81	6	1	1	1	1	3	16							

Table 122 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in Cattle >2 years (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

				<i>E. faecalis</i> Cattle > 2 years																	
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				105																	
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																	
Antimicrobials:				<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	105	0.0%	0									34	69	2							
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	105	5.7%	6										1		38	58	2				6
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	105	1.0%	1								17	85	1	1	1						
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	105	0.0%	0			2	12	65	25	1											
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Daptomycin	105	1.0%	1				1	36	57	10	1										
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Teicoplanin	105	0.0%	0			105															
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Vancomycin	105	0.0%	0					57	47	1											
Macrolides - Erythromycin	105	4.8%	5				30	11	38	21					5						
Oxazolidines - Linezolid	105	0.0%	0					10	95												
Penicillins - Ampicillin	105	0.0%	0			3	8	86	8												
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	105	23.8%	25				74	6			1	2	2	20							

Table 123 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

<i>E. faecalis</i> PIGS		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	94																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	94	7.4%	7								1	20	65	1					3	4	
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	94	19.1%	18										1		33	42					18
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	94	8.5%	8								11	74		1	7	1					
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	94	0.0%	0				1	10	66	17											
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Daptomycin	94	0.0%	0					1	32	52	9										
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Teicoplanin	94	0.0%	0				93	1													
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Vancomycin	94	0.0%	0						73	20	1										
Macrolides - Erythromycin	94	24.5%	23					19	8	25	19	2			21						
Oxazolidines - Linezolid	94	0.0%	0						9	85											
Penicillins - Ampicillin	94	0.0%	0				1	4	79	10											
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	94	54.3%	51					41	2					1	50						

Table 124 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecalis* in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

<i>E. faecalis</i> GALLUS GALLUS		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	38																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	38	0.0%	0								2	28	8								
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	38	31.6%	12											3	20	3					12
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	38	13.2%	5								13	19	1		5						
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	38	0.0%	0					13	20	4	1										
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Daptomycin	38	0.0%	0			1		5	19	9	4										
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Teicoplanin	38	0.0%	0				38														
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Vancomycin	38	0.0%	0						27	11											
Macrolides - Erythromycin	38	57.9%	22					3	5	3	5	2		2	18						
Oxazolidines - Linezolid	38	0.0%	0					2	20	16											
Penicillins - Ampicillin	38	0.0%	0				2	7	21	5	3										
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	38	57.9%	22					15	1					4	18						

Table 125 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *Enterococcus faecium* in animals, 2012

Test method used: Broth dilution		Number of reporting laboratory: 1	
Standards used for testing		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from	
	CLSI	Feedingstuff	-
	EUCAST	Animals	x
		Food	-
		Humans	-
		Dilution method Cut-off value concentration (µg/ml) Resistant >	Diffusion method Cut-off value Zone diameter (mm) Resistant <=
<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	Standard		
Aminoglycosides			
	Gentamicin	EUCAST	32
	Streptomycin	EUCAST	128
Amphenicol			
	Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	32
Cyclic Lipopeptides			
	Daptomycin	EUCAST	4
Fluoroquinolones			
	Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	4
Penicillins			
	Ampicillin	EUCAST	4
Glycopeptides			
	Vancomycin	EUCAST	4
	Teicoplanin	EUCAST	2
Macrolides			
	Erythromycin	EUCAST	4
Tetracyclines			
	Tetracycline	EUCAST	4
Oxacolidinone			
	Linezolid	EUCAST	4
Streptogramins			
	Synercid	EUCAST	1

Table 126 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in animals (qualitative tables), 2012

<i>E. faecium</i>															
	Gallus Gallus			Calves			Young cattle (1-2 years)			Cattle > 2 years			Pigs		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	92			16			40			45			50		
Antimicrobials:	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	92	0.0%	0	16	0.0%	0	40	0.0%	0	45	0.0%	0	50	4.0%	2
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	92	13.0%	12	16	6.3%	1	40	5.0%	2	45	0.0%	0	50	4.0%	2
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	92	1.1%	1	16	0.0%	0	40	0.0%	0	45	0.0%	0	50	0.0%	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	92	3.3%	3	16	0.0%	0	40	5.0%	2	45	2.2%	1	50	0.0%	0
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Daptomycin	92	0.0%	0	16	0.0%	0	40	0.0%	0	45	6.7%	3	50	0.0%	0
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Teicoplanin	92	0.0%	0	16	0.0%	0	40	0.0%	0	45	0.0%	0	50	0.0%	0
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Vancomycin	92	0.0%	0	16	0.0%	0	40	0.0%	0	45	0.0%	0	50	0.0%	0
Macrolides - Erythromycin	92	40.2%	37	16	43.8%	7	40	20.0%	8	45	15.6%	7	50	38.0%	19
Oxazolidines - Linezolid	92	0.0%	0	16	0.0%	0	40	0.0%	0	45	0.0%	0	50	0.0%	0
Penicillins - Ampicillin	92	3.3%	3	16	0.0%	0	40	0.0%	0	45	0.0%	0	50	0.0%	0
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	92	52.2%	48	16	18.8%	3	40	12.5%	5	45	11.1%	5	50	22.0%	11
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	92	31.5%	29	16	43.8%	7	40	70.0%	28	45	71.1%	32	50	50.0%	25
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	92	37.0%	34	16	50.0%	8	40	25.0%	10	45	24.4%	11	50	40.0%	20
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	92	21.7%	20	16	0.0%	0	40	2.5%	1	45	4.4%	2	50	6.0%	3
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	92	9.8%	9	16	6.3%	1	40	2.5%	1	45	0.0%	0	50	0.0%	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	92	0.0%	0	16	0.0%	0	40	0.0%	0	45	0.0%	0	50	4.0%	2
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	92	1.1%	1	16	0.0%	0	40	7.5%	3	45	0.0%	0	50	0.0%	0

N = number of isolates tested

n = number of resistant isolates

r% = % isolates resistant

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For enterococci this includes resistance to streptomycin, gentamicin, chloramphenicol, ampicillin, vancomycin, erythromycin, daptomycin, tetracyclin.

Table 127 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in Calves (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

<i>E. faecium</i> Calves		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	16																					
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	16	0.0%	0								2	13	1									
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	16	6.3%	1											5	9	1					1	
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	16	0.0%	0								1	15										
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	16	0.0%	0					6	3	3	4											
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Daptomycin	16	0.0%	0						2	4	10											
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Teicoplanin	16	0.0%	0				11	5														
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Vancomycin	16	0.0%	0						13	3												
Macrolides - Erythromycin	16	43.8%	7					1	1	1	6	7										
Oxazolidines - Linezolid	16	0.0%	0							16												
Penicillins - Ampicillin	16	0.0%	0						13	3												
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	16	18.8%	3					13							3							

Table 128 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in young Cattle (1-2 years) (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

<i>E. faecium</i> Young cattle (1-2 years)																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	40	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	40	0.0%	0								10	23	7									
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	40	5.0%	2										1	14	23						2	
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	40	0.0%	0								7	33										
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	40	5.0%	2				1	3	5	4	25	2										
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Daptomycin	40	0.0%	0							13	27											
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Teicoplanin	40	0.0%	0				16	24														
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Vancomycin	40	0.0%	0						36	4												
Macrolides - Erythromycin	40	20.0%	8						1	5	26	7			1							
Oxazolidines - Linezolid	40	0.0%	0						1	38	1											
Penicillins - Ampicillin	40	0.0%	0					3	24	12	1											
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	40	12.5%	5				35							1	4							

Table 129 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in Cattle >2 years (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

<i>E. faecium</i> Cattle > 2 years		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	45																					
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	45	0.0%	0								11	27	7									
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	45	0.0%	0										2	13	26	4						
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	45	0.0%	0								6	39										
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	45	2.2%	1						5	13	26	1										
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Daptomycin	45	6.7%	3					1	4	15	22	3										
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Teicoplanin	45	0.0%	0				25	19	1													
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Vancomycin	45	0.0%	0						38	6	1											
Macrolides - Erythromycin	45	15.6%	7					3	2	10	23	6				1						
Oxazolidines - Linezolid	45	0.0%	0							43	2											
Penicillins - Ampicillin	45	0.0%	0				2	4	25	13	1											
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	45	11.1%	5					38	2						1	4						

Table 130 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

		<i>E. faecium</i> PIGS																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		50																			
		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	50	4.0%	2								9	33	6							2	
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	50	4.0%	2											13	35						2
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	50	0.0%	0								5	45									
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	50	0.0%	0				1	11	23	6	9										
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Daptomycin	50	0.0%	0						1	14	35										
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Teicoplanin	50	0.0%	0				39	11													
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Vancomycin	50	0.0%	0						48	2											
Macrolides - Erythromycin	50	38.0%	19					1	3	2	25	14	3		2						
Oxazolidines - Linezolid	50	0.0%	0							49	1										
Penicillins - Ampicillin	50	0.0%	0				4	2	27	16	1										
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	50	22.0%	11					37	1	1				2	9						

Table 131 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. faecium* in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2012

<i>E. faecium</i> GALLUS GALLUS																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	92	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	92	0.0%	0								26	56	9	1								
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	92	13.0%	12										2	35	40	3				3	9	
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	92	1.1%	1								29	51	5	6			1					
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	92	3.3%	3					11	19	40	19	2		1								
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Daptomycin	92	0.0%	0					3	15	52	22											
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Teicoplanin	92	0.0%	0				86	6														
Glycopeptides (Cyclic peptides, Polypeptides) - Vancomycin	92	0.0%	0					87	5													
Macrolides - Erythromycin	92	40.2%	37				8	7	26	14	5	1	1	30								
Oxazolidines - Linezolid	92	0.0%	0					17	74	1												
Penicillins - Ampicillin	92	3.3%	3				6	7	42	17	17	2		1								
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	92	52.2%	48				41	3				1	4	4	39							

6. Foodborne outbreaks

Foodborne outbreaks are defined as two or more human cases of the same disease or infection where the cases are linked or are probably linked to the same food source. A situation in which the observed human cases exceed the expected number of cases and where a same food source is suspected, is also indicative of a foodborne outbreak.

A. Foodborne outbreaks

System in place for identification, epidemiological investigations and reporting of food borne outbreaks

Presently, every district (n = 95) is responsible for outbreak investigation. However, food borne outbreaks affecting more than one district or even more than one province (Austria = 9 provinces) are regulated by the Federal Zoonoses Act (Zoonosengesetz, BGBl. I, 128/2005 entered into force on 1. January 2006). The Federal Zoonoses Commission was founded to advise the Federal Minister to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria. One target of the Zoonoses Act is to ensure that foodborne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation. It regulates, in case of food borne outbreaks affecting more than one province that the governors of the affected provinces provide operative units to investigate possible or confirmed food borne outbreaks. Data concerning epidemiological criteria, potential implicated food items and the source of an outbreak must be collected and adequate epidemiological and microbiological examinations must be conducted. Short reports summarize each outbreak and must be communicated to the Federal Commission for Zoonoses and to AGES.

Description of the types of outbreaks covered by the reporting:

Since there has not been a coordinated approach for outbreak investigation in most provinces, the large majority (99 of 122) of food borne outbreaks are classified as household outbreaks. Coordinated investigation of outbreaks affecting more than one province - unhampered by district limits - will drastically decrease the total number of outbreaks.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country:

In 2012, 122 food borne outbreaks affecting 561 persons were reported. 97 persons were hospitalized and 0 person died. The total number of foodborne outbreaks decreased by 47 % compared to 2011. The average number of cases affected by an outbreak was 4.6 persons, ranging from two to 147 persons per outbreak. 14 % (13 % in 2011) of the reported outbreaks were acquired abroad. 53 % of all foodborne outbreaks acquired in Austria were caused by *Campylobacter* spp. (n=56), 41 % by *Salmonella* spp. (n=43) and only 51 % thereof by serotype Enteritidis (n=30) compared to (80 %) in 2011.

Relevance of the different causative agents, food categories and the agent/food category combinations

Campylobacter and *Salmonella* pose the most important agents causing 93 % of all foodborne outbreaks, similar as in 2011. The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks

The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Evaluation of the severity and clinical picture of the human cases

17.3 % of patients affected by these food borne outbreaks are reported as hospitalized (22.7 % in 2011); like in 2011, there occurred no deaths in association with outbreaks.

Control measures or other actions taken to improve the situation

Improvement due to the implementation of the Federal Zoonoses Act e.g. the chain of command in terms of investigation of foodborne outbreaks affecting more than one province was implemented.

Additional information

The situation of foodborne outbreaks are published in the National Zoonoses Brochure.

Table 132 Foodborne outbreaks with food vehicle identified and strong evidence (EMS), 2012

Outbreak ID	causative agent	agent category	causative agents1	causative agents2	nr. of outbreaks	outbreak type	foreign outbreak	number of human cases	number of hospitalisations	number of deaths	food vehicle	food suspected	food confirmed	nature of evidence	setting	place of origin of problem	origin of food vehicle	contributory factors
2812, 2085, 2480, 2581, 2582, 2586, 2599, 2589, 2587	Salmonella	Salmonella spp.	Stanley		1	General		147	10	0	Turkey meat and products thereof	no	yes	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans, Analytical epidemiological evidence	Mobile retailer, market/street vendor	at farm	Austria	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
2522	Salmonella	Salmonella spp.	Enteritidis	PT8	1	General		67	12	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	no	yes	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	Restaurant, Cafe, Pub, Bar, Hotel, Catering service	Restaurant, Cafe, Pub, Bar, Hotel,	Non EU	Cross-contamination
2455	STEC/VTEC		O113	H8	1	Household / domestic kitchen		3	0	0	Other or mixed red meat and products thereof	no	yes	Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	Household / domestic kitchen	at slaughterhouse	Austria	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient

Data source: EMS as of April 8, 2013

Table 133 Foodborne outbreaks with no food vehicle identified or weak evidence, 2012

		Outbreaks with no food vehicle identified or weak evidence			
		Number of Outbreaks	Number of Human Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths
Agents categories	Causative agents				
<i>Salmonella</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	10	25	5	0
	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	30	95	32	0
	Other serovars	11	28	2	0
<i>Campylobacter</i>		61	137	30	0
<i>Listeria</i>	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	2	5	5	0
	Other <i>Listeria</i>	0	0	0	0
<i>Yersinia</i>		0	0	0	0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> , pathogenic	Verotoxigenic <i>E. coli</i> (VTEC)	1	3	0	0
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>B. cereus</i>	0	0	0	0
	Other <i>Bacillus</i>	0	0	0	0
Staphylococcal enterotoxins		0	0	0	0
<i>Clostridium</i>	<i>Cl. botulinum</i>	0	0	0	0
	<i>Cl. perfringens</i>	0	0	0	0
	Other Clostridia	0	0	0	0
Other Bacterial agents	<i>Brucella</i>	0	0	0	0
	<i>Shigella</i>	0	0	0	0
	Other Bacterial agents	0	0	0	0
Parasites	<i>Trichinella</i>	0	0	0	0
	<i>Giardia</i>	0	0	0	0
	<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	0	0	0	0
	<i>Anisakis</i>	0	0	0	0
	Other Parasites	1	2	0	0
Viruses	Norovirus	2	47	1	0
	Hepatitis viruses	1	2	0	0
	Other Viruses	0	0	0	0
Other agents	Histamine	0	0	0	0
	Marine biotoxins	0	0	0	0
	Other Agents	0	0	0	0
Unknown agent		0	0	0	0

Data source: EMS as of April 8, 2013

Information on specific microbiological agents

6.1. Staphylococcal Enterotoxins

6.1.1. Staphylococcal enterotoxins general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

6.1.2. Staphylococcal enterotoxins in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

Detection of staphylococcal enterotoxins in food with coagulase positive Staphylococci exceeding 100 000 CFU/g

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Several food (e. g. icecream, meat, cheese, etc.) is tested for coagulase positive Staphylococci. If the number of detected Staphylococci exceeds 100 000 CFU/g, the food is further tested for staphylococcal enterotoxins. Therefore a screening ELISA for staphylococcal enterotoxins A-E is performed (commercially available Sandwich ELISA). For a positive screening result another ELISA reveals the toxin group with the detection limit of at least 10µg/kg.

All isolates and/or food samples are sent to the National Reference Laboratory in Graz, where the Enterotoxins A, B, C1, C2, C3, D, E are identified via an ELFA (enzyme linked fluorescent assay). RPLA (reverse passive latexagglutination) and ELISAs for further investigations on the Enterotoxins may complete the analysis.

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table below

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 134 Staphylococcal enterotoxins in food, 2012

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Staphylococcal enterotoxins	Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin, unspecified
Bakery products		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	19	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	39	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	7	2	2
		unspecified	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	11	1	1
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	3	1	1
Dairy products (excluding cheeses)		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	21	0	0
Fish		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	27	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - fresh		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	1	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	1	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - chilled		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	21	0	0
Meat from pig		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	32	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat preparation		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	30	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	2	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	2	0	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	32	0	0
Soups - ready-to-eat		unspecified	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	Gram	1	0	0

6.2. Cronobacter sakazakii

6.2.1. Cronobacter sakazakii in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method ISO 22964:2006

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table below

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 135 Cronobacter sakazakii in food, 2012

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Cronobacter sakazakii
Infant formula		at processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	100	Gram	5	0
		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	100	Gram	1	0
			CH	single (food/feed)	100	Gram	1	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	100	Gram	1	0
			HR	single (food/feed)	100	Gram	1	0
		unspecified	XX	single (food/feed)	100	Gram	1	0

6.3. Histamine

6.3.1. Histamine general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

6.3.2. Histamine in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Fish, fishery products, cheese

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

>200mg/kg for fish - fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured

>400mg/kg for fish - fishery products which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine

>400mg/kg for cheese

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

High performance liquid chromatography with UV detection; (HPLC-UV)

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

Not available

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the Community for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table below

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 136 Histamine in food, 2012

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units in non-conformity ≤ 100mg/kg	
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheep's milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		at retail	IT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0
Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured		unspecified	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0
			DE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
			PG	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
			PT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
			SI	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
			TH	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0
Fish - Fishery products which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine		unspecified	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0
Fish - raw		at border control	MV	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
		at retail	IT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
		unspecified	XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified		at retail	DK	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0
			ES	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
			PT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0
			SI	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
		unspecified	CN	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
Other food of non-animal origin		at retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0

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